

Time Reversal Breaking and Entropy Production in Non-Equilibrium Systems: Insights from Mean Back Relaxation

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¹This work is based on the authors bachelor thesis and not part of the dissertation

²This work is relevant for this thesis and cited in multiple places. However, no text or figures are taken from this article.

ABSTRACT

The distinction between equilibrium thermal fluctuations, exemplified by Brownian motion, and active non-equilibrium processes is an essential problem in various fields of non-equilibrium statistical physics and biophysics. While Brownian motion is created by the random collision of a colloidal particle with much smaller surrounding particles, many biological and artificial systems exhibit externally and self-driven motion, for example, induced by external energy sources and molecular motors. This thesis addresses the problem of differentiating these motion types by focusing on the breaking of time reversal symmetry, a hallmark of non-equilibrium dynamics.

We investigate a novel quantity, the mean back relaxation (MBR), to detect said time reversal symmetry breaking. The mean back relaxation is a three point correlation function and is defined as the negative ratio of the displacement between $[0, t]$ to the displacement from $[-\tau, 0]$. We find that the long time value of MBR approaches $\frac{1}{2}$ if later displacements get statistically independent from earlier ones, and if time reversal symmetry is valid. We demonstrate that MBR shows time reversal breakage for an active Brownian particle in a harmonic potential. We derive a solution for the finite time MBR for a Gaussian process in terms of the mean squared displacement (MSD) with a path integral formalism. This allows the analytic investigation of the time dependence of MBR curves in a Gaussian model. Also, we introduce a new density based MBR generalizing MBR to other types of observables. By analyzing the variance of the back relaxation (VBR), we characterize MBRs statistical properties and give estimates on how to select MBR parameters for practical applications.

Connecting MBR to fundamental concepts, we derive a new bound for entropy production, a central quantity in non-equilibrium dynamics. The bound is valid for time antisymmetric observables whose absolute value is bounded, and we find that the tightest observable is the sign of entropy production. This leads to an interesting coarse graining scheme that leaves the bound intact by grouping paths according to their stochastic entropy production. We test the entropy bound for a time discrete ring and compare it to other known relations.

We apply MBR to experimental data obtained from colloidal particles in living cells. We can qualitatively reconstruct the curves found from cell data with a Random Horse and Cart model. Both in the model and cell data for different cell types, the long time value of MBR is linearly related to effective energy amplitude, which quantifies the violations of the fluctuation dissipation theorem (FDT), a common indirect marker of breaking of time reversal symmetry.

Finally, we test the time reversal properties of MBR for cell data. We show that for colloidal particles in cells, MBR detects breaking of time reversal

symmetry. This is one of the first direct empirical evidences for observable time reversal breaking of colloidal particles in living cells. The time reversal breaking is greatly reduced by depolymerization of microtubules, which hints that the effect is linked to cytoskeletal activity. We also apply the entropy production bound by inserting the anti-symmetric part of MBR and find that the lower bound given by MBR is correlated to FDT violations for different cell types, quantified by the effective energy amplitude.

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1.

Introduction

1.1. Preamble

Merry and Pippin were having a glorious day. The two children were playing in some of their neighbor's corn fields. As they raced past each other, the corn plants, which were constantly swaying in the continuous wind, swirled around them. Also, once in a while, they met a scarecrow that they pushed around for fun. On the other side of the field, farmer Frank was having an awful day. Again, two of the neighboring children had hidden in one of his corn fields, ready to steal some of his precious harvest, as he was certain. But this time, he was determined to catch them red-handed. Looking down from his upstairs window, he could see every single field he owned. Sadly, his eyesight was not as good as it once was ¹. All the different corn plants merged into a large green and yellow surface. But there was something else. He could see the brown heads of the scarecrows dancing around. Most of them were very old and fragile, thus easily shaken by the wind. Suddenly, one of them moved. And then another one. And another one. He knew that the children liked to play with them, but how could he tell if the scarecrows were just pushed around by fluctuations in the wind or by the children's play?

Noticeably, Frank is facing the problem of distinguishing presumably passive fluctuations transmitted by the air molecules from an active driving of the scarecrows by the naughty kids. We can face a very similar problem if we look at small probe particles inside an active environment, as, for example, suspended probe particles inside the cytoplasm of living cells. Similar to the scarecrows, these particles are subject to thermal fluctuations and active processes inside the cell. However, it is not that easy to spot if active processes are present if one has only access to the coarse grained description of the comparatively large particles or scarecrows in the medium. If Frank had a better experimental resolution or eyesight, then he could observe the movement of the corn plants and maybe have a better chance of spotting the children. But even in this case, their uncovering would not be a given. So we are stuck to the highly coarse grained trajectories of the scarecrows or suspended particles and ask ourselves how we can detect active driving. For the suspended particles, we will see that time reversal symmetry of the trajectories will play an important role in distinguishing passive from actively driven motion. We then investigate if the novel observable mean back relaxation can show the violation of this symmetry, and try to connect it to the

¹Some people in the village argued that it never was actually any good.

Figure 1.1.: Sketch of a Brownian particle. The colloidal particle (gray) is suspended in a solution of smaller particles (blue). These particles randomly collide with the gray particle, triggering a random motion of the colloidal particle.

concept of entropy production. We will, however, begin by discussing why the particles fluctuate without active driving in the first place.

1.2. Brownian particles as model system

1.2.1. Brownian motion

In 1828 Robert Brown discovered by looking at pollen suspended in water using a microscope, that these particles exhibited an erratic and random motion [6]. As a big surprise at this time, the movement was visible both for organic and inorganic matter. This observation was very inspiring for many scientists of this time. The underlying theory was later worked out by Einstein and Smoluchowski (1905-1906) and experimentally confirmed by Perrin in 1908 [7–10]. The revolutionary idea was that the movement of the colloidal particles, which we define as small particles in the range from nanometers to a micron, was caused by random collisions with much smaller particles in the suspension, as illustrated in Fig. 1.1. These particles move much faster, resulting in chaotic and unpredictable collisions. The interesting part about this hypothesis was that the colloidal particles are small enough that classical thermodynamics is not valid anymore, but at the same time, they are large enough, compared to the solvent particles, that we can perform statistical mechanics. Einstein was, starting from this hypothesis, able to make macroscopic predictions that could be experimentally confirmed, giving important proof to the atomistic theory [7].

In the last century, there has been a lot of work put into understanding how the random motion of colloidal particles can be modeled and connected to the underlying classical Hamilton dynamics, or even include quantum effects [11–14]. While initially this work still focused on equilibrium settings, nowadays there is an increasing focus also on active matter. With the colloidal particle still as a paradigm, we can also look at active motion, as for example exhibited by swimming bacteria. These were first experimentally observed under a microscope by van Leeuwenhoek and Hook in the 1670s [15], which predates the discovery of Brownian motion. The special feature of this type of Brownian motion is that the colloidal particles are self propelled, and thus active, but thermal fluctuations can still be relevant [16, 17]. By introducing this activity into the system, many effects appear that would be unthinkable in thermal equilibrium, like collective phenomena as motility-induced phase separation [18]. Also state observables, well known from equilibrium statistical physics like pressure, can behave very differently in non-equilibrium setups and depend a lot on interaction details [19]. Another version of activity would be that the colloidal particle itself is still a passive particle, but the suspension contains activity in some form. For example, the bath could consist of self propelling particles that kick the passive particle [20]. This could again be bacteria or molecular motors found in the cellular cytoplasm [21]. Especially with the upcoming of advanced particle tracking and manipulation, for example, using optical tweezers [22, 23], the analysis of such active particles gets more and more interesting.

Before we start to dive into the more technical parts of this thesis, we want to propose the essential question of the thesis, which goes back to the very beginning in 1828. How do we distinguish an ordinary equilibrium Brownian particle from an active one, just by looking at its movement? Active can mean either self propelled or in an active solution. That this question is sometimes not easy to answer with the naked eye is also shown by the fact that great microbiologists, like Kitasato for the pest bacterium, or Shiga and Flexner for the dysentery bacteria, initially described these non-motile bacteria as self-propelled [24, 25]. Before we can approach the question from the perspective of statistical physics, we will lay some groundwork in the next sections of this introduction to introduce the necessary vocabulary, which we require for the remainder of the thesis.

1.2.2. Langevin equation

Physical Motivation

Let's assume we have a Brownian particle as we described in the previous section. How can we model the motion of such a particle? We start with the fundamental Newton equations of motion

$$m\ddot{x}(t) = F(x, \dot{x}, t) \quad (1.1)$$

where the acceleration of a particle is proportional to the force applied to the particle. The proportionality constant is given by the mass of the particle. Generally speaking,

we can split up the force on a particle into three components [26]

$$F(x, \dot{x}, t) = -U'(x) - \gamma\dot{x} + f(t). \quad (1.2)$$

We will now go through the terms one by one. The first contribution is given by some potential $U(x)$. This can be given by an external potential or conservative interaction forces between different particles. The force is then given by the derivative of this potential. The second term $-\gamma\dot{x}$ is the Stokes friction the particle feels in a liquid at low Reynolds numbers. Under this force, the kinetic energy of the particle is dissipated into the liquid over time. Therefore, generally speaking, the particle would reach a state of rest. However, as we observed in the previous section, particles suspended in a liquid exhibit random motion because of random collisions with liquid particles. We therefore add a third force $f(t)$ which is a random force or noise transmitted through the thermal fluctuations of the collisions. Generally, the mean force $\langle f(t) \rangle = 0$, should vanish, so there is no overall drift in the system. Also, we assume that the dynamics in the liquid are very fast compared to the dynamics of the probe particle. This means that when a liquid particle collides with the probe, it subsequently collides with many other liquid particles in a short amount of time. Hence, if the next collision with the probe occurs, it is statistically independent of the earlier collisions with the probe. This property is also called Markovian, or the liquid has no memory of previous collisions with the probe. In the mathematical sense, we can write this as $\langle f(t)f(t') \rangle = A\delta(t-t')$, with a force amplitude A and the delta function $\delta(t-t')$. This means for all time $t \neq t'$ the random forces $f(t)$ and $f(t')$ are uncorrelated. The last parameter we need to fix is the force amplitude A . For simplicity we assume $U'(x) = 0$, then we can formally solve Eq. (1.2) in one dimension for the velocity $\dot{x} = v$

$$v(t) = \frac{1}{m} \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-\frac{\gamma}{m}(t-s)} f(s) ds. \quad (1.3)$$

The velocity autocorrelation function evaluates as

$$\langle v(t)v(t) \rangle = \frac{1}{m^2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' e^{-\frac{\gamma}{m}(2t-s-s')} \langle f(s)f(s') \rangle \quad (1.4)$$

$$= \frac{A}{2\gamma m}. \quad (1.5)$$

The equipartition theorem states that for a quadratic degree of freedom, we obtain on average an energy of $\frac{1}{2}k_B T$. This means that the kinetic energy is given by

$$\frac{1}{2}m \langle v^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{2}k_B T \quad (1.6)$$

$$\Rightarrow A = 2\gamma k_B T. \quad (1.7)$$

We can use this insight from fundamental thermodynamics to fix the amplitude of the random forces, such that they are thermodynamically consistent. We can sum up our

findings into

$$m\ddot{x} = -U'(x) - \gamma\dot{x} + f(t) \quad (1.8)$$

with $\langle f(t) \rangle = 0$ and $\langle f(t)f(t') \rangle = 2k_B T \gamma \delta(t - t')$. Eq. (1.8) is known as Langevin equation and was first introduced by Paul Langevin in 1908[27]. It is a stochastic differential equation that phenomenologically describes the movement of a Brownian particle. The random force is referred to as thermal noise and increases with the temperature of the liquid. The same is also true if the friction or dissipation γ increases. This relation between thermal noise and dissipation is usually called a fluctuation dissipation theorem. Theorems of this kind come in various forms, which we discuss more generally in section 1.2.4. A simplified version of Eq. (1.8) is found in the case of small masses m , where the inertial time scale $\frac{\gamma}{m}$ is much faster than every interaction time scale encoded in $U'(x)$. In this case, one approximates $m\ddot{x} \approx 0$ and finds the overdamped Langevin equation

$$\gamma\dot{x} = -U'(x) + f(t). \quad (1.9)$$

This simplified equation is often used in biophysical settings, or generally if the systems are "small". The free solution $U'(x) = 0$ has an important result. For the *mean squared displacement* (MSD) $\Delta x^2(t) = \langle (x(t) - x(0))^2 \rangle$ we find

$$\Delta x^2(t) = \frac{1}{\gamma^2} \int_0^t ds \int_0^t ds' \langle f(s)f(s') \rangle \quad (1.10)$$

$$= 2 \frac{k_B T}{\gamma} t. \quad (1.11)$$

The MSD increases linearly in time with a constant $D = \frac{k_B T}{\gamma}$, which is known as Einstein relation. In Einstein's original work in 1905 he was able to first make the connection between fluctuations D and the thermodynamic and material properties $k_B T$ and γ [7].

Mathematical description

In the previous paragraph, we gave the physical motivations in finding the Langevin equation Eq. (1.8) & (1.9). We will briefly discuss the mathematical modeling with the Wiener process for stochastic differential equations.

Mathematically, for a stochastic variable X the corresponding stochastic differential equation (SDE) is formulated as

$$dX_t = a(X, t)dt + \sigma(X, t)dW \quad (1.12)$$

where we introduce the Wiener process W_t . This stochastic process has the following

properties [28, 29]

$$W_0 = 0 \quad (1.13a)$$

$$\text{Increments } W_{t+\Delta t} - W_t \text{ are independent of past } W_s, s \leq t \quad (1.13b)$$

$$P(W_{t+\Delta t} - W_t) \propto \mathcal{N}(W_{t+\Delta t} - W_t | 0, \Delta t) \quad (1.13c)$$

$$W_t \text{ is continuous in } t. \quad (1.13d)$$

Property Eq. (1.13c) means that increments of the Wiener process are Gaussian distributed with zero mean and standard deviation Δt . The term $a(X_t, t)$ in Eq. (1.12) is called the drift term, and $\sigma(X_t, t)$ is named diffusion. The general solution of the SDE is given by

$$X_t - X_0 = \int_0^t a(X_s, s) ds + \int_0^t \sigma(X_s, s) dW_s. \quad (1.14)$$

The first integral term $\int_0^t a(X(s), s) ds$ can be easily understood as a Riemann integral and therefore needs no further discussion. The second integral over the Wiener process $\int_0^t \sigma(X(s), s) dW_s$, however, has some rather peculiar properties, depending on how the integral is defined. There are two main conventions, the Ito convention and the Stratonovich convention. The Ito convention is rather simple

$$\int_0^t \sigma(X_s, s) dW_s = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \sum_{n=1}^N \sigma(X_{t_n}, t_n) (W_{t_n + \Delta t} - W_{t_n}) \quad (1.15)$$

where we discretize time into $N + 1$ time points which are equidistantly separated by Δt . So the time point t_n is given by $t_n = t_0 + n\Delta t$. The Ito convention has some mathematical advantages because it is a semi-martingale, which opens the pathway to many mathematical theorems. However, it requires a modification of the chain rule. According to Ito's lemma for a stochastic process $X_t = h(W_t)$ the following relation holds [29]

$$dX_t = h'(W_t) dW_t + \frac{1}{2} h''(W_t) dt. \quad (1.16)$$

The first term of Eq. (1.16) corresponds to the known chain rule. The term $\frac{1}{2} h''(W_t) dt$ is additional and is referred to as suspicious drift because it is a differential in dt , reassembling a drift term. While it is technically possible to use Ito calculus and there are in principle no limitations, another integral convention, the Stratonovich convention, is used especially in physics [30]. It is usually denoted as $\circ dW$. The stochastic integral is then defined as

$$\int_0^t \sigma(X_s, s) \circ dW_s = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\sigma(X_{t_n + \Delta t}, t_n + \Delta t) + \sigma(X_{t_n}, t_n)}{2} (W_{t_n + \Delta t} - W_{t_n}) \quad (1.17)$$

In this case, the chain rule behaves as expected

$$dX_t = h'(W_t) \circ dW_t \quad (1.18)$$

and one can apply basic calculus. The Ito and Stratonovich conventions are completely equivalent and can always be transformed into each other if one uses Ito's lemma Eq. (1.16). Numerically, one usually uses the Euler-Mayurama method, which is equivalent to directly applying the Ito convention of the stochastic integral for a finite time step Δt . There are also higher order schemes as the Runge-Kutta-Milstein method, which is primarily used in the simulations of this thesis [31].

1.2.3. Path integral

The Langevin equations discussed in section 1.2.2 describe the time evolution of a stochastic variable via a SDE. There is an equivalent description in terms of path probabilities. This description will be useful when we discuss entropy production and stochastic thermodynamics in the following. We start by defining a path. A path ω of x is a collection of time ordered stochastic values

$$\omega(t) = (x_{t_1}, x_{t_2}, \dots, x_{t_n}) \quad (1.19)$$

with $t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_n$, where we generally assume that the distance between two neighboring time points is small. For a Wiener process, this is rather simple, because all increments are statistically independent. The probability of finding a specific Wiener process is therefore given by

$$P[W(t)] = \prod_{n=1}^N \mathcal{N}(W_{t_{n+1}} - W_{t_n} | 0, t_{n+1} - t_n). \quad (1.20)$$

$P[W(t)]$ is the probability of finding the path $W(t)$ and we use square brackets[...] to denote a functional dependence. How can we use this to get the probability of a path $x(t)$ that is described by the SDE

$$\dot{x}_t = a(x_t, t)dt + \sigma(x_t, t)dW \quad (1.21)$$

In the discretized form (Ito convention), we can write this equation as

$$x_{t+\Delta t} - x_t = a(x_t, t)\Delta t + \sigma(x_t, t)(W_{t+\Delta t} - W_t) \quad (1.22)$$

$$\Delta x = a(x_t, t)\Delta t + \sigma(x_t, t)\Delta W \quad (1.23)$$

for a small Δt . We know the probability of finding an increment $P(\Delta W)$ which is given by a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(\Delta W | 0, \Delta t)$. To get a probability for the increment Δx we use the fundamental identity $P(\Delta W)d\Delta W = P(\Delta x)d\Delta x$. The differential is given by

$\frac{d\Delta W}{d\Delta x} = \frac{1}{\sigma(x_t, t)}$ and with that we get the probability of an increment [24]

$$P(\Delta x) = \frac{d\Delta W}{d\Delta x} P(\Delta W) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma(x_t, t)^2\Delta t}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\Delta x - a(x_t, t)\Delta t)^2}{\sigma(x_t, t)^2\Delta t}\right). \quad (1.24)$$

The probability of the full path is given by the product of all displacements $\Delta x_n = x_{t_{n+1}} - x_{t_n}$

$$P[x] = \prod_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma(x_{t_n}, t_n)^2\Delta t}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(\Delta x_n - a(x_{t_n}, t_n)\Delta t)^2}{\sigma(x_{t_n}, t_n)^2\Delta t}\right) \quad (1.25)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Omega} \exp\left(\sum_{n=1}^N -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta x_n}{\Delta t} - a(x_{t_n}, t_n)\right)^2}{\sigma(x_{t_n}, t_n)^2} \Delta t\right) \quad (1.26)$$

The actual path integral, which we can use to evaluate path observables, is then given by

$$\int \mathcal{D}x \exp\left(\sum_{n=1}^N -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta x_n}{\Delta t} - a(x_{t_n}, t_n)\right)^2}{\sigma(x_{t_n}, t_n)^2} \Delta t\right) \quad (1.27)$$

with the differential $\mathcal{D}x = \prod_{n=1}^N \frac{dx_{t_n}}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma(x_{t_n}, t_n)^2\Delta t}}$. In the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ we get the Onsager-Machlup functional

$$A[x] = \int \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\dot{x}(t) - a(x(t), t))^2}{\sigma(x(t), x)^2} dt \quad (1.28)$$

with the total path probability

$$P[x] = \frac{1}{\Omega} e^{-A[x]}. \quad (1.29)$$

For a Langevin equation like Eq. (1.9) this reads like [32–34]

$$A[x] = \frac{1}{4D} \int \left(\dot{x} + \frac{U'}{\gamma}\right)^2 dt, \quad (1.30)$$

with the action in the Ito convention, and

$$A[x] = \frac{1}{4D} \int \left(\dot{x} + \frac{U'}{\gamma}\right)^2 + \frac{U''(x)}{\gamma} dt \quad (1.31)$$

in the Stratonovich convention.

We can now attach probabilities to paths, and by integrating over all possible paths, we get path integrals. In principle, Langevin equations and the path integral are equivalent to each other and describe the same system. However, the latter is more useful to discuss the properties of path ensembles. For completeness, there is also a third description. The probability $W_1(x, t)$ of the particle being at position x at time t for a overdamped

Langevin Equation like Eq. (1.9) is given by the Fokker Planck equation [26]

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} W_1(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\left(D \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \frac{U'}{\gamma} \right) W_1(x, t) \right] \quad (1.32)$$

which is a partial differential equation. For $U(x) = 0$, a free particle, this equation collapses to the diffusion equation. However, we will primarily work with Langevin equations and path integrals in the following.

1.2.4. Fluctuation dissipation theorem

A key technique in describing a system in physics is to analyze its response to a perturbation. For small perturbation forces F , the response of an observable x can generally be written as [35]

$$\langle x(t) \rangle - \langle x(0) \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \chi(t-s) F(s) ds \quad (1.33)$$

with the susceptibility $\chi(t)$. This susceptibility needs to fulfill the causality condition $\chi(t < 0) = 0$, otherwise future forces would influence past displacements. A whole field of statistical physics deals with this type of response theory [36–39], both in equilibrium and non-equilibrium. In equilibrium, one can relate the susceptibility to spontaneous fluctuations in the unperturbed system. For a force $F(t)$ which couples to the phase space observable y , one finds the following response formula [35]

$$\langle x(t) \rangle = \langle x \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{k_B T} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} ds \frac{d}{dt} \langle xy(t-s) \rangle_{\text{eq}} \theta(t-s) F(s), \quad (1.34)$$

where we identify

$$\chi(t-s) = -\frac{1}{k_B T} \frac{d}{dt} \langle xy(t-s) \rangle_{\text{eq}} \theta(t-s) \quad (1.35)$$

as the susceptibility. We can rewrite this relation in Fourier space as

$$2i\chi''(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt [\chi(t) - \chi(-t)] e^{-i\omega t} = \frac{i\omega C(\omega)}{k_B T} \quad (1.36)$$

$$\Rightarrow \chi''(\omega) = \frac{\omega C(\omega)}{2k_B T} \quad (1.37)$$

with χ'' the complex part of the susceptibility, and for $y = x$ the correlation function $C(\omega) = \langle x(\omega)x(-\omega) \rangle$. This complex part of the susceptibility is also referred to as the dissipative part because the dissipated energy ΔE due to the perturbation is given by [40]

$$\Delta E = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \omega \chi''(\omega) F(\omega) F(-\omega) d\omega. \quad (1.38)$$

Eq. (1.38) only depends on χ'' and, thus, the imaginary part of the susceptibility gives the dissipation of the system. Therefore, Eq. (1.37) relates the fluctuations of a system, given by C and the dissipation χ'' , hence the name fluctuation dissipation theorem (FDT). The real part of the response function χ' is also fixed by the imaginary part, via the Kramers-Kronig relations [41]. Therefore, Eq. (1.37) fully determines the spectrum and the susceptibility.

In practice, Eq. (1.37) can be used for determining the mechanical properties of a material by measuring the unperturbed spectrum $C(\omega)$ of a prob particle. This approach is usually referred to as passive (micro-)rheology [42]. For this to work, the system, however, has to be in equilibrium.

Another way is to use the FDT as a marker for non-equilibrium. If Eq. (1.37) is violated, we can state the system is out of equilibrium². To use this approach, one measures the susceptibility by applying a force to the colloidal particle and separately measures the correlation function in the unperturbed system. In this context, effective temperatures or energies are often mentioned. In the non-equilibrium situation, we can modify Eq. (1.37) as [2]

$$\chi''(\omega) = \frac{\omega C(\omega)}{2E_{\text{eff}}(\omega)} \quad (1.39)$$

where E_{eff} is a frequency dependent correction factor. If $E_{\text{eff}}(\omega) \neq k_B T$ for any frequency ω , then the system is out of equilibrium. Because E_{eff} has the units of energy, we can call it an effective energy. However, on its own, it has no bigger meaning than that it quantifies the FDT violation. Alternatively, $T_{\text{eff}} = \frac{E_{\text{eff}}}{k_B}$ we can define an effective temperature, which again has the units of temperature but has no higher meaning. This approach to test if a system is in equilibrium has been applied in multiple experiments, for example, involving hair bundle cells or blood vessels [44–47]. Therefore, FDT violations have proven to be a useful tool to show, for example, that living systems are actually out of equilibrium.

The major complication of this approach is usually that one has to determine the susceptibility using active perturbations. Such experimental programs can be very invasive and are sometimes difficult to conduct. Therefore, it would be generally preferred to have methods that just rely on passive observations and not active perturbations. Hence, we will introduce the concepts of time reversal symmetry and entropy production to give a different approach to detecting non-equilibrium.

²Another possibility is that the weak coupling assumption is violated. During the proof, one generally assumes that the system is weakly coupled to a heat bath. This means that the system and bath exchange energy, but are dynamically independent. In this case, the combined system might be in equilibrium, but one can not split into a separate system and bath. While these technicalities are generally ignored in classical settings, they can be relevant for quantum mechanics [43].

1.3. Time reversal and entropy production

1.3.1. Time reversal symmetry and detailed balance

In the following chapters, we will use the breaking of time reversal symmetry and detailed balance breakage as a marker of non-equilibrium features of a system. This means we need to discuss how the two concepts, time reversal symmetry and equilibrium, are related.

A (closed) system is in equilibrium if the probability $p(\Gamma)$ of finding the system at $\Gamma = (\{q_i\}, \{p_i\})$ is the same everywhere in the accessible phase space. Here q_i are the generalized coordinates and p_i the generalized momenta. The accessible phase space is on the energy shell $H(\Gamma) = E$ with H the Hamilton function governing the dynamics of the system. The energy E is, in this case, a control parameter. The overall concept is referred to as the microcanonical ensemble. The probability is then expressed as $p(\Gamma) = \frac{1}{\Omega}$ where

$$\Omega = \frac{1}{N!h^{3N}} \int d\Gamma \delta(H(\Gamma) - E). \quad (1.40)$$

is the phase space volume of the energy shell. From here, one can go on and define thermodynamic quantities like entropy, temperature, etc., the standard textbook procedure in a statistical mechanics course [48]. We want to focus on the implications of the underlying dynamics.

Consider a sequence of phase space states $\Gamma_1, \dots, \Gamma_n$, then the system obeys time reversal symmetry if the joint probability W_n of finding the system at these points at the given times $t_1 < \dots < t_n$ obeys the following relation [40]

$$W_n(\Gamma_1, t_1; \dots; \Gamma_n, t_n) = W_n(\pi\Gamma_n, t_1; \dots; \pi\Gamma_1, t_n) \quad (1.41)$$

with the kinematic reversal operator $\pi\Gamma = (\{q_i\}, \{-p_i\})$ flipping all momenta or velocities of the state. The qualitative statement of this is rather simple: The probability of finding the trajectory of a system is the same as if the system follows the same trajectory but backwards. The system is statistically speaking time reversal symmetric because we have no way of distinguishing time forward and time backward trajectories. Therefore, every averaged quantity over $W_n(\Gamma_1, t_1; \dots; \Gamma_n, t_n)$ must have the same result as if averaged over the time reversed dynamics $W_n(\pi\Gamma_n, t_1; \dots; \pi\Gamma_1, t_n)$.

For classical Hamilton dynamics, this property is fulfilled by microscopic irreversibility. This means under the time reversal operation

$$t \rightarrow -t \quad (1.42a)$$

$$q_i \rightarrow q_i \quad (1.42b)$$

$$p_i \rightarrow -p_i \quad (1.42c)$$

the Hamilton or Newtonian equations of motion are invariant, as long as the (interaction) forces only depend on positions q_i and not on the momentum or velocities p_i . Because the dynamics are deterministic, the probability of finding a path is only given by the probability of the initial condition and the fact that the path is a solution of the equations of motion. Because of microscopic reversibility, for every solution of the equations of motion, the time reversed path is also a solution. The probability of finding these paths, therefore, only differs by the probability of the initial conditions $p(\Gamma_0)$ and $p(\pi\Gamma_t)$. However, in the microcanonical ensemble, every microstate has the same probability; thus, in equilibrium, $p(\Gamma_0) = p(\pi\Gamma_t)$ is trivially fulfilled. Hence, all forward paths have the same probability as the backward paths. The final important conclusion is that the classical equilibrium microscopic Hamilton dynamics is time reversal symmetric.

Often, one does not observe all degrees (q_i, p_i) of the underlying Hamilton dynamics but transitions between some coarse grained states n . A standard example are so called Markov processes, where the transition from one state n to m does not depend on any previous transitions. Such processes are typically used to model chemical reaction networks, like molecular motors, and transitions between lattice states [49, 50]. For a continuous time discrete Markov process, the probability of finding the particle in state n is given by p_n , and this probability changes in time given by the master equation [29]

$$\partial_t p_n(t) = \sum_{m \neq n} [p_m(t)w_{mn} - p_n(t)w_{nm}] \quad (1.43)$$

with w_{nm} the transition rate from state n to m . The terms $j_{mn} = p_m(t)w_{mn} - p_n(t)w_{nm}$ are the probability currents between the Markov states.

For these Markov systems, we would like to preserve the time reversal symmetry of the underlying Hamilton dynamics. This leads to the notion of detailed balance, if

$$p_m(t)w_{mn} = p_n(t)w_{nm} \quad (1.44)$$

for all states n, m then detailed balance is fulfilled. The practical implication of this property is that all probability currents j_{nm} vanish. For a Markov process detailed balance ensures that time reversal symmetry, defined on the W_n probabilities, is valid. Often, the terms time reversal symmetry and detailed balance are used interchangeably. This is only exactly true for a Markov process, generally time reversal symmetry is a stronger property.

As a final remark, for the coarse grained dynamics, we have imposed that if the underlying dynamic is in equilibrium, the coarse grained dynamic has to obey time reversal symmetry. So, detecting broken time reversal symmetry shows that the system is out of equilibrium, which we use as a marker for non-equilibrium. The inverse, however, is not true. A coarse grained system can obey time reversal symmetry even if the underlying dynamic does not. Therefore, detecting the breakage of time reversal symmetry can only serve as a marker for non-equilibrium and not as a marker for equilibrium.

1.3.2. Stochastic thermodynamics

In this section, we want to discuss entropy production as the natural, physically motivated observable to describe the absence of time reversal symmetry. To define entropy production, we first have a look at thermodynamics.

In classical thermodynamics, we consider a system that is coupled to heat bath, meaning that the system can absorb and transfer heat to this bath, which is assumed to be an unlimited source and sink. However, this interaction follows certain phenomenological rules, for example, there is no spontaneous heat transfer from a heat bath at high temperature to a heat bath of low temperature without the investment of work. A central concept here is entropy, or better, the change in entropy. The entropy change in a system due to heat transfer with a bath is given by [51]

$$\Delta S_Q = \frac{\Delta Q}{T}. \quad (1.45)$$

In addition to entropy exchange via heat transfer, the internal entropy in a system can also change, for example, by mixing processes. For irreversible processes, the total change in entropy, or entropy production, between the system and the bath is always positive

$$\Delta S \geq 0 \quad (1.46)$$

with equality if the process is reversible. Irreversible processes often involve mixing or other effects that do not naturally reverse without external intervention, as the application of work. Eq. (1.46) is the famous second law of thermodynamics.

These relations were first and foremost phenomenological observations, but in later works have been grounded by the principles of statistical mechanics. In statistical mechanics, one defines the entropy in equilibrium of an isolated system as the so called Boltzmann entropy

$$S_B = \log(\Omega) \quad (1.47)$$

with Ω the microcanonical partition sum of Eq. (1.40). The Boltzmann entropy increases if the number of accessible microstates increases. Another, more general access is via the Gibbs or Shanon entropy S , which is motivated by information theory. If $\rho(\Gamma, t)$ is the probability density, then

$$S = -\frac{1}{N!h^{3N}} \int d\Gamma \rho(\Gamma) \log(\rho(\Gamma)). \quad (1.48)$$

Here S_B is the special case for the $\rho(\Gamma, t) = \frac{1}{\Omega}$ microcanonical ensemble. The advantage of Eq. (1.48) is that we can describe how the system approaches the final equilibrium state, which maximizes the entropy, because the probability distribution is completely flat. This was investigated by Boltzmann, and he could show that for an ideal gas with collisions that the entropy increases but never decreases in the process, as one would expect by the second law. This relation is known as the H-Theorem [52].

In the following, we want to discuss the relation between the breakage of time reversal symmetry and entropy production. This yields a generalization of the entropy production to fluctuating paths, which is important when analyzing systems far from thermal equilibrium. For this discussion, we mainly follow Ref. [53], however, we adapted the notation to be consistent with the previous discussion.

To make this relation as general as possible, we start with Hamilton dynamics with a phase space point

$$\Gamma = (q_1, \dots, q_N, p_1, \dots, p_N) \in \Omega \quad (1.49)$$

where Ω is the whole phase space on the energy shell with energy E . Because energy is conserved, the whole dynamics lies in Ω . Usually, we have no access to the microscopic degrees of freedom, but to a more coarse grained version of phase space $\hat{\Omega}$. We define coarse grained phase space observable $M(\Gamma)$ where we map a microscopic phase space point $\Gamma \in \Omega$ to a macro or mesoscopic phase space observable $M(\Gamma) \in \hat{\Omega}$. We also define for a microscopic phase space region $A \subset \Omega$ the phase space volume $|A|$.

Next, we need the notion of a phase space trajectory. Let f be a map that propagates a phase space point Γ along the Liouville equations for time Δt . Then we write a microscopic trajectory as

$$\gamma = (\Gamma, f\Gamma, f^2\Gamma, \dots, f^n\Gamma) \quad (1.50)$$

and the corresponding macroscopic trajectory

$$\omega = (M(\Gamma), M(f\Gamma), \dots, M(f^n\Gamma)). \quad (1.51)$$

To define probability distributions, we make the first assumption. Inside the macroscopic states $M(\Gamma)$, we assume that all belonging microscopic states are distributed by the microcanonical ensemble. In this case, the probability of finding a microstate is

$$\nu(\Gamma) = \frac{\hat{\nu}(M(\Gamma))}{|M(\Gamma)|}, \quad (1.52)$$

where $\hat{\nu}(M)$ is a probability density on $\hat{\Omega}$.

Entropy is given by the Boltzmann entropy, which is defined as

$$\hat{S}_B(M) = \log |M| \quad (1.53)$$

on the macro states M . The corresponding microscopic version is given by $S_B(\Gamma) = \hat{S}_B(M(\Gamma))$. Generally, differences in Boltzmann entropy are what we refer to as differences of thermodynamic entropy. To relate the Boltzmann entropy to time reversal breaking, consider the following scenario. For every microscopic trajectory that starts at M_0 and ends at M_n , the following relation holds

$$\log \left(\frac{P(\gamma = (\Gamma, f\Gamma, \dots) | M(\Gamma) = M_0)}{P(\theta\gamma = (\Gamma, f\Gamma, \dots) | M(\Gamma) = \pi M_n)} \right) = \hat{S}_B(M_n) - \hat{S}_B(M_0) \quad (1.54)$$

Figure 1.2.: Illustration of how to connect entropy production with path probabilities.

Given that a microscopic path γ starts in M_0 , its probability is given by $P(\gamma|\gamma(0) = M_0) = 1/|M_0|$. If a path is connecting M_0 and M_n , then the reversed path $\theta\gamma$ is connecting πM_n and πM_0 . By the same construction, the probability of $\theta\gamma$ is $P(\theta\gamma|\theta\gamma(0) = \pi M_n) = 1/|\pi M_n| = 1/|M_n|$. With Eq. (1.53) one arrives at Eq. (1.54).

where $\theta\gamma$ is the time reversed trajectory. This result follows from the fact that the underlying dynamics are deterministic, and so the path probability is only defined by the probabilities of the initial points, which are determined by the phase space volume. This construction is illustrated in Fig. 1.2 We can see from Eq. (1.54) that the time reversal can indeed pick up changes in Boltzmann entropy. However, usually we have no access to the microscopic degrees and therefore need a relation for the macroscopic states M . For the coarse grained dynamics we can, however, obtain a very similar relation. If the trajectory starts at M_0 and ends in M_n , then for the trajectories $\omega = (M_0, \dots, M_n)$ and $\theta\omega = (\pi M_n, \dots, \pi M_0)$

$$\log \left(\frac{P[\omega]}{P[\theta\omega]} \right) = [\hat{S}_B(M_n) - \hat{S}_B(M_0)] + [-\log(\mu_t(M_n) + \log(\mu_0(M_0))] \quad (1.55)$$

for any initial and final probability distribution μ_0, μ_t on $\hat{\Omega}$. What is generally meant as entropy production in statistical mechanics is encoded in the difference of Boltzmann entropies. The term $(-\log(\mu(M_n) + \log(\mu(M_0)))$ arises due to the stochasticity of the coarse grained dynamics and has a priori no relation to entropy production [53]. On the other hand, including this term gives rise to beneficial mathematical properties, as we will see in section 1.3.3, and may also be physically informed. The whole right hand side of Eq. (1.55) is called stochastic entropy production. We also want to emphasize that to make the connection to the Boltzmann entropy for every macro observable M , the underlying microstates Γ with $M = M(\Gamma)$ have to be distributed by the microcanonical distribution. Therefore, the system must be at least locally in equilibrium. Eq. (1.55) is strictly speaking only valid for closed systems, however, it can also be generalized to open systems. If the system is coupled to multiple (equilibrated) heat baths, then one

gets the same result as Eq. (1.55) [53].

How does this translate to a Langevin description of a colloidal particle? Here we follow the introduction of Ref. [33]. For illustration, consider the overdamped Langevin equation

$$\gamma \dot{x} = -F(x) + \xi(t). \quad (1.56)$$

The heat dissipated into the bath must, by the first law, equal the energy that is required to displace x against the force $F(x) = -u'(x)$. The heat is therefore given as

$$q = \int_0^t F(x) \dot{x} ds. \quad (1.57)$$

We can identify this heat flow as a change in entropy inside the bath $s_m = \frac{q}{T}$ at temperature T . Recall the Onsager MachLup action in section 1.2.3. If we look at the time anti-symmetric part of the action, we get

$$A[x(t)] - A[\theta x(t)] = \frac{1}{k_B T} \int_0^t F(x) \dot{x} ds = \frac{q}{k_B T} = \frac{s_m}{k_B}. \quad (1.58)$$

The change in entropy is therefore given by the log ratio of the path probabilities with fixed initial positions, similar to Eq. (1.54)

$$\frac{s_m}{k_B} = \log \left(\frac{P[\omega(t)|\omega(0) = x_0]}{P[\theta\omega(t)|\theta\omega(0) = x_t]} \right). \quad (1.59)$$

As in Eq. (1.54), the entropy production is the log ratio of path probabilities. That entropy production is deeply related to time reversal symmetry and can be expressed by path probabilities is an important concept in various non-equilibrium models. For a Markov process, this means the transition rates have to fulfill

$$\frac{w_{nm}}{w_{mn}} = e^{-\frac{\Delta U}{k_B T}}, \quad (1.60)$$

where ΔU is the energy change between the different states. This condition is also referred to as local detailed balance. In the following, we assume that the change in entropy can indeed be written as the log ratio of path probabilities. Because of its physical relevance and its connection to time reversal, entropy production is one of the most important measures that quantifies the reversibility of a system. That is why it is of major interest to quantify whether a system is out of equilibrium.

Eq. (1.59) only refers to the entropy change in the bath, but how do we account for the entropy change in the system? We use the informational change in entropy along the trajectory

$$\frac{s_{\text{sys}}}{k_B} = \log(p(x(0), 0)) - \log(p(x(t), t)) \quad (1.61)$$

where $p(x(t), t)$ is the solution of the Fokker-Planck equation at time t [54]. This

corresponds to making an informed choice on the macroscopic probability distribution μ in Eq. (1.55). This can be further understood by considering the informational entropy at time t

$$\frac{S_{\text{sys}}(t)}{k_B} = \int dx p(x, 0) \log(p(x, 0)) - \int dx p(x, t) \log(p(x, t)). \quad (1.62)$$

This part is, on average, only relevant if the system relaxes to a steady state distribution. If $p(x, t) = p_s(x)$ is stationary then

$$\frac{S_{\text{sys}}(t)}{k_B} = \int dx p_s(x) \log(p_s(x)) - \int dx p_s(x) \log(p_s(x)) = 0 \quad (1.63)$$

vanishes. All in all, the total change in entropy of entropy production is given by

$$s = s_m + s_{\text{sys}} \quad (1.64)$$

Note that s, s_m, s_{sys} are all path dependent fluctuating quantities, where the mean

$$S = \langle s \rangle \quad (1.65)$$

is the quantity one usually refers to as entropy production. The final expression for stochastic entropy production is

$$\frac{s}{k_B} = \log \left(\frac{P[\omega]}{P[\theta\omega]} \right) = \log \left(\frac{P[\omega(t)|\omega(0) = x_0]}{P[\theta\omega(t)|\theta\omega(0) = x_t]} \right) + \log \left(\frac{p(x_0, 0)}{p(x_t, t)} \right). \quad (1.66)$$

It is the log ratio of the full path probabilities, which, in comparison to Eq. (1.59), also accounts for the probabilities of the final and end state. In equilibrium, the path probability $P[\omega] = P[\theta\omega]$ is time reversal symmetric and therefore it immediately follows $s = 0$. If we remember the Langevin example system, then

$$s_m = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^t F(x) \dot{x} ds \quad (1.67)$$

$$= -\frac{1}{T} \int_0^t \frac{\partial U(x)}{\partial x} \dot{x} ds \quad (1.68)$$

$$= -\frac{1}{T} [U(x_t) - U(x_0)]. \quad (1.69)$$

In equilibrium we also expect a Boltzmann distribution $p(x) = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\frac{U(x)}{k_B T}}$. With this, we get

$$s_{\text{sys}} = k_B \log \left(\frac{e^{-\frac{U(x_0)}{k_B T}}}{e^{-\frac{U(x_t)}{k_B T}}} \right) \quad (1.70)$$

$$= \frac{1}{T} [U(x_t) - U(x_0)] = -s_m. \quad (1.71)$$

Therefore, $s = s_{\text{sys}} + s_m = 0$, which is exactly what we expect. This means in equilibrium, the stochastic entropy production vanishes for every path.

1.3.3. Fluctuation theorems

In the previous section, we discussed entropy production as the log ratio of path probabilities. This has an interesting implication for stochastic entropy because of its dependence on probabilities.

Consider the following relation

$$\begin{aligned}\langle e^{-s} \rangle &= \int \mathcal{D}\omega \frac{P[\theta\omega]}{P[\omega]} P[\omega] \\ &= 1\end{aligned}\tag{1.72}$$

which follows from the normalization of $P[\theta\omega]$. Importantly, by Jensen's inequality we get that

$$\langle e^{-s} \rangle \geq e^{-\langle s \rangle}\tag{1.73}$$

$$\Rightarrow \langle s \rangle \geq 0\tag{1.74}$$

which means the mean of stochastic entropy production is always positive. For a macroscopic system where fluctuations are small, this reassembles the second law Eq. (1.46). For a microscopic system, the second law is on average also obeyed, however, it is spontaneously possible for entropy to decrease. The equality Eq. (1.72) is also referred to as the integral fluctuation theorem or Kawasaki identity and was first discovered using computer simulations [55, 56]. Since Eq. (1.72) is an equality, it is sometimes also called a generalization of the second law.

Another class of fluctuation theorems lives directly on the probability of paths. For Markov processes, the Crooks fluctuation theorem relates the probability between trajectories starting from one equilibrium into another one, governed by some time dependent protocol $\lambda(t)$. In this case, we can write [57]

$$\frac{P[\theta\omega]}{P[\omega]} = e^{\beta\Delta F - \beta W}\tag{1.75}$$

where ΔF is the difference between the free energies of the initial and final equilibrium states, and W the work done by the protocol. This is also another example of an informed choice of the probability μ in Eq. (1.55), where μ_0 and μ_t are both the Boltzmann distribution in the respective equilibria [53]. Further, we can interpret this as writing this as the difference in Helmholtz free energy

$$\frac{S}{k_B} = \frac{\Delta F}{k_B T} - \frac{W}{k_B T},\tag{1.76}$$

however, not on the ensemble level, but for individual trajectories. If we take the mean of Eq. (1.75), also called the Crooks fluctuation theorem, we get the Jarzynski relation [58]

$$e^{-\beta\Delta F} = \langle e^{-\beta W} \rangle.\tag{1.77}$$

By applying again the Jensen inequality, we get

$$\Delta F \geq \langle W \rangle \quad (1.78)$$

another version of the second law. The main insight of fluctuation theorems, as we have seen in this section, is that we can generalize concepts from thermodynamics from the ensemble level down to individual fluctuating trajectories. For example, the Jazinksy relation can be used to make a map of free energies by applying a time dependent protocol, for example, by unfolding a complex polymers like RNA [59].

1.3.4. Thermodynamic uncertainty relation

Nils Bohr already very early made the conjecture that relations similar to the uncertainty relation must also exist for thermodynamics because they are a property of probability and not quantum mechanics [60]. A simple example are energy and temperature of a thermometer. To measure the temperature, the thermometer must exchange energy with the environment. If one wants to know the energy (state) of the thermometer, we have to effectively isolate it and measure the energy. However, in this case, we do not know the temperature of the bath because many temperatures could thermalize this specific energy state. On the other hand, if we measure the temperature, we do not know exactly the current energy state of the thermometer. One can formally derive the following inequality [60]

$$\Delta E \Delta \frac{1}{T} \geq k_B \quad (1.79)$$

where Δ denotes the standard deviation around the thermal average. Energy and temperature are conjugated observables, similar to momentum and position in quantum mechanics. One can derive similar relations between other typical quantities, as for example volume and pressure.

In recent years, people have also found that other fairly general inequalities relate entropy production to certain observables. The most famous one involves a general integrated current

$$J(t) = \int_0^t U(x(s)) \dot{x}(s) ds. \quad (1.80)$$

The precision of the current, given by the Fano-factor, in time continuous overdamped dynamics, is bounded by the entropy production [61–65]

$$\langle s \rangle \geq 2 \frac{\langle J(t) \rangle^2}{\text{Var}[J(t)]}. \quad (1.81)$$

The interpretation of this inequality is that making an integrated current precise, for example, representing the phase or time of a clock, costs entropy. And the more precise the clock is supposed to be, the more entropy production is required. Because it involves precision, this relation is also commonly referred to as the thermodynamic uncertainty

relation (TUR). Eq. (1.81) itself can also be interpreted as a more tight version of the second law, because the right hand side does not need to be zero. An interesting aspect of these types of bounds is that they remain valid, even if the dynamics are coarse grained. So even by looking at a highly simplified dynamics, for example by only tracking one particle, we get a lower bound on entropy production. However, generally integrating out degrees of freedom means that the observed entropy production reduces [66]. Another feature is that one does not necessarily need to sample probabilities to estimate entropy production, nor does one need knowledge about all degrees of freedom and interactions. A simpler observable is enough, which can be advantageous if the accessible statistics are limited. The possibility of getting a bound on entropy production is sometimes referred to as model free inference [66].

If one wants to use Eq. (1.81) for inference, then one has to search for the current J that maximizes the right hand side of Eq. (1.81). One way to achieve this is by composing the current J out of multiple individual J_n

$$J = \sum_n J_n \quad (1.82)$$

and optimize the composition [67]. The other possibility is to saturate the underlying mathematical inequalities to saturate the bound. For the correlation TUR, a variant that also incorporates densities, one can give the exact current that will saturate the bound [65].

Another limitation is that the classical TURs are only valid for time continuous dynamics and overdamped motion [64, 68]. Especially the latter can be a problem if there is no time scale separation at which inertial degrees of freedom can be ignored. However, there have been extensions, for example, to discrete time dynamics and general time-reversal anti-symmetric observables, and not only currents [68, 69]. One example for this is the Fluctuation Theorem Uncertainty Relation (FTUR), which is valid for any anti-symmetric observable $O_-[\omega] = -O_+[\theta\omega]$, if the system is stationary or periodically driven [69]

$$\frac{\text{Var}[O_-]}{\langle O_- \rangle^2} \geq \frac{2}{e^{\langle s \rangle} - 1} \quad (1.83)$$

which is a huge generalization, however, the FTUR bound is always less tight than the TUR bound. The bound is, as the original TUR, saturated for $O_- = s$ and $\langle s \rangle \rightarrow 0$.

1.4. Outline of the thesis

The thesis is organized as follows. The general aim is to find a statistical observable that can detect the breakage of time reversal symmetry or detailed balance. In this thesis, we investigate the potential of the mean back relaxation (MBR), a three-point correlation function, which we first introduced in [2]. In chapter 2 we establish this quantity and discuss its properties as a time reversal marker, and give general solutions

for Gaussian processes. In chapter 3 we discuss the variance of back relaxation (VBR), which gives information about the statistics of MBR. We give again a general solution for Gaussian processes. In chapter 4 we analyze the general structure of MBR from cell data and compare this to a model system that qualitatively matches a lot of the results we observe in the experiment. We also investigate the relationship between MBR and FDT violations i.e. the effective energy that has been experimentally determined for different cell types. Strikingly, the MBR and the amplitude of this effective energy are strongly correlated. At last, we compare VBR in cells to the Gaussian model. While we see there that the qualitative properties of our investigation in chapter 3 for Gaussian processes hold, cell data nevertheless has a strong non-Gaussian signature in VBR. In chapter 5 we make a small detour from MBR and derive a bound for entropy production. Unlike the original TUR, which is limited to overdamped dynamics and requires both mean and variance, this bound is also valid for non-overdamped dynamics and requires only the observable mean. We derive such a relation because we can then at a later point use it to get an estimate for entropy production. The last part of the thesis in chapter 6 then focuses on the actual time reversal properties of the cell data. We will see that MBR indeed shows that the dynamics in cells breaks time reversal symmetry. With this insight, we then apply our results in chapter 5 to get a lower bound on entropy production. We compare to the effective energies and see that the bound and the effective energy amplitude are also correlated.

2.

Mean Back Relaxation

This chapter is largely identical to the publication [4]. We introduce here the mean back relaxation (MBR) as the central observable of this dissertation.

- Section 2.1 was taken from [4] with small changes to integrate Section 2.2.
- Section 2.2 was written by me and is not included in [4] as is the case for Fig. 2.1.
- The remaining sections are taken from [4]. The word "cut off" was exchanged with "length parameter" for overall consistency with the remaining thesis.

Matthias Krüger introduced me to the concept of MBR. The mathematical definition of MBR was finalized by me and Matthias Krüger. I performed the mathematical calculations and numerical simulations. I wrote the original draft of the paper under the supervision of Matthias Krüger. Some of the words might be his.

2.1. Introduction

The analysis of particle trajectories is a fundamental building block of modern statistical physics, both in simulation and experiment. Especially in the latter, nowadays advanced techniques allow particle tracking with high precision and time resolution, leading to an extensive use of statistical analysis and the determination of microrheological and non-equilibrium properties of complex media [42, 44, 47, 70, 71]. Correlation functions obtained from these trajectories, like the mean squared displacement (MSD), are in equilibrium related to powerful theorems like the fluctuation dissipation theorem (FDT) or Green-Kubo relation [35, 38, 72–75]. Breakage of time reversal symmetry is quantified by entropy production, for which powerful theorems exist [3, 33, 61, 63, 65, 76–78]. Multi-point correlation functions, that depend on multiple time points, have the potential to be sensitive to time reversal breakage and can therefore serve as intriguing observables in non-equilibrium systems. Conditioning trajectories, for example by selecting trajectories that start at certain positions [79–81] has lead to interesting insights. In the following, we will analyze a multi-point observable that has been termed mean back relaxation (MBR) [2, 82]. It was shown that MBR is a marker for broken detailed balance in confinement [2]. In this chapter we expand on the properties of this quantity and analyze it in more depth. We also extend it towards microscopic densities, which yields a marker for broken detailed balance in confinement and for bulk systems.

The chapter is organized as follows. In sections 2.2 and 2.3, we motivate and define MBR. We discuss its properties in confined systems in section 2.4, where we reproduce the proof that the deviation of the long time value of MBR from $\frac{1}{2}$ marks broken detailed balance in confinement and a fluctuation theorem. We probe these findings on an active Brownian particle trapped in a potential. In section 2.5 we derive conditioned correlations in a path integral formalism. In section 2.6, we apply this to find a general relation between MBR and mean squared displacement in Gaussian systems. At last in section 2.7 we introduce a new version of MBR based on densities, showing that its deviation from $\frac{1}{2}$ marks broken detailed balance in bulk systems and confinement.

2.2. Mean Back Relaxation: Motivation

The central idea of MBR lies in the following question: If a particle moved, for example, to the right in a previous time interval, what is it going to do in the future? Generally, one would expect that if there is no overall drift in the system, the particle would move to the left. But by how much? As a dimensionless quantitative measure, we define the back relaxation as the negative ratio between the displacement d in the interval $[-\tau, 0]$ and the displacement b between $[0, t]$ (ignoring division by 0)

$$B \approx -\frac{b}{d}. \quad (2.1)$$

A more rigorous mathematical definition can be found in section 2.3. The mean of Eq. (2.1) is the mean back relaxation. The hope is that how the particle responds to displacements d is different in equilibrium and non-equilibrium settings, and thus MBR might reveal differences in time forward and time reversed dynamics. MBR can be understood as a measure of persistence. If b and d have the same sign, the back relaxation is negative, while if they have opposite signs, it is positive. Negative MBR, therefore, means that the particle tends to move in the same direction, while positive MBRs indicate that the particle moves in the opposite direction. This connection is visualized in Fig. 2.1.

The most typical observable investigated for colloidal particles is the MSD. However, it is not particularly useful to investigate time reversal symmetry, because

$$\Delta x^2(t) = \int dx_t dx_0 (x_t - x_0)^2 W_2(x_t, t; x_0, 0) \quad (2.2)$$

$$= \int dx_t dx_0 (x_t - x_0)^2 W_2(x_0, t; x_t, 0) \quad (2.3)$$

it is insensitive to replacing the joint two-point probability W_2 with its time reversed. Therefore, MSD is not able to detect breaking of time reversal symmetry. Other options usually involve currents, which are primarily used in the context of Markov networks, which can detect breaking of time reversal symmetry if one can construct one for the particular system. The most famous example is the entropy production itself. That MBR might be a possible marker is motivated by another conditioned correlation, the mean

Figure 2.1.: Illustrates the meaning of basic values of MBR. If the particle moves on average in the same direction between $-\tau$ and 0 and 0 and t , MBR is negative. If future displacement is not influenced by the past displacement, MBR vanishes. For positive values, the particle typically moves in the opposite direction in the respective time intervals. The value of $\frac{1}{2}$ is the expected long time t value in equilibrium under the conditions of Eq. (2.8) & (2.9) .

conditional displacement (MCD). Here, one fixes the initial point of the trajectory x_0 and then looks at the mean conditioned displacement $\langle x(t) - x_0 \rangle_{|x_0}$. With this quantity, one can derive conditions on monotonicity in equilibrium. It has been used to show that a driven particle in an optical tweezers suspended in a viscoelastic background is out of equilibrium [80, 83]. However, the MCD is not easily applicable to a bulk system because it is not possible to sample unique x_0 positions.

2.3. Mean Back Relaxation: Conditioned correlations

The mean back relaxation (MBR) [2] is the average future displacement of a particle divided by the displacement in the past. For particle position coordinate x , we define it in terms of two time periods t and τ and a length parameter l as,

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \left\langle -\frac{x_t - x_0}{x_0 - x_{-\tau}} \vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) \right\rangle \quad (2.4)$$

$$= \int dx_t dx_0 dx_{-\tau} \left(-\frac{x_t - x_0}{x_0 - x_{-\tau}} \right) \times \quad (2.5)$$

$$\times \vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) W_3(x_t, t; x_0, 0; x_{-\tau}, -\tau).$$

W_3 is the three point probability function, i.e., the probability of finding the particle at the positions $x_t, x_0, x_{-\tau}$ at the corresponding times. MBR is thus the ratio of the displacement $b = x_t - x_0$ in future, i.e., between 0 and t and the displacement in the past, $d = x_0 - x_{-\tau}$, i.e., between times $-\tau$ and 0 . One observes that the particle typically travels in the opposite direction or "relaxes back" compared to its earlier movement,

in which case b and d have opposite signs [2]. We therefore include by convention a minus sign, so that MBR is positive in these cases.

In contrast to the definition provided in Ref. [2], we have made here explicit that $|d| < l$ is excluded, with length parameter $l > 0$. We use in Eq. (2.5) a Heaviside step function $\theta(x)$ in the following factor

$$\vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) = \frac{\theta(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}| - l)}{\langle \theta(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}| - l) \rangle}. \quad (2.6)$$

As mentioned, the factor $\vartheta_l(|x_\tau - x_0|)$ excludes the region of vanishing denominator in Eq. (2.5). The denominator in Eq. (2.6) is introduced for normalization ¹. This definition of MBR in Eq. (2.5) has a practical implementation in data from experiments or simulations; instances with $|x_\tau - x_0| < l$ are excluded from trajectories. In other words, the object $\langle \theta(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}| - l) \rangle$ needs not to be evaluated explicitly. A sample code for evaluation of MBR of a Brownian particle in a harmonic potential can be found at SI. In Ref. [2], MBR was evaluated in the limits of small τ and small l . The existence of these limits cannot be expected a priori. We continue here by analyzing MBR for finite l and finite τ .

To illustrate the meaning of the condition, we give the following equivalent formulation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) &= \int d d d b \left(-\frac{b}{d} \right) \vartheta_l(|d|) p(b, d) \\ &= \int d d \left(-\frac{\langle b \rangle_d}{d} \right) \vartheta_l(|d|) p(d). \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

Here $\langle b \rangle_d = \langle x_t - x_0 \rangle_d = \int d b [b p(b|d)]$ is the conditional average of the displacement $b = x_t - x_0$ given d . Eq. (2.7) shows that MBR probes how conditions affect the movement of the particle. Division by d , despite the need of a length parameter l , is advantageous, as it renders MBR dimensionless. This gives MBR a quantitative meaning, which we expect to allow useful quantitative comparison of different systems.

2.4. MBR in stationarity

2.4.1. Long time limit of MBR and time reversal

In this subsection, we reproduce for completeness some of the results given in Ref. [2]. We will in this subsection discuss stationary systems in confinement. We thus assume that a stationary distribution $W_1(x)$ with a finite mean $\langle x \rangle$ exists. We also assume that

¹ $\langle \theta(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}| - l) \rangle$ is nonzero if displacements $|d| \geq l$ occur.

the joint three-point distribution function can be separated for $t \rightarrow \infty$, i.e.,

$$\langle x \rangle = \int dx x W_1(x) \text{ with } \langle x \rangle \text{ finite,} \quad (2.8a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} W_3(x_t, t; x_0, 0; x_{-\tau}, -\tau) \\ = W_1(x_t) W_2(x_0, 0; x_{-\tau}, -\tau). \end{aligned} \quad (2.8b)$$

We introduced the joint two-point probability W_2 [26]. In this subsection, we assume the following symmetry of W_2

$$W_2(x_t, t; x_0, 0) = W_2(x_0, t; x_t, 0), \quad (2.9)$$

which is the usual condition for detailed balance for the joint distribution [26, 40]. We insert Eq. (2.8) in the definition of MBR, Eq. (2.5), and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \int dx_t dx_0 dx_{-\tau} \left(-\frac{x_t - x_0}{x_0 - x_{-\tau}} \right) \times \\ \times \vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) W_1(x_t) W_2(x_0, 0; x_{-\tau}, -\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} = \int dx_0 dx_{-\tau} \left(-\frac{\langle x \rangle - x_0}{x_0 - x_{-\tau}} \right) \times \\ \times \vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) W_2(x_0, 0; x_{-\tau}, -\tau). \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

Evaluating half of Eq. (2.11) by a change of variables, $x_0 \leftrightarrow x_{-\tau}$ yields a form in terms of the difference of W_2 with arguments exchanged,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \frac{1}{2} + \\ \frac{1}{2} \int dx_0 dx_{-\tau} \left(-\frac{\langle x \rangle - x_0}{x_0 - x_{-\tau}} \right) \vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) \times \\ \times [W_2(x_0, 0; x_{-\tau}, -\tau) - W_2(x_{-\tau}, 0; x_0, -\tau)], \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

The term in the second line vanishes when inserting Eq. (2.9). The long time value of MBR is thus

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) \stackrel{(2.8)\&(2.9)}{=} \frac{1}{2}. \quad (2.13)$$

We conclude that, if Eq. (2.13) is violated and Eq. (2.8) holds, Eq. (2.9), i.e., detailed balance, must be broken. Notably, the result in Eq. (2.13) is independent of the time period τ , and it is independent of the length parameter l .

Eq. (2.13) is not restricted to particle position x . It is generally valid for observables A with $\pi A = \epsilon A$, $\epsilon \in \{-1, 1\}$ with π the kinematic reversal operator and the corresponding detailed balance condition $W_2(A_t, t; A_0, 0) = W_2(\epsilon A_0, t; \epsilon A_t, 0)$. We provide the corresponding general derivations in appendix A.1.

2.4.2. Fluctuation theorem

In this subsection we assume Eq. (2.8) to be given, without assuming symmetry of W_2 . We introduce path probability $p[x(t)]$, so that, with detailed balance, $p[x(t)] = p[\theta x(t)]$ for any path, with bracket [...] indicating the functional dependence on $x(t)$. The path probabilities of $x(t)$ and $\theta x(t)$ yield a fluctuation theorem for MBR. The stochastic total change of entropy for the stationary process is defined as [33, 53, 54, 79]

$$s[x(t)] = \log \frac{p[x(t)]}{p[\theta x(t)]}. \quad (2.14)$$

Stochastic total change of entropy therefore is log ratio of the probability of a given path and the probability of its reversed. We rewrite Eq. (2.12) by change of integration variables

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) \\ = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \left\langle \frac{x_0 + x_{-\tau} - 2\langle x \rangle}{x_0 - x_{-\tau}} \vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) \right\rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

Eq. (2.15) is reformulated in the fluctuation theorem [3]

$$\left\langle \left(-\frac{\langle x \rangle - x_0}{x_0 - x_{-\tau}} \right) \vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) (1 + e^{-s}) \right\rangle = 1. \quad (2.16)$$

Note that for any observable $O(x(t))$ the average of the time reversed observable can be rewritten as

$$\langle O[\theta x(t)] \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}x(t) O[x(t)] \frac{p[\theta x(t)]}{p[x(t)]} p[x(t)] \quad (2.17)$$

$$= \langle O[x(t)] e^{-s} \rangle \quad (2.18)$$

using entropy production as defined in Eq. (2.14) and $\mathcal{D}x(t)$ denoting a path integral. The fluctuation theorem Eq. (2.16) therefore states that the long time value of MBR evaluated from original and reversed dynamics add up to unity

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} (\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) + \mathcal{M}_r(\tau, t, l)) \\ = \left\langle -\frac{\langle x \rangle - x_0}{x_0 - x_{-\tau}} \vartheta_l(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|) \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\langle x \rangle - x_{-\tau}}{x_{-\tau} - x_0} \vartheta_l(|x_{-\tau} - x_0|) \right\rangle = 1, \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

where we introduced $\mathcal{M}_r(\tau, t, l)$, the MBR evaluated from time backward trajectories. Notably, the result in Eq. (2.19) is independent of the time period τ , and it is independent of the length parameter l . In equilibrium, original and reversed dynamics are statistically indistinguishable, which is equivalent to $s = 0$ for all paths, hence the long time value of MBR equals $\frac{1}{2}$ as stated previously.

Figure 2.2.: MBR as a function of time t , obtained from simulations of an active or passive Brownian particle, Eq. (2.20), for $\tau = 2.0 \frac{\gamma}{k}$, $l = 0.2 \sqrt{\frac{\gamma D}{k}}$ and $\frac{\gamma D_\phi}{k} = 0.2$. Blue line shows a passive particle with $v_0 = 0$, i.e., a system with detailed balance, and MBR approaches the long time value $\frac{1}{2}$. The solid red line shows an active Brownian particle with $v_0 / \left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{\gamma D}} D \right) = 7$. The long time value deviates from $\frac{1}{2}$, indicating a non-equilibrium system. The red dotted line is for the same system, evaluated for the time reversed trajectories. In this case, for $t \rightarrow \infty$, MBR deviates from $\frac{1}{2}$ in opposite direction. Their sum is shown as a dark red dotted line, which approaches unity in the long time limit, as predicted by the fluctuation theorem Eq. (2.16). Reprinted from Ref. [4].

To sum up, in a system with Eq. (2.8) fulfilled, Eq. (2.16) holds, and the long time values of MBR evaluated from original and reversed dynamics add up to unity, Eq. (2.19). With Eqs. (2.8) and (2.9) fulfilled, the long time value of MBR equals $\frac{1}{2}$. If Eq. (2.8) is fulfilled, a deviation of the long time value from $\frac{1}{2}$ thus marks the invalidity of Eq. (2.9), i.e., breakage of detailed balance. These results are independent of time period τ and length parameter l .

2.4.3. Example: Active Brownian particle

To demonstrate the results of the previous subsection, we probe a two-dimensional active Brownian particle confined in a harmonic trap of stiffness k , described by the

Figure 2.3.: Long time limit of MBR of ABP as function of τ with $l = 0.2\sqrt{\frac{\gamma D}{k}}$ and $\frac{\gamma D_\varphi}{k} = 0.2$. In the passive case $v_0 = 0$ (blue line) the MBR is $\frac{1}{2}$ independent of τ . In the active case with $v_0/\left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{\gamma D}}D\right) = 7$ (red line), MBR depends on τ , and the deviation from $\frac{1}{2}$ shows a maximum, denoted τ_{\max} . The inset shows τ_{\max} as a function of $\frac{D}{v_0^2}$, for different $\frac{1}{D_\varphi}$, with all times in units of $\frac{\gamma}{k}$. Different line colors indicate different $\frac{1}{D_\varphi}$, equidistant between $\frac{k}{D_\varphi \gamma} = 0.67$ and $\frac{k}{D_\varphi \gamma} = 5.0$ (corresponding to a spacing of ≈ 0.394 between lines). Reprinted from Ref. [4].

Langevin equations[16, 84]

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = -\frac{k}{\gamma}\mathbf{x} + v_0\hat{\mathbf{e}}(\varphi) + \mathbf{f} \quad (2.20a)$$

$$\dot{\varphi} = f_\varphi \quad (2.20b)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{e}} = (\cos(\varphi), \sin(\varphi))^\top$ and white noise random forces $\langle f^{(i)}(t)f^{(j)}(t') \rangle = 2D\delta(t-t')\delta_{ij}$ and $\langle f_\varphi(t)f_\varphi(t') \rangle = 2D_\varphi\delta(t-t')$. D and D_φ are the translational and rotational diffusion coefficients, respectively. Simulation results are shown in Fig. 2.2, where we use one of the coordinates to evaluate MBR. Simulation details can be found in appendix A.2. If the active propulsion $v_0 = 0$ vanishes, the system is in equilibrium. The blue line in Fig. 2.2 shows this case, for $\tau = 2.0\frac{\gamma}{k}$ and $l = 0.2\sqrt{\frac{\gamma D}{k}}$, and indeed MBR approaches the equilibrium $\frac{1}{2}$ value for large times t . The red lines in Fig 2.2 are for finite v_0 , using the same values of τ and l as for the passive case. In this case the long time MBR deviates from $\frac{1}{2}$. This result indicates the breakage of detailed balance. Evaluation of MBR for the reversed trajectories results in a deviation from $\frac{1}{2}$ of opposite sign for $t \rightarrow \infty$, i.e., they add up to one as stated by the fluctuation theorem Eq. (2.16). The

Figure 2.4.: The long time limit of MBR of ABP as function of l with $\tau = 2.0 \frac{\gamma}{k}$ and $\frac{\gamma D_\varphi}{k} = 0.2$. In the passive case $v_0 = 0$ (blue line) there is no dependence, as expected from Eq. (2.13). In the active case $v_0 / \left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{\gamma D}} D \right) = 7$ (red line) MBR depends on l , with the limit $l \rightarrow 0$ apparently existing. The fluctuation theorem Eq. (2.16) does not depend on l shown by the red dotted line for $v_0 / \left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{\gamma D}} D \right) = 7$. Reprinted from Ref. [4].

active Brownian particle therefore demonstrates that a deviation of MBR from $\frac{1}{2}$ detects the breakage of time reversal symmetry, and this breakage is accurately described by the corresponding fluctuation theorem.

Figure 2.3 shows the long time value of MBR as a function of τ . For $v_0 = 0$, this long time value is indeed independent of τ , as stated by Eq. (2.13). For finite v_0 , i.e., with detailed balance broken, the long time value does depend on τ . For $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, the long time MBR seems to approach $\frac{1}{2}$, and the deviation from $\frac{1}{2}$ is most pronounced for an intermediate value of τ , denoted τ_{\max} . The model in Eq. (2.20) encodes three time scales, $\frac{1}{D_\varphi}$, $\frac{D}{v_0^2}$ and $\frac{\gamma}{k}$, resembling the time scales of rotational diffusion, the time scale where active and passive motion are comparable, and the time scale of relaxation in the harmonic potential, respectively. The inset in Fig. 2.3 shows the dependence of τ_{\max} on these, by varying $\frac{1}{D_\varphi}$ and $\frac{D}{v_0^2}$ and by scaling the axes in units of $\frac{\gamma}{k}$. τ_{\max} increases with $\frac{1}{D_\varphi}$ and with $\frac{D}{v_0^2}$, indicating that breakage of detailed balance is sensitive to D_φ and v_0 : As regards the dependence on propulsion velocity v_0 , we interpret that for smaller v_0 , it takes a longer time for activity to become noticeable, and hence τ_{\max} is larger. Decreasing rotational diffusion D_φ makes the motion more persistent and thereby increases the timescales of motion. This seems to also increase the timescale τ_{\max} .

Figure 2.4 shows the long time value as a function of the length parameter l . As expected, for $v_0 = 0$, this value is independent of l . Also, for finite v_0 , the sum of forward and

backward cases is independent of l . For finite v_0 , the long time value does depend on l . Notably, the data suggests that the limit $l \rightarrow 0$ exists.

2.5. Conditioned correlations and MBR in path integrals

2.5.1. Conditioned path integrals

We provide here the derivation of MBR in a path integral formalism. This can then directly be used to compute MBR for a Gaussian system in section 2.6. The path integral is formally given by [32]

$$1 = \int \mathcal{D}x(t) e^{A[x(t)]} \quad (2.21)$$

with probability $p[x(t)] = e^{A[x(t)]}$ with the action $A[x(t)]$ which is a functional of the path $x(t)$. To compute correlations of particle positions we introduce the moment generating functional [34]

$$Z[j(t)] = \int \mathcal{D}x(t) e^{A[x(t)] + \int ds j(s)x(s)}. \quad (2.22)$$

Any moment of positions is calculated by taking functional derivatives with respect to $j(t)$, which we will refer to as the source term. In case of the mean value

$$\langle x(t) \rangle = \frac{1}{Z[0]} \left. \frac{\delta Z[j]}{\delta j(t)} \right|_{j=0}. \quad (2.23)$$

with $\frac{\delta}{\delta j(t)}$ the functional derivative at time t . To condition the functional on traveling a distance d in a time interval τ , we include a delta-function

$$\hat{Z}[j] = \int \mathcal{D}x(t) \delta(x(0) - x(-\tau) - d) e^{A[x(t)] + \int ds j(s)x(s)} \quad (2.24)$$

$$= \int \mathcal{D}x(t) \frac{dq}{2\pi} e^{-iqd} \times \quad (2.25)$$

$$\times e^{A[x(t)] + \int ds x(s)(j(s) + iq\delta(s) - iq\delta(s+\tau))} \\ = \int \frac{dq}{2\pi} e^{-iqd} Z[j(t) + iq\delta(t) - iq\delta(t + \tau)]. \quad (2.26)$$

By using the Fourier representation of the delta function, we expressed the conditioned generating functional by a Fourier transformation of the original generating functional with an altered source term $j(t) + iq\delta(t) - iq\delta(t + \tau)$. The conditioned mean position

is then given by

$$\langle x(t) \rangle_d = \frac{1}{\hat{Z}[0]} \left. \frac{\delta \hat{Z}[j]}{\delta j(t)} \right|_{j=0} \quad (2.27)$$

$$= \frac{\frac{\delta}{\delta j(t)} \int \frac{dq}{2\pi} e^{-iqd} Z[j(t) + iq\delta(t) - iq\delta(t + \tau)]}{\int \frac{dq}{2\pi} e^{-iqd} Z[iq\delta(t) - iq\delta(t + \tau)]} \Big|_{j=0} \quad (2.28)$$

Note that this expression is equivalent to

$$\langle x(t) \rangle_d - \langle x(0) \rangle_d = \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial(ik)} \int \mathcal{D}\mathbf{x}(t) \frac{dq}{2\pi} e^{iq(x(0)-x(-\tau)-d)} e^{ik(x(t)-x(0))} e^{A[x(t)]}}{\int \mathcal{D}\mathbf{x}(t) \frac{dq}{2\pi} e^{iq(x(0)-x(-\tau)-d)} e^{ik(x(t)-x(0))} e^{A[x(t)]}} \Big|_{k=0} \quad (2.29)$$

$$= \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial(ik)} \int \frac{dq}{2\pi} e^{-iqd} \langle e^{iq(x(0)-x(-\tau))} e^{ik(x(t)-x(0))} \rangle}{\int \frac{dq}{2\pi} e^{-iqd} \langle e^{iq(x(0)-x(-\tau))} e^{ik(x(t)-x(0))} \rangle} \Big|_{k=0} \quad (2.30)$$

which technically only requires ordinary and no functional derivatives. Notably, the term $\langle e^{iq(x(0)-x(-\tau))} e^{ik(x(t)-x(0))} \rangle$ is a four point correlation of microscopic density e^{ikx} [85, 86]. The MBR is explicitly calculated via

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \left\langle -\frac{x_t - x_0}{d} \vartheta_l(|d|) \right\rangle \quad (2.31)$$

$$= - \int dd \frac{\langle x(t) \rangle_d - \langle x(0) \rangle_d}{d} \vartheta_l(|d|) p(d) \quad (2.32)$$

with $p(d)$ the probability of the particle displacement d in time τ . We omit here the explicit derivation of $p(d)$ in the path formalism.

2.6. MBR for Gaussian systems – MBR-MSD formula

We will in this section find MBR for a stationary, one dimensional Gaussian process by applying Eq. (2.30). Examples for such processes are harmonically coupled Brownian particles, which are widely used to model complex material behaviors [87–90].

2.6.1. Relating MBR and MSD for Gaussian systems

Consider a stationary process with displacements $x(t) - x(0)$ Gaussian distributed. For simplicity, we consider displacements with zero mean, i.e., $\langle x(t) - x(0) \rangle = 0$ for any t .

The four point correlator of Eq. (2.30) is given for this case by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle e^{iq(x(0)-x(-\tau))} e^{ik(x(t)-x(0))} \rangle = \\ \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \langle (x(0) - x(-\tau))^2 \rangle q^2 - \frac{1}{2} \langle (x(t) - x(0))^2 \rangle k^2 \right. \\ \left. - \langle (x(t) - x(0))(x(0) - x(-\tau)) \rangle qk\right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.33)$$

Inserting Eq. (2.33) into Eq. (2.30) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x(t) \rangle_{|d} - \langle x(0) \rangle_{|d} = \\ \frac{\int dq (iq) [\langle (x(t) - x(0))(x(0) - x(-\tau)) \rangle] e^{-iqd} e^{-\frac{q^2}{2\sigma^2}}}{\int dq e^{-iqd} \exp\left(-\frac{q^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.34)$$

with $\frac{1}{\sigma^2} = \langle (x(0) - x(-\tau))^2 \rangle$. After completing the square, the calculation reduces to evaluation of the first moment of a Gaussian distribution in q with mean $-id\sigma^2$ and variance σ^2 . The final result for the conditioned mean is given by

$$\langle x(t) \rangle_{|d} - \langle x(0) \rangle_{|d} = d \frac{\langle (x(t) - x(0))(x(0) - x(-\tau)) \rangle}{\langle (x(0) - x(-\tau))^2 \rangle}. \quad (2.35)$$

Notably, the conditioned mean is linear in d , which renders MBR independent of cutoff length l . From this expression we can evaluate MBR via

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = - \int dd \frac{\langle x(t) \rangle_{|d} - \langle x(0) \rangle_{|d}}{d} \vartheta_l(|d|) p(d) \quad (2.36)$$

$$= - \frac{\langle (x(t) - x(0))(x(0) - x(-\tau)) \rangle}{\langle (x(0) - x(-\tau))^2 \rangle}. \quad (2.37)$$

Note that integration over the probability distribution $p(d)$ is trivial after division by d , as it then reduces to unity by normalization, i.e., $1 = \int dd \vartheta_l(|d|) p(d)$. A useful reformulation of Eq. (2.37) is obtained by expressing the correlations in terms of the mean squared displacement (MSD) $\Delta x^2(t) = \langle (x(t) - x(0))^2 \rangle = 2 \langle x^2 \rangle - 2 \langle x(t)x(0) \rangle$. This transformation relates the MBR in Gaussian systems with the MSD,

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\Delta x^2(t + \tau) - \Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)} \right). \quad (2.38)$$

The MBR-MSD formula, (2.38), is the main result of this section. As MBR in (2.38) is independent of the length parameter l , we will omit this argument in the remainder of this section for brevity. We will discuss conclusions for special cases in the following subsections.

It is insightful to recall that a stationary Gaussian process of zero mean is completely characterized by its mean squared displacement. It is thus no surprise that MBR in this case can be expressed in terms of MSD.

2.6.2. Example: Overdamped particles

As an example, consider two Brownian particles coupled by a harmonic spring. We also include an external trapping potential, so that the system is stationary,

$$\dot{x}_1 = -\frac{k'}{\gamma_1}x_1 - \frac{k}{\gamma_1}(x_1 - x_2) + f_1(t) \quad (2.39a)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -\frac{k'}{\gamma_2}x_2 - \frac{k}{\gamma_2}(x_2 - x_1) + f_2(t), \quad (2.39b)$$

with coupling constants k and k' , friction coefficients γ_i and random forces $\langle f_i(t)f_j(t') \rangle = \frac{2k_B T_i}{\gamma_i} \delta_{ij}$. The particles may have different temperatures $T_1 = T$, $T_2 = T + \Delta T$, so that cases out of equilibrium can be considered. The MSD of x_1 is for this linear system found analytically, it reads in the considered stationary state, (see details in appendix A.3)

$$\Delta x_1^2(t) = \frac{2k_B T}{k} \left[\Psi(\tau_1, \tau_2)(1 - e^{-t/\tau_1}) + \Psi(\tau_2, \tau_1)(1 - e^{-t/\tau_2}) \right] \quad (2.40)$$

with the timescales $\tau_{1,2}$ and the dimensionless function Ψ given in appendix A.3. MBR of the particle is then found via Eq. (2.38). We restrict, for simplicity of discussion, to the limit of small τ . The MSD in Eq. (2.40) is diffusive for small times, and Eq. (2.38) can be rewritten in the limit of $\tau \rightarrow 0$,

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{M}(t, \tau) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\frac{d}{dt'} \Delta x^2(t')|_{t'=t}}{\frac{d}{dt'} \Delta x^2(t')|_{t'=0}} \right). \quad (2.41)$$

In this limit, MBR is thus related to time derivatives of MSD. We will use Eq. (2.41) in the following.

It is insightful to consider the case of $k' \ll k$, for which the time scales separate, i.e., in this limit, $\tau_1 \ll \tau_2$, with

$$\tau_1 = \frac{\gamma_1}{k} \frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2} \quad (2.42)$$

$$\tau_2 = \frac{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2}{2k'}. \quad (2.43)$$

In this limit, τ_1 is the relaxation time of the bond between the particles, and τ_2 is the time of relaxation in the external trap.

For $t \ll \tau_1$, the particle dynamics is that of a free particle, i.e., $\Delta x^2(t) = 2tk_B T/\gamma_1$, and MBR in Eq. (2.41) vanishes. A free Brownian particle shows zero MBR.

For $\tau_1 \ll t \ll \tau_2$, MSD shows an intermediate diffusive regime,

$$\Delta x^2(t) = 2t \left[\frac{k_B T}{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2} + \frac{k_B \Delta T \gamma_2}{(\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)^2} \right]. \quad (2.44)$$

Figure 2.5.: MBR for two coupled Brownian particles in a harmonic potential with $\frac{k'}{k} = 0.003$ (Eq. (2.39), analytical solution using Eq. (2.41)). (a) shows the small time window $t \ll \tau_2$. Solid lines give equilibrium cases $T_1 = T_2 = T$ for different ratios of friction coefficients γ_i . Dotted line shows $\frac{\Delta T}{T} = 3$ and $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} = 1$. Horizontal lines at the right indicate the plateau of Eq. (2.45). (b) Same curves on logarithmic time axis, illustrating the different time regimes, including approach of $\frac{1}{2}$ for $t \gg \tau_2$. Inset shows the dependence of the MBR on τ at different t for $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} = 1$. Reprinted from Ref. [4].

In this time window, \mathcal{M} , using Eq. (2.41), is nearly time independent, i.e., it shows a plateau of height

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2} - \frac{\Delta T}{T} \frac{\gamma_1 \gamma_2}{(\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)^2} \right). \quad (2.45)$$

Fig. 2.5 shows example curves of MBR of this model, for a ratio of $k'/k = 0.003$, in which the two time scales are well separated.

Fig. 2.5a) shows the time window $t \ll \tau_2$, demonstrating that the curves indeed plateau at values given by Eq. (2.45). Notably, for $\Delta T = 0$, the plateau of Eq. (2.45) is bound between 0 and $\frac{1}{2}$, and it can take negative values for finite ΔT .

For $t \gg \tau_2$, the MSD saturates to its final, time independent value. In this limit, MBR found via Eq. (2.41), approaches the value $\frac{1}{2}$, for any values of parameters in Eq. (2.39). Fig. 2.5b) uses a logarithmic time axis to illustrate the three mentioned time regimes, displaying the final approach to $\frac{1}{2}$ of all curves shown.

It is important to realize that the stochastic Gaussian 1d process of x_1 in Eq. (2.39) is time reversal symmetric [2, 91], i.e., Eq. (2.9) holds, for any sets of parameters. This is the reason why, MBR, for $t \gg \tau_2$ must approach $\frac{1}{2}$ to obey Eq. (2.13).

We may use this example to illustrate the case of "bulk" referred to in Ref. [2]. Let τ_2 be so large (i.e., k' be so small), that MBR can only be resolved (e.g. due to experimental limitations) for $t \ll \tau_2$. MBR curves in this case may look similar as shown in Fig. 2.5a) [2]. One has to keep in mind that, during this time window, where MSD still grows as a function of time, a deviation of MBR from $\frac{1}{2}$ is not related to broken detailed balance.

This observation was stated as "MBR is not a marker for broken detailed balance in bulk" in Ref. [2].

We conclude this section by noting that the model of Eq. (2.39) may be extended to an arbitrary number of connected overdamped degrees. In a setting of equilibrium, i.e., all temperatures equal, the corresponding Smoluchowski equation [85] allows an expansion in eigenfunctions to yield for the MSD [26] of one of the degrees

$$\Delta x^2(t) = \sum_n |c_n|^2 (1 - e^{-\lambda_n t}). \quad (2.46)$$

The eigenvalues λ_n are real and non-negative, as are the expansion coefficients $|c_n|^2$. Inserting Eq. (2.46) into Eq. (2.38), we find

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_n |c_n|^2 (1 - e^{-\lambda_n \tau}) e^{-\lambda_n t}}{\sum_n |c_n|^2 (1 - e^{-\lambda_n \tau})} \right). \quad (2.47)$$

From Eq. (2.47), MBR for this overdamped equilibrium system, is a monotonic function of time, and rests between 0 and $\frac{1}{2}$

$$0 \leq \frac{d}{dt} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t), \quad (2.48)$$

$$0 \leq \mathcal{M}(\tau, t) \leq \frac{1}{2}. \quad (2.49)$$

2.7. Density Mean Back Relaxation marks broken detailed balance in confinement and bulk

As emphasized in section 2.6, for large systems (sometimes termed as bulk), it may take a long time for the limit of Eq. (2.8b) to be approached, i.e., the long time limit of Eq. (2.13) may not be reachable in practice.

This challenge can be overcome by introducing observables that show well defined mean values even in the limit of large system size. We propose here to use the microscopic density in Fourier space [86] (for simplicity restricting to a one dimensional wave vector q)

$$\rho_q(t) = \sum_{j=1}^N e^{iqx_j(t)}. \quad (2.50)$$

Here, j runs over the different particles of an N particle system. ρ_q is the Fourier transform of the microscopic density in position space, $\rho(x) = \sum_{j=1}^N \delta(x - x_j)$ [86]. We continue under the assumption that the mean $\langle \rho_q \rangle$ is unique and well defined. This assumption rests on the observation that the mean density $\langle \rho(x) \rangle$ is finite for typical

particle interactions [86], so that

$$\langle \rho_q \rangle = \int dx \langle \rho(x) \rangle e^{iqx} \quad (2.51)$$

is finite as well. For example, for homogeneous systems, the mean density is constant in space $\langle \rho(x) \rangle = \rho_0$, and $\langle \rho_q \rangle = \rho_0 \delta(q)$ vanishes for any finite q [86].

We thus introduce the *density* mean back relaxation dMBR,

$$\mathcal{M}^\rho(\tau, t, l, q) = \left\langle -\frac{\rho_q(t) - \rho_q(0)}{\rho_q(0) - \rho_q(-\tau)} \vartheta_l(|\rho_q(0) - \rho_q(-\tau)|) \right\rangle. \quad (2.52)$$

dMBR additionally depends on the wave vector q compared to MBR. A global displacement $x_i + a$ yields a factor $\rho_q(t) \rightarrow e^{iqa} \rho_q(t)$, which cancels in Eq. (2.52). dMBR does thus not depend on the choice of coordinate origin. Most important, we can thus state

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}^\rho(\tau, t, l, q) \stackrel{(A.1)\&(A.2)}{=} \frac{1}{2}, \quad (2.53)$$

so that a deviation of dMBR from $\frac{1}{2}$ marks broken detailed balance. Furthermore, the sum of long time values of dMBR for original and reversed trajectories adds up to unity, analogously to Eq. (2.19),

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}^\rho(\tau, t, l, q) + \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}^\rho_r(\tau, t, l, q) = 1. \quad (2.54)$$

To demonstrate these properties, we revisit the two coupled particles of Eq. (2.39), see Fig. 2.6. Indeed, for $T_1 = T_2$, dMBR approaches $\frac{1}{2}$, while it deviates from $\frac{1}{2}$ for $T_1 \neq T_2$, with Eq. (2.54) fulfilled. As expected, the deviation from $\frac{1}{2}$ depends on q . We expect that the dependence on q yields information on the length scales of the system.

2.8. Summary

We discussed several properties of the recently introduced mean back relaxation, and extended the definition by including a length parameter l , so that MBR depends, additionally to observation time t , on the parameters of time period τ and length l . In stationary confined systems, deviation of the long time value of MBR from $\frac{1}{2}$ marks breakage of detailed balance [2]. With or without detailed balance, MBR from forward and reversed paths sum up to unity. These statements are true for any values of τ and l . We exemplify this for the case of a trapped active Brownian particle.

We point out that Eq. (2.13) is generally valid for observables that are even or odd under time reversal. Future work will investigate MBR with particle velocity, which is odd under time reversal.

Using a path integral approach we find a general solution for MBR in terms of multipoint density correlations. Evaluating this for Gaussian systems yields a relation between mean squared displacement (MSD) and MBR, from which additional properties of MBR

Figure 2.6.: Density MBR, Eq. (2.52), for the model of two coupled particles of Eq. (2.39), with $\tau = 0.1 \frac{\gamma_1}{k}$, $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} = 1$, $\frac{k'}{k} = 0.003$ and $l = 0.01$ (l is dimensionless for dMBR). Main plot shows the long time limit as a function of q , displaying the value of $\frac{1}{2}$ for equal temperatures, and a deviation for different temperatures. The deviation from $\frac{1}{2}$ is maximal for $q_{\max} \approx 0.11 \sqrt{\frac{k}{k_B T}}$ for this set of parameters. Inset shows the behavior for $q = 0.8 \sqrt{\frac{k}{k_B T}}$ as a function of time, where we note that the numerical data obey Eq. (2.54). Reprinted from Ref. [4].

in Gaussian systems can be inferred. In Gaussian overdamped equilibrium systems, MBR is monotonic in time, and takes values between 0 and $\frac{1}{2}$. We exemplified the relation between MBR and MSD via the example model of two trapped coupled Brownian particles. Studying the regime of parameters for which the relaxation times are well separated allows for additional insights: For intermediate times, the MSD is diffusive, and MBR takes (nearly) time independent values, which show a strong dependence on the chosen parameters. For even longer times, MSD approaches a constant, and MBR approaches $\frac{1}{2}$ for any set of parameters. We point out that Eq. (2.13) is valid for the latter time regime only, and the value of $\frac{1}{2}$ is found because 1d stationary Gaussian systems obey detailed balance.

We define a density MBR, dMBR, using the Fourier transform of microscopic density as observable. dMBR enjoys the same properties as MBR: It marks breakage of detailed balance, and sums up to unity from normal and reversed paths. We illustrate its advantages using the model of coupled Brownian particles: i) The final value of MBR is typically approached faster compared to position MBR; its relaxation time remains finite when the trapping potential vanishes, in contrast to that of position MBR. ii) Density MBR uses the positions of both particles as an input, and it detects broken detailed balance for the case of different temperatures, in contrast to position MBR.

Future work will investigate how the relaxation time of density MBR can be estimated a priori.

It remains open whether monotonicity and positivity of MBR in equilibrium can be proven more generally. For dMBR, more examples need to be studied, by testing it in many-body systems [92, 93].

3.

Variance of Back Relaxation

This chapter is based on sections V.A and V.B of Ref. [5], which correspond to sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 which were slightly modified to fit the structure of the remaining thesis. This part of the original draft was written by me under the supervision of (MK). Some of the words might be his. Section 3.4 is new and written by me.

3.1. Introduction

In chapter 2 we have extensively analyzed the mean of the back relaxation. For practical purposes, it is important to estimate the statistical error of MBR. In this chapter, we address this by defining the variance of back relaxation (VBR). We will also find the relation between VBR and MSD for a Gaussian process and give guidance on how to select the length parameter l .

3.2. Formal expression

VBR is given by the variance of the observable averaged in Eq. (2.5),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{VBR}(\tau, t, l) = & \left\langle \left(-\frac{x(t) - x(0)}{x(0) - x(-\tau)} \partial_l(x(0) - x(-\tau)) \right)^2 \right\rangle \\ & - \left\langle \left(-\frac{x(t) - x(0)}{x(0) - x(-\tau)} \partial_l(x(0) - x(-\tau)) \right) \right\rangle^2. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

3.3. Gaussian process: Dependence on t , τ and l

For a Gaussian process, VBR is found in terms of MSD and MBR (see appendix B for details),

$$\text{VBR}(\tau, t, l) = \mathcal{M}(\tau, t)^2 [(\alpha(\tau, t) - 1)g(\eta) + h(\eta)]. \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.1.: Variance of back relaxation (VBR) versus the length parameter $\eta = \frac{l}{\sqrt{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}$, from Eq. (3.2), for various values of $\alpha = 4 \left(1 - \frac{\Delta x^2(t+\tau) - \Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}\right)^{-2} \frac{\Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$. Gray vertical line gives $\eta_{\min}^{(g)}$, the position of the minimum of VBR approached for large α . Reprinted from Ref. [5].

We introduced the functions

$$g(\eta) = \frac{1}{\operatorname{erfc}(\eta)^2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{e^{-\eta^2}}{\eta} - \operatorname{erfc}(\eta) \right), \quad (3.3)$$

$$h(\eta) = \left(\frac{1}{\operatorname{erfc}(\eta)} - 1 \right). \quad (3.4)$$

with the complementary error function $\operatorname{erfc}(x)$. We also introduced a dimensionless number

$$\alpha(\tau, t) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{M}(\tau, t)^2} \frac{\Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}. \quad (3.5)$$

Notably, for Gaussian systems $\alpha \geq 1$.

We introduced the dimensionless length parameter $\eta = \frac{l}{\sqrt{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}$. Notably, for the Gaussian process, MBR is independent of l , but VBR in Eq. (3.2) depends on it. Note that MBR in Eq. (3.2) can be replaced in terms of MSD via Eq. (2.38), so that VBR may equivalently be expressed purely in terms of MSD.

For any τ and t , VBR in Eq. (3.2) has a minimum as a function of η : $g(\eta \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \frac{e^{\eta^2}}{\eta}$, and $h(\eta \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \sqrt{\pi} \eta e^{\eta^2}$, i.e., VBR diverges as $\eta \rightarrow \infty$ as long as MBR is nonzero. For $\eta \rightarrow 0$, g diverges as $g(\eta \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{\eta}$ while $h(\eta \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow 0$ stays finite. VBR thus diverges as a power law for $\eta \rightarrow 0$, except for special cases MBR = 0 or $\alpha = 1$.

The divergence of VBR for large η is understood from the observation that $\langle \theta(|x_0 - x_{-\tau}| - l) \rangle$ goes to zero in that limit. In other words, for $\eta \rightarrow \infty$, there are less and less occurrences of displacements $|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|$ larger than l , yielding worse and worse statistics. For small η , events with smaller and smaller $|x_0 - x_{-\tau}|$ are taken into account in Eq. (2.5), yielding a larger variance due to the smaller and smaller denominator in that equation.

The minimum of VBR as a function of t , τ and l is of interest, as one may expect the smallest statistical error of MBR at that minimum. We will continue by discussing this minimum as a function of η , starting with t and τ fixed. Notably, $g(\eta)$ shows a global minimum at $\eta_{\min}^{(g)} = 0.654334$, corresponding to a length l of $l \approx 0.92537 \sqrt{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$, i.e., l comparable to the square root of MSD at time τ . In contrast, $h(\eta)$ in Eq. (3.4) is a monotonically growing function of η , and the minimum of VBR, η_{\min} , thus depends on α in Eq. (3.2), and is smaller than $\eta_{\min}^{(g)}$, $\eta_{\min} \leq \eta_{\min}^{(g)}$. In practical situations, $\text{MBR} \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$ and if $\Delta x^2(t) \gg \Delta x^2(\tau)$, $\alpha - 1 \gg 1$. We expand around this case, i.e., perform an asymptotic expansion around $\alpha - 1$ infinite, finding, for the minimum of VBR,

$$\eta_{\min}(\alpha) = \eta_{\min}^{(g)} - \frac{h'(\eta_{\min}^{(g)})}{g''(\eta_{\min}^{(g)})} \frac{1}{\alpha - 1} + \mathcal{O}((\alpha - 1)^{-2}), \quad (3.6)$$

with expansion coefficients $h'(\eta_{\min}^{(g)}) = 5.84259$ and $g''(\eta_{\min}^{(g)}) = 6.71207$. For $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$, η_{\min} approaches $\eta_{\min}^{(g)}$, and is smaller for finite α .

Figure 3.1 shows VBR as a function of η for several values of α . For all curves shown, VBR has a single minimum. Both the value of η_{\min} as well as the minimal value of VBR decrease with α . For large α , the position η_{\min} is seen to become independent of α (Eq. (3.6)), while VBR, at that minimum, grows linearly in α , as expected from Eq. (3.2).

As is evident in Eq. (3.2), η_{\min} depends only on α , and Fig. 3.2 shows that dependence. For large α , η_{\min} approaches $\eta_{\min}^{(g)}$ with a power law, where the red dashed line shows the two terms given in Eq. (3.6). For $\alpha \rightarrow 1$, η_{\min} goes to zero as $\eta_{\min} \propto (\alpha - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. Recall that $\alpha > 1$ for a Gaussian process.

The inset of Fig. 3.2 shows $\text{VBR}(\eta_{\min})/\text{MBR}^2$, as a function of α . We see that this ratio increases linearly with α for large α , as expected from Eq. (3.2), and asymptotically reaches zero for $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ with a power law of $(\alpha - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

How does $\alpha(\tau, t)$ depend on τ and t ? To investigate this, we rewrite Eq. (3.5) purely in terms of MSD

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(\tau, t) &= \frac{4\Delta x^2(t)\Delta x^2(\tau)}{(\Delta x^2(t + \tau) - \Delta x^2(t) - \Delta x^2(\tau))^2} \\ &= \alpha(t, \tau), \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

i.e., α is symmetric in its arguments. In case of diffusive behavior, i.e., $\Delta x^2(t) \simeq 2Dt$ for large t , $\alpha(\tau, t)$ grows without bound with increasing time. If MSD reaches a finite

Figure 3.2.: Position of minimum of VBR, η_{\min} , as a function of α . Solid blue line shows the numerically exact solution, and the dotted grey and red lines show the zeroth and first order terms of Eq. (3.6), respectively. Inset shows VBR, evaluated at η_{\min} , as a function of $\alpha - 1$, displaying the two power laws with a cross over at $\alpha - 1 \approx 0.1$. Reprinted from Ref. [5].

value, i.e., $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \Delta x^2(t) = A$, we obtain

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \alpha(\tau, t) = \frac{4A}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}. \quad (3.8)$$

If MSD grows with time, there is thus a regime where α decreases with increasing τ . With the symmetry $\alpha(\tau, t) = \alpha(t, \tau)$, the statement holds true for τ and t exchanged.

Summarizing, η_{\min} takes values between zero and 0.65, so that, especially, for large α , $\eta \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$ is a useful rule of thumb, i.e., the length parameter that minimizes VBR may be estimated as of order $\sqrt{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$. $\text{VBR}(\eta_{\min})/\text{MBR}^2$ grows as a function of α , which itself depends on τ and t .

3.4. Summary

We have calculated the variance of back relaxation to get an idea of the statistics of MBR. We give an explicit expression for a Gaussian process and find that, while MBR is independent of the length parameter l , VBR does depend on it. VBR diverges for small and large l , with a minimum in between. This minimum can serve as an estimate for an ideal length parameter. Generally, this minimum depends on the MSD, τ and t . As a rule of thumb, we provide that l should be chosen as of order $l \approx \sqrt{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$. This is the main result in this section. In the first study of MBR in [2], we tried to

minimize the length parameter to increase the statistics. However, in the final analysis, the length parameter was estimated by a similar principle as presented in this chapter to avoid detector noise at very small length scales. The results here provide theoretical considerations on how to choose the length parameter. It also provides guidelines for temporal and spatial resolution for experiments. For any given τ , the spatial resolution should be below $\sqrt{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$ to apply MBR.

4.

MBR, VBR and effective Energy in cells and model

This chapter is an adapted reprint of the publication [5] and is a continuation of chapter 3. The different sections have been reordered for better readability. The experimental data was obtained by Till Moritz Muenker (TMM) and was originally presented in [2]. The original manuscript was written by me and TMM under the supervision of MK and Timo Betz (TB). Some of the words may be theirs. This chapter contains

- Section 4.1 is an abbreviated version of section I of [5] to give a context to the work originally performed and extended upon in [2] by the same authors.
- Section 4.2 is identical to section III of [5]. The analysis of the experimental data has been done by me, in collaboration with TMM. The model was designed by me and MK, all mathematical calculations were performed by me.
- Section 4.3 is identical to section IV of [5]. The analysis of the experimental data has been performed by TMM. The mathematical derivations have been performed by me.
- Section 4.4 is identical to sections V.C and V.D of [5]. The analysis of the experimental data has been performed by me. Mathematical derivations and simulations have been performed by me.
- Section 4.5 is identical to section VI of [5].

In formulas, "MBR" was replaced by \mathcal{M} for overall consistency in the thesis.

4.1. Introduction

Over the past decades, studies have shown that the mechanical properties of cells play a key role in many essential cellular functions like migration, proliferation, and development, and often these properties are dysregulated in severe diseases like cancer or Covid-19 [94–101]. A plethora of studies has demonstrated this by probing the viscoelastic material properties of cells from the outside using techniques like atomic force microscopy [102], flow cytometry [103], or micropipette aspiration [104]. However, even though recent studies emphasize that also intracellular mechanics are relevant for many cellular processes [100, 105, 106], they have been less extensively studied.

One reason for this are the elaborate experimental techniques required to probe these intracellular mechanical properties.

Passive techniques, like particle tracking microrheology [107], infer the mechanical properties in form of response functions or shear moduli by measuring fluctuations of the unperturbed system, relying on the fluctuation dissipation theorem (FDT) [35, 38, 72–75]

$$C(\omega) = \frac{2k_B T \chi''(\omega)}{\omega}. \quad (4.1)$$

It connects the imaginary part of the response function $\chi(\omega)$ with the power spectral density $C(\omega)$, with frequency ω , and thermal energy $k_B T$. However, this powerful theorem is only applicable in equilibrium. Out of equilibrium, the relation breaks down, which can be prominently observed in cells [47, 108–110]. Therefore, intracellular mechanical properties are classically determined by applying external forces to a probe particle and observing the particle motion in response to these forces, i.e., thereby directly measuring the response function $\chi(\omega)$. This requires elaborate experimental techniques like optical or magnetic tweezers [111–113]. It has been found that, in cells, the above relation can be generalized by introduction of a so called effective energy E_{Eff} [44, 47, 114],

$$C(\omega) = \frac{2E_{\text{Eff}}(\omega) \chi''(\omega)}{\omega}. \quad (4.2)$$

For example, for a probe particle immersed in cells of various types [106], it was found, using an optical tweezer setup, that the effective energy follows a power law, i.e., $\frac{E_{\text{Eff}}(\omega)}{k_B T} \simeq 1 + \frac{\Omega}{\omega}$, with the frequency prefactor Ω depending on the cell under investigation [106].

Because detailed balance is considered a sufficient condition for FDT in Eq. (4.1) [26], such a finding of $E_{\text{Eff}} \neq k_B T$ marks the violation of detailed balance, whose inference is generally considered a non-trivial problem [115, 116]. This discussion emphasizes that the quest to obtain mechanical properties of active systems such as cells is intimately connected to the question of broken detailed balance.

In previous work, we introduced the so called mean back relaxation (MBR) [2, 4, 82], which correlates particle positions at three different times. More specifically, MBR quantifies the dependence of future displacements of a probe particle on its past trajectory. In Ref. [2], we observed a linear relationship between the above introduced E_{eff} and the long time limit of MBR. Such relation was also observed in a simple model system [2, 117] of a probe particle in a randomly moving trap. In Ref. [4], we showed that, if the particle position relaxes to a well defined mean position in a finite amount of time, MBR reaches, for long times, the value of $\frac{1}{2}$ in a system with detailed balance. Under the mentioned conditions, any deviation of $\frac{1}{2}$ thus marks broken detailed balance [118]. MBR thus appears to have promising properties, which we aim to investigate further in this chapter.

MBR, introduced in detail below, depends on two time parameters, t and τ , and one

Figure 4.1.: (a) MBR obtained from experimental data on A549 cells as a function of time t , for various values of τ and $l = 0.002 \mu\text{m}$. τ ranges from 0.05 ms to 3 s. MBR reaches a plateau for $t \approx 0.5$ s. With increasing τ , this plateau decreases until it reaches a minimum around $\tau \approx 0.04$ s and then decays to zero for larger τ . (b) MBR obtained from the RHC model of Eq. (4.3), plotted in a similar manner as the data in a), for parameters $\frac{k_1}{k_2} = 1.0$, $\frac{y_1}{y_2} = 0.2$, $\frac{D_d}{D_1} = 0.5$, corresponding to timescales of $\lambda_1^{-1} = 0.475 \frac{y_1}{k_2}$ and $\lambda_2^{-1} = 10.525 \frac{y_1}{k_2}$. The phenomenology is similar to what is observed in a), with the final approach of zero for large τ as a power law $\propto \frac{1}{\tau}$, see main text. Reprinted from Ref. [5].

length parameter, l . Here we discuss the dependence of MBR on the time parameters in detail, both for cells and for a model system.

4.2. Mean Back Relaxation: Model and experiment

In this section, we will analyze the dependence of MBR on the parameters τ and t . We will initially show results from probe particles in living cells, and then introduce and analyze a model system which allows to rationalize the behavior observed for cells.

4.2.1. Experiment: Cells

In Ref. [2], we analyzed MBR from probes in various different living cell types, all showing similar characteristic behavior of MBR. Here we focus on one specific type of cell, namely A549 human lung carcinoma cells. Figure 4.1(a) shows MBR as a function of time t for various different values of τ , and $l = 0.002 \mu\text{m}$. Recall that the curve shown in Ref. [2] corresponds to $\tau = 0.6$ ms. For all values of τ shown, MBR rises as a function of time, reaches a maximum, and then settles to t -independent value [2]. While qualitatively true for all τ , the height of the maximum as well as the long time value are strongly dependent on τ . Strikingly, the long time value is negative for intermediate values of τ . For increasing τ -values, MBR eventually vanishes for all times t , as the displacement in the period $[-\tau; 0]$ has less and less influence on the

Figure 4.2.: (a) Experiments: $\text{MBR}(t, \tau, l)$ at $t = 1$ s and $l = 0.002 \mu\text{m}$ for A549 cells as a function of time τ . For increasing τ , MBR decreases, gets negative and decays to 0 from below. The minimum is approximately reached at $\tau \approx 0.04$ s. In the main panel, the x-axis is in log scale, and in the inset, we see the same data but in linear scale. (b) RHC Model: The long time limit, $t \rightarrow \infty$, of MBR as a function of τ for different activity $\frac{D_q}{D_1}$ as labeled. $\frac{k_1}{k_2} = 1.0$ and $\frac{y_1}{y_2} = 0.2$ corresponding to the timescales of $\lambda_1^{-1} = 0.475 \frac{y_1}{k_2}$ and $\lambda_2^{-1} = 10.525 \frac{y_1}{k_2}$. Initially, MBR decreases with τ . For large τ , $\tau \gg \lambda_i^{-1}$, the curve follows a power law $\frac{1}{\tau}$, see Eq. (4.17). For $\frac{D_q}{D_1}$ small, MBR remains positive, approaching zero from above. For large $\frac{D_q}{D_1}$, MBR approaches zero from below. The dashed line, showing Eq. (4.18), is the critical activity that separates the two cases. The black line shows the τ dependent minimum MBR, reached for $\frac{D_q}{D_1} \rightarrow \infty$, and given in Eq. (4.20). Reprinted from Ref. [5].

displacement in the period $[0; t]$, so that the latter averages to zero in the accessible time frame.

Figure 4.2(a) shows the long time value (here taken at $t = 1$ s) as a function of τ , further highlighting the mentioned behavior, with a minimum at around 40ms, and a gradual approach toward zero for larger τ . To understand the behavior seen in Figs. 4.1(a) and 4.2(a), we introduce a model system, which will be shown to yield a similar MBR behavior.

4.2.2. Model system: "Random Horse and Cart"

Model

We continue by investigating the dependence of MBR on t and τ in more depth in a Gaussian model system which can be driven away from equilibrium. Recall that for Gaussian systems, MBR does not depend on l . Thus, this model can not provide any insights into a possible dependence on l in our experiments. We now extend the model introduced in Ref. [2] by an additional degree of freedom x_2 in order to introduce memory. The observed tracer particle at position x_1 (the "cart") has a bare friction

Figure 4.3.: Sketch of the "Random Horse and Cart" (RHC) model of Eq. (4.3). The particle x_1 (the cart) is linearly coupled to the particle q (the horse). This coupling is nonreciprocal, as x_1 feels the coupling force, but q does not (the diode-spring). This non-reciprocity causes the system to be out of equilibrium. Further, x_1 is linearly coupled to a bath particle x_2 that mimics a viscoelastic environment. All particles follow overdamped Langevin equations. Reprinted from Ref. [5].

coefficient γ_1 , and it is trapped in a harmonic potential with stiffness κ_2 , centered at position q . The potential may mimic an elastic coupling or caging of the particle in the cytoskeleton. The position q performs a diffusion process with diffusion coefficient D_q , independent of the dynamics of x_1 , thereby driving particle x_1 out of equilibrium (pulling the cart as a "horse"), thus mimicking the active dynamics of a cell environment. In addition to the model introduced in Ref. [2], the tracer particle is here also linearly coupled, with coupling strength k_1 , to a bath particle at position x_2 [87–90, 119–121] with friction coefficient γ_2 , which mimics the viscoelastic surrounding of the cytoplasm of a cell. The Langevin equations of this Random Horse and Cart (RHC) system are

$$\dot{x}_1 = -\frac{k_1}{\gamma_1}(x_1 - x_2) - \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1}(x_1 - q) + \xi_1(t), \quad (4.3a)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -\frac{k_1}{\gamma_2}(x_2 - x_1) + \xi_2(t), \quad (4.3b)$$

$$\dot{q} = \xi_q(t), \quad (4.3c)$$

with white noises $\langle \xi_i(t)\xi_j(t') \rangle = 2D_i\delta(t-t')\delta_{ij}$. The system is also shown as a sketch in Fig. 4.3. $D_1 = k_B T/\gamma_1$ and $D_2 = k_B T/\gamma_2$ obey the Einstein relation with thermal energy $k_B T$. The trap diffuses with D_q . As the motion of the trap is not influenced by the position x_1 , the interaction between q and x_1 is non-reciprocal. This model thus breaks detailed balance for finite D_q . We refer to D_q as "activity" in the following. Notably, Eqs. (4.3) can also be obtained by starting with three particles connected via reciprocal interactions with a temperature and friction coefficient for particle q . Letting these two parameters go to infinity while keeping their ratios fixed yields Eqs. (4.3). The horse may thus be understood as a particle with high temperature and large friction coefficient.

Mean squared displacement

We first derive the mean squared displacement (MSD) of particle x_1 of the RHC, and then use Eq. (2.38) to find MBR. MSD can be determined analytically and reads [122]

(see C)

$$\begin{aligned} \beta k_2 \Delta x_1^2(t) = & 2 \frac{D_q}{D_1} \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} t \\ & + \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) \\ & + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t}), \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

with rates

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{1,2} = & \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{k_1}{k_2} + \frac{\gamma_1 k_1}{\gamma_2 k_2} \right. \\ & \left. \pm \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{k_1}{k_2} + \frac{\gamma_1 k_1}{\gamma_2 k_2} \right)^2 - 4 \frac{\gamma_1 k_1}{\gamma_2 k_2}} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

W.l.o.g., we use $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2$ throughout. The rates are proportional to the bare rate $\frac{k_2}{\gamma_1}$ and dependent on dimensionless ratios otherwise. Notably, the rates are independent of activity D_q . D_q enters MSD in the dimensionless factors $\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \frac{D_q}{D_1} g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$. The dimensionless functions $f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) > 0$ and $g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) < 0$ are given in Appendix C.1, and are independent of D_q . The RHC model thus shows short time diffusion, i.e., $\lim_{t \ll \lambda_1^{-1}, \lambda_2^{-1}} \Delta x_1^2(t) = 2D_1 t$, and long time diffusion $\lim_{t \gg \lambda_1^{-1}, \lambda_2^{-1}} \Delta x_1^2(t) = 2D_q t$; The latter result is intuitive as the particle, for long times, follows the trap position q .

The activity enters MSD only in the dimensionless ratio $\frac{D_q}{D_1}$, for which three regimes can be identified corresponding to the signs of the functions Ψ : For

$$\frac{D_q}{D_1} < \frac{\gamma_1 (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \lambda_2}{k_2 \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} + \lambda_1} \quad (4.6)$$

$\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) > 0$ and $\Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) > 0$, therefore both exponential terms in Eq. (4.4) contribute positively to the MSD, and MSD has a negative curvature for all times t . For

$$\frac{\gamma_1 (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \lambda_1}{k_2 \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} + \lambda_2} < \frac{D_q}{D_1} \quad (4.7)$$

$\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) < 0$ and $\Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) < 0$, therefore both exponential terms contribute negatively to the MSD. MSD has a positive curvature for all times t . In between, i.e., for

$$\frac{\gamma_1 (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \lambda_2}{k_2 \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} + \lambda_1} < \frac{D_q}{D_1} < \frac{\gamma_1 (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \lambda_1}{k_2 \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} + \lambda_2} \quad (4.8)$$

Ψ corresponding to the larger time scale λ_2^{-1} is negative while Ψ corresponding to the smaller timescale λ_1^{-1} is positive. Eq. (4.8) turns out to be a necessary, but not sufficient condition for MSD to change from negative curvature for short times to positive curvature for larger times.

At the boundaries, where either of the Ψ change sign and go through zero, the system

displays only a single timescale. Note that Eqs. (4.6), (4.7) and (4.8) are independent of the rate $\frac{k_2}{\gamma_1}$ because all contributions cancel with the prefactor in λ_1 and λ_2 . Thus, they only depend on the dimensionless ratios $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2}$ and $\frac{k_1}{k_2}$.

We will discuss in subsection 4.2.2 and 4.2.2, how these regimes translate to behavior of MBR.

Mean Back Relaxation: Dependence on t for $\tau \rightarrow 0$

We discuss the behavior of MBR using Eq. (2.38), and the solution for MSD of Eq. (4.4). We start by discussing the dependence of MBR on time t in the limit of $\tau \rightarrow 0$, which can be taken analytically for this model,

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\lambda_1 \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) + \lambda_2 \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t})}{\frac{D_q}{D_1} \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} + \lambda_1 \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \lambda_2 \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}. \quad (4.9)$$

For the discussion of MBR, it is useful to remark, that for the given model, Eq. (2.38) turns in this limit to

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2D_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Delta x^2(t) \right). \quad (4.10)$$

MBR in this limit, as a function of time t , has three characteristic shapes, related to the cases discussed in Sec. 4.2.2. Fig. 4.4 displays these cases. Recall that the boundaries between the regimes depend only on k_1/k_2 and γ_1/γ_2 , and Fig. 4.4 displays them for $k_1/k_2 = 1$ as a function of γ_1/γ_2 .

For *small* D_q/D_1 , i.e., for Eq. (4.6) fulfilled, MBR grows monotonically for all times t : This results from Eq. (4.10) with the curvature of MSD being negative, i.e., $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Delta x^2(t) \leq 2D_1$ for all times t , and monotonically shrinking. For *large* D_q/D_1 , i.e., for Eq. (4.7) fulfilled, MBR shrinks monotonically for all times t : This also results from Eq. (4.10) with the curvature of MSD being positive, i.e., $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Delta x^2(t) \geq 2D_1$ for all times t , and monotonically growing. The two boundaries of Eqs. (4.6) and (4.7) are shown in Fig. 4.4 as a dark green and dark red line, respectively.

In between these two lines, i.e., with Eq. (4.8) fulfilled, MBR curves can be nonmonotonic. Notably, Eq. (4.8) is a necessary condition for non-monotonic MBR to occur, but not a sufficient one. Searching for sufficient conditions, we find that a maximum occurs for a subspace of Eq. (4.8), namely for

$$\frac{\gamma_1}{k_2} \frac{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)\lambda_2}{\frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} + \lambda_1} < \frac{D_q}{D_1} < -\frac{\lambda_1^2 f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \lambda_2^2 f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{\lambda_1^2 g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \lambda_2^2 g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}. \quad (4.11)$$

Within these boundaries, MBR is positive for small t and shows a maximum at a time of $t_{\max} = \frac{1}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} \log \left(-\frac{\lambda_1^2 \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)}{\lambda_2^2 \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)} \right)$. The lower bound of Eq. (4.11) agrees with the one Eq. (4.6),

Figure 4.4.: Regimes of qualitatively different shapes of $\text{MBR}(t, \tau)$ of the RHC model of Eq. (4.3). Green regime: MBR grows monotonically as a function of time t , see inset (a). In the red area, MBR shrinks monotonically as a function of time t for $\tau \rightarrow 0$, see inset (c). In the blue area, MBR is non-monotonic as a function of time, for $\tau \rightarrow 0$, see inset (b). The blue area with light red stripes corresponds to the regime, where, as a function of τ , MBR turns from non-monotonic to monotonic in t , i.e., the red solid line moves to the left with increasing τ . A red dashed dotted line indicates the boundary between non-monotonic and monotonic for a specific τ as labeled. Long time value of MBR changes sign at $D_q/D_1 = 1$ shown as a gray dashed line. Reprinted from Ref. [5].

thus shown as a dark green line. The upper bound of Eq. (4.11) is shown as a light red curve in Fig. 4.4. On the right hand side of this curve, i.e., for

$$\frac{\lambda_1^2 f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \lambda_2^2 f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{\lambda_1^2 g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \lambda_2^2 g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)} < \frac{D_q}{D_1} \quad (4.12)$$

fulfilled, MBR is negative and decreases monotonically, i.e., Eq. (4.7) is a sufficient but not necessary condition for such behavior. Notably, as is the case for the other boundaries, Eqs. (4.11) and (4.12) only depend on the ratios $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2}$ and $\frac{k_1}{k_2}$.

Also, the long time value of MBR takes a simple form which is not influenced by the presence or absence of the particle x_2 in Eq. (4.3), i.e., the long time value is identical to the one found for the case of $k_1 = 0$ studied in Ref. [2],

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau \rightarrow 0, t \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{D_q}{D_1} \right). \quad (4.13)$$

The order of limits is not important in Eq. (4.13), i.e., Eq. (4.13) is found by either order.

Figure 4.5.: Illustration of MBR as resulting from MSD of RHC, at $t = 1/\frac{\gamma_1}{k_2}$, for different τ . Arrows indicate the MSD at different τ values, and insets at the beginning of the arrows show construction of the ratio β (with $\mathcal{M}(\tau, t) = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \beta)$, see main text) at the corresponding value of τ . In the insets, the lengths of the red lines equal $\Delta x^2(\tau)$ and the length of the green lines equal $\Delta x^2(t + \tau) - \Delta x^2(\tau)$. $\beta = \frac{\Delta x^2(t + \tau) - \Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$ is thus the ratio between the length of green and red lines. For small τ the red line is longer than the green one, MBR is positive. For increasing τ , the green line grows relatively larger compared to the red one, eventually leading to a negative MBR at intermediate τ . For large τ , the lengths of the two lines approach each other, and $\beta \rightarrow 1$. MBR vanishes. Reprinted from Ref. [5].

The long time value of MBR thus solely depends on the ratio D_q/D_1 , changing sign at $D_q/D_1 = 1$, which is shown as a dashed line in Fig. 4.4.

In the following, we focus on parameters for which MBR shows a maximum as a function of t , as this is the behavior observed in the cell data in Fig. 4.1(a). See the top curve in Fig. 4.1(b), which corresponds to $\tau \rightarrow 0$. Remarkably, for the parameters chosen, it looks very similar to the top curve in Fig. 4.1(a). As the simpler model of Ref. [2] shows no maximum as a function of time, we see that the particle x_2 , i.e., memory, is crucial in obtaining qualitative agreements with cell data.

Dependence on τ

We continue with analyzing the dependence of MBR on time τ . Eq. (4.12) above, i.e., the boundary between non-monotonic and monotonic dependence on time t can be

extended for finite τ . For finite τ , curves are negative and monotonic in t , if

$$\begin{aligned} & - \frac{\lambda_1 f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + \lambda_2 f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})}{\lambda_1 g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + \lambda_2 g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})} \\ & < \frac{D_q}{D_1}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.14)$$

Notably, τ enters this expression exponentially in the combinations $\tau \lambda_i$. With increasing τ , the left hand side of Eq. (4.14) decreases, i.e., the curve separating blue and red areas in Fig. 4.4 moves to the left. For $\tau \gg \frac{1}{\lambda_i}$, this line approaches $\frac{D_q}{D_1} = 1$.

The green line in Fig. 4.4, given by Eq. (4.6), i.e., the "left" border of non-monotonic behavior, is independent of τ . The area of nonmonotonic MBR behavior thus stays of finite size for any τ . In Fig. 4.4, we marked the area

$$1 < \frac{D_q}{D_1} < \frac{\lambda_1^2 f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \lambda_2^2 f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{\lambda_1^2 g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \lambda_2^2 g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)} \quad (4.15)$$

by red stripes. In this area, MBR changes from non-monotonic for small τ , to monotonic negative behavior for larger τ . On the other hand, parameters in the blue area left of $\frac{D_q}{D_1} = 1$ are non-monotonic for all values of τ .

Figure 4.1(b) shows curves for parameters in the latter case, i.e., in the blue area, as a function of t for various values of τ . For small τ , $\tau \ll \lambda_i^{-1}$, the curve does not depend on τ , and it is non-monotonic by construction, and it ends with a positive value for $t \rightarrow \infty$, as stated by Eq. (4.13).

For τ comparable to λ_1^{-1} and λ_2^{-1} , MBR decreases and the long time value eventually turns negative (Eq. (4.13) holds only for $\tau \rightarrow 0$). For large τ , $\tau \gg \lambda_i^{-1}$, it asymptotically vanishes with a power law in τ , which will be discussed in more detail below. The astonishing similarity with curves obtained from cells, shown in panel Fig. 4.1(a) suggests that the experimental system is located in the blue regime of Fig. 4.4.

The mentioned behavior is further visualized via Eq. (2.38) above, using the MSD of this model, in Fig. 4.5. Eq. (2.38) can be written $\mathcal{M}(\tau, t) = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \beta(\tau, t))$, with the ratio $\beta(\tau, t) = \frac{\Delta x^2(t+\tau) - \Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$. The numerator of β is shown as a green line in the insets of Fig. 4.5, while the denominator is shown as a red line. For small τ , MSD grows faster between 0 and τ compared to the interval t to $t + \tau$, hence the ratio β is smaller than one: MBR is positive. With τ increasing β increases as well, hence MBR gets smaller. When β exceeds unity, MBR is negative. For large τ , long time diffusion dominates, the green and red lines approach each other in length, i.e., $\beta \rightarrow 1$ and $\text{MBR} \rightarrow 0$. MBR thus vanishes for large τ .

Limit of $t \rightarrow \infty$ as a function of τ

The dependence on τ can be investigated easier in the limit of $t \rightarrow \infty$, in which case we find,

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{2 \frac{D_q}{D_1} \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \tau}{\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)(1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)(1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})} \right)^{-1} \quad (4.16)$$

For $\tau \rightarrow 0$, this expression approaches Eq. (4.13). Notably, in this expression, τ appears in the product $\tau \lambda_i$, but also in a power law form. The latter dominates in the limit of $\tau \gg \lambda_i^{-1}$,

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau \rightarrow \infty, t \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{1}{4} \frac{\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{\frac{D_q}{D_1} \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \tau}. \quad (4.17)$$

For large τ , the MBR vanishes as a power law, and not, as might be naively expected, exponentially.

Figure 4.2(b) shows the limit of $t \rightarrow \infty$ as a function of τ for various values of D_q/D_1 . The curves start at $\tau = 0$, with the value given by Eq. (4.13). For large τ , MBR approaches zero with the power law of Eq. (4.17). The power law changes sign when $\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) = 0$, which corresponds to

$$\frac{D_q}{D_1} = -\frac{f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)} \quad (4.18)$$

Notably, at this value of D_q/D_1 , the power law vanishes, and MBR approaches zero exponentially with τ . This critical activity as a function of $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2}$ is also shown as the blue dotted line in Fig. 4.4.

Eq. (4.18) and Eq. (4.13) thus give rise to a range of activity values for which the large t limit, as a function of time τ , changes sign from positive to negative. This occurs for

$$-\frac{f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)} < \frac{D_q}{D_1} < 1 \quad (4.19)$$

For very large activity, $D_q/D_1 \rightarrow \infty$, $\mathcal{M}(\tau, t \rightarrow \infty)$ approaches a limiting line, given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}_{\min}(\tau, t \rightarrow \infty) &= \frac{1}{2} \frac{g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)(1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)(1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})}{2\tau + g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)(1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)(1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

In the RHC model of Eq. (4.3), MBR cannot fall below this line. This line is shown in Fig. 4.2 as a thick black line. For $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, it approaches zero as $\frac{g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{2\tau}$. For $\tau \rightarrow 0$,

it diverges as $\frac{g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)\lambda_1^2 + g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)\lambda_2^2}{2\tau}$, in agreement with the finding of Eq. (4.13) that, in the limit $\tau \rightarrow 0$, MBR can reach arbitrary negative values.

The surprising agreement of the curves shown in Fig. 4.2(a) and (b) is a further support that the simple model captures the system in a cell in many aspects qualitatively. Notably, the experimental curve in Fig. 4.2(a) crosses from positive to negative, i.e., indicating to be in the range of Eq. (4.19).

4.3. MBR and effective energy

As discussed in the introduction, we observed in Ref. [2] a surprising phenomenological relation between MBR and effective energy (see Eq. (4.21) below for its definition). While in Ref. [2], we restricted to small values of τ , we will here consider a range of τ values.

4.3.1. Effective energy and FDT

The effective energy $E_{\text{eff}}(\omega)$ is defined as the ratio of correlation and response function at frequency ω ,

$$E_{\text{eff}}(\omega) = \frac{\omega C(\omega)}{2\chi''(\omega)}. \quad (4.21)$$

For systems obeying detailed balance, FDT is recovered with $E_{\text{eff}} = k_B T$. Studying E_{eff} is thus one way of quantifying the violation of FDT and of detailed balance.

4.3.2. Effective energy and MBR in RHC model system

For the RHC model of Eq. (4.3), response function and correlation in Eq. (4.2) can be found analytically, see appendix C for the detailed calculation [11, 14, 123]. Notably, the linear response function χ is independent of the activity parameter D_q , so that the dependence of the ratio of χ and C on D_q results purely from the correlation C . E_{eff} can thus be found as the ratio of correlation taken at D_q and at $D_q = 0$,

$$\frac{E_{\text{eff}}}{k_B T} = \frac{\langle x(\omega)x(-\omega) \rangle}{\langle x(\omega)x(-\omega) \rangle_{D_q=0}} \quad (4.22)$$

$$= 1 + \frac{D_q k_2^2}{D_1 \gamma_1^2} \frac{1}{\omega^2} \frac{1}{\frac{k_1^2}{\gamma_2^2} + \omega^2} \quad (4.23)$$

$$\stackrel{\omega \rightarrow 0}{=} 1 + \frac{D_q k_2^2}{D_1 \gamma_1^2} \frac{1}{\omega^2} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}} \quad (4.24)$$

$$= 1 + \frac{E_0}{k_B T} \frac{\omega_c^2}{\omega^2}. \quad (4.25)$$

In the third line, we took the limit $\omega \rightarrow 0$ to identify the asymptotic behavior, and we introduced the "corner" frequency $\omega_c^2 = \frac{k_2^2}{\gamma_1^2}$. We extract the amplitude

$$E_0 = k_B T \frac{D_q}{D_1} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}}. \quad (4.26)$$

E_0 depends on activity $\frac{D_q}{D_1}$ and on the ratio $\frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}$ of the friction of bath and tracer particles. For $\gamma_2 \ll \gamma_1$, we recover the case studied in Ref. [2], where particle x_2 is absent, and $E_0 = k_B T D_q / D_1$.

Eq. (4.16) can be solved for D_q/D_1 in terms of MBR (we use for brevity, in the following equations, notation $M \equiv \mathcal{M}(\tau, t \rightarrow \infty)$),

$$\frac{D_q}{D} = \frac{(1 - 2M)(F_{12} + F_{21})}{4M \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \tau - (1 - 2M)(G_{12} + G_{21})} \quad (4.27)$$

with abbreviations

$$F_{ij} = f(\lambda_i, \lambda_j)(1 - e^{-\lambda_i \tau}), \quad (4.28)$$

$$G_{ij} = g(\lambda_i, \lambda_j)(1 - e^{-\lambda_i \tau}). \quad (4.29)$$

With Eq. (4.26), this yields a relation between E_0 and M ,

$$\frac{E_0}{k_B T} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}} \frac{(1 - 2M)(F_{12} + F_{21})}{4M \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \tau - (1 - 2M)(G_{12} + G_{21})}. \quad (4.30)$$

Figure 4.6(b) shows E_0 as a function of M from Eq. (4.30) for various values of τ . In the limit $\tau \rightarrow 0$, Eq. (4.30) simplifies to the linear relation $\frac{E_0}{k_B T} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}}(1 - 2M)$, which was displayed in Ref. [2] (for $\gamma_2 \ll \gamma_1$). Such relation is also observed for cell data. For finite τ , the relation is curved, as seen in Fig. 4.6(b). Even in these cases, for moderate deviations of MBR from $\frac{1}{2}$, a linear relation is found

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E_0}{k_B T} &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}} \times \\ &\times \frac{e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}(\lambda_2 - \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1}) - \lambda_2 - (e^{-\lambda_2 \tau}(\lambda_1 - \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1}) - \lambda_1)}{\frac{k_2}{\gamma_1}(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)\tau} \times \end{aligned} \quad (4.31)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\times (1 - 2M) + \mathcal{O}((1 - 2M)^2) \\ &= \frac{\lambda(\tau)}{k_B T} \left(M - \frac{1}{2} \right) + \mathcal{O} \left(\left(M - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.32)$$

The slope of this linear relation, $\lambda(\tau)$, decreases with τ , as is visible in Fig. 4.6(b).

Figure 4.7(b) shows the slope $\lambda(\tau)$ as a function of τ , for various ratios of γ_1/γ_2 , showing the mentioned decrease. For large τ , $\tau \gg \{\lambda_1^{-1}, \lambda_2^{-1}\}$, the slope decreases with a power

Figure 4.6.: (a) Amplitude E_0 of effective energy against the long time limit of MBR for multiple τ between 5×10^{-5} s and 0.01 s, for different cell types as labeled. For each τ value the values from different cells fall on a straight line, which is fitted and also shown. For increasing τ the slope of that line decreases. (b) Effective energy amplitude E_0 against the long time limit of MBR for $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} = 0.2$ and $\frac{k_1}{k_2} = 1.0$ in the RHC model of Eq. (4.3). Color indicates the respective τ . For small τ the relation between E_0 and MBR is linear, and it is curved for larger τ . Close to $\text{MBR} = 1/2$, it is linear for any τ , see main text. Reprinted from Ref. [5].

law τ^{-1} , i.e., in this limit,

$$\frac{E_0}{k_B T} = -\frac{2}{1 + \frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}} \frac{\gamma_1}{k_2 \tau} \left(M - \frac{1}{2} \right) + \mathcal{O} \left(\left(M - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right). \quad (4.33)$$

Interestingly, the prefactor of the power law in Eq. (4.33) is very similar to the result of λ for $\tau \rightarrow 0$ found above. What is the range of validity of the linear relation in Eq. (4.32)? It must break if \mathcal{M} approaches its minimum as a function of activity \mathcal{M}_{\min} given in Eq. (4.20).

In this case, increasing activity $\frac{D_q}{D}$ does no longer decrease M , as seen in Fig. 4.2(b). As E_0 in Eq. (4.26) increases with D_q , independent of τ , the linear relation can then no longer hold. This lower bound for MBR depends on τ and diverges in the limit $\tau \rightarrow 0$. A smaller τ , therefore, increases the range where the long time value of MBR is sensitive to an increase of the driving $\frac{D_q}{D}$.

For larger τ , M comes closer to its minimum, and the relation between M and E_0 must become less precise. We will thus, in our experiments, restrict to the range where M decreases as a function of τ (see Fig. 4.2(a)).

4.3.3. Experiment: Effective energy and MBR relation for various τ

In a previous study [2], we determined the effective energy and the viscoelastic properties of 8 different cell types and cell conditions using optical tweezers based active and

Figure 4.7.: (a) Slope $\lambda(t)$ of the linear relation between E_0 and long time limit of MBR, extracted from Fig. 4.6(a), against τ . The magnitude of the slope decreases with increasing τ . The grey dotted line shows MBR as a function of time t of Fig. 4.1a) for $\tau = 1.82$ ms, shifted and rescaled along the y -axis, i.e., MBR in the blue area in the inset, which shows original MBR of Fig. 4.1a). (b) Slope $\lambda(\tau)$ of the linear expansion in Eq. (4.32) for $\frac{k_1}{k_2} = 1$ and various $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2}$ as labeled. For large τ , λ decays as a power law, $\lambda \simeq -2\tau^{-1}/(1 + \gamma_2/\gamma_1)$ and for $\tau \rightarrow 0$ it approaches the constant $-2/(1 + \gamma_2/\gamma_1)$. Reprinted from Ref. [5].

passive microrheology (Material and Methods in [5]). In particular, we investigated HeLa cells, passivated HeLa cells, A549 cells, C2C12 cells, CT26 cells, HoxB8 cells, and MDCK cells (Material and Methods in [5]). This study yielded, for all cells investigated, good agreement with the phenomenological relation,

$$E_{\text{Eff}} = E_0 \left(\frac{\omega_0}{\omega} \right)^\nu + k_B T, \quad (4.34)$$

with $\nu \approx 1$ for all cell types. We chose $\omega_0 = 1$ Hz, which defines and yields, for each cell type, a value for amplitude E_0 . In Ref. [2], we chose a small τ -value of 0.6 ms for evaluation of MBR, and observed a striking linear dependence between effective energy amplitude E_0 and MBR long-time value. Here we investigate this relation for different τ values, limiting ourselves to $\tau \leq 0.01$ s; In Fig. 4.2(a), we see that, in this regime, MBR decreases with τ , see also the discussion at the end of Sec. 4.3.2. Strikingly, when we compare the effective energy amplitude E_0 to MBR longtime value for different values of τ , we observe linear dependencies for all values of τ , as can be seen in Fig. 4.6(a).

For each τ -value, the relation between E_0 and MBR longtime value can be accurately fit by a linear function (see Supplementary table in [5] for fitting uncertainties)

$$E_0 = \lambda(\tau) \left(\text{MBR}(t \rightarrow \infty, \tau) - \frac{1}{2} \right). \quad (4.35)$$

This result suggests that knowledge of the τ -specific slope $\lambda(\tau)$, as shown in Fig. 4.7(a) is sufficient to determine the effective energy amplitude E_0 from an MBR measurement in these cases. As Fig. 4.7(a) shows, the magnitude of the slope decreases with increasing τ , similarly as in the model system discussed in Sec. 4.3.2 and shown in Fig. 4.7(b).

Figure 4.7(a) also shows, as a comparison, the time t dependent $\mathcal{M}(t)$ of Fig. 4.1 a) (grey dotted line) shifted and rescaled along the y -axis. This shows that the time dependence of $\lambda(\tau)$ for small τ is comparable to the time dependence of $\mathcal{M}(t)$ for small t . This allows to estimate, from MBR, on what time scales $\lambda(\tau)$ is expected to vary. Generally MBR can therefore also be used to scan relevant time scales in the system. Returning to the initial questions, we thus extend the relation between MBR and effective energy to finite values of τ , compared to Ref. [2].

4.4. VBR in model and cell data

4.4.1. Variance: RHC model

The RHC model of Eq. (4.3) is Gaussian, so that VBR is given in Eq. (3.2). Evaluating VBR for RHC thus allows testing of Eq. (3.2) in numerical simulations [124] as well as estimating VBR for our experiments. Figure 4.8(b) shows VBR as a function of the length parameter l , for fixed t and τ , confirming Eq. (3.2) using numerical simulations of RHC. We observe the mentioned divergence for small and large l . The amplitude of VBR is to a good estimate given by the ratio of MSD evaluated at the times t and τ . Thus, increasing the time τ with keeping t fixed leads to a reduction of VBR (This overdamped process has a monotonic MSD). Because the MSD increases linearly for large t , VBR, evaluated at η_{\min} has no upper bound in this model. Therefore, the statistical error of MBR increases with t . Increasing τ on the other hand reduces VBR. Notably the curves are rather flat around the minimum, which softens the requirement of a precise choice of the length parameter l .

4.4.2. Variance: Experiment

For the data obtained in the mentioned cell, we find that VBR has a similar functional behavior as the Gaussian reference model. The dots show the variance directly obtained from the cell data, while the line shows the prediction from MSD of this data using Eqs. (2.38) and (3.2). There is a surprising agreement between the two for small τ . However, one should keep in mind that the experimental resolution is about 2nm, so that what is seen at smaller l may be measurement noise. For larger values, the cell VBR grows and lies above the Gaussian prediction. From this, we conclude that the data obtained from cells are notably non-Gaussian. However, since the curve is rather flat in the region of the minimum, the exact choice of the length parameter is not that important and the Gaussian estimate is still reasonable. Therefore, using the Gaussian estimate for the length parameter is also a good starting point for cell data.

Figure 4.8.: (a) VBR from A549 cells (red dots) compared to the Gaussian prediction using the particle's MSD via Eq. (3.2) (grey line) for $\tau = 1$ ms and $t = 1$ s. Both curves show a similar qualitative behavior with a divergence for $l \rightarrow 0$ and $l \rightarrow \infty$. The two disagree, especially for larger τ , demonstrating a non-Gaussianity of the process. (b) VBR of the RHC model of Eq. (4.3) against the length parameter l for $\frac{k_1}{k_2} = 1.0$, $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} = 0.2$, $\frac{D_q}{D_1} = 0.5$ and $t = 1.0 \frac{\gamma_1}{k_2}$ for two values of τ as labeled. The lines show the analytical prediction of Eq. (3.2) and crosses give numerical results from simulation. One can see the growth for low and high l . We note that the curve is rather flat around the minimum, which means that, especially for larger τ , VBR is rather insensitive to the precise choice of l . Reprinted from Ref. [5].

4.5. Summary

Mean back relaxation depends on two time parameters τ and t , and one length parameter l . Here we investigated in detail the dependence of MBR on τ and t , both in a linear driven RHC model system as well as for data obtained from cells. The RHC model is found to qualitatively reproduce the characteristic shapes of MBR as a function of t found in cells, namely a non-monotonic behavior with MBR first rising and then decaying with t . This shape as a function of t is found in the investigated cells for any τ , with however the height of the maximum as well as the final value strongly dependent on τ . This behavior is also found in the RHC system for a certain regime of parameters. We find a strong dependence of MBR on τ , which emphasizes the importance of this parameter. It is thus not only the future motion that is of interest (i.e., the dependence on t), but also the motion in the past, i.e., dependence on τ . There are other parameter regimes where MBR, as a function of t is monotonically decreasing or monotonically increasing. Notably, non-monotonic shapes cannot be found in the simpler model of Ref. [2]. The RHC model used here introduces one more (bath) particle, which yields memory, thus indicating that non-monotonic MBR behavior is a sign of memory.

For large τ , MBR decays to zero, found both in cell data, as well in the RHC model system. In the latter, it does so with a power law. Depending on the parameters, the power law can approach zero from above or below.

The large t limit of MBR shows, in cells, a minimum as a function of τ . Such behavior is

found in the RHC model system as well. The model furthermore shows a τ dependent absolute minimum of MBR. This minimum goes to $-\infty$ for $\tau \rightarrow 0$, which suggest that for small τ , MBR depends strongest on activity.

This finding is of relevance when comparing MBR to effective energy. For cell data, the effective energy shows a linear relation with the long time value of MBR. While this relation was observed in Ref. [2] for small values of τ , we observe and establish it here for a range of τ values. For the RHC model system, this linear relation is also found, with however a limited range of validity, which decreases with increasing τ . This can be attributed to the existence of the above mentioned absolute minimum of MBR. Future work has to investigate whether such limitations of the linear behavior can also be seen in experimental cellular systems.

For the Gaussian model studied, MBR does not depend on the length parameter l [4], and, in absence of a model that allows discussion of l , we have thus not investigated the l dependence of MBR obtained in cells here. Investigation of the dependence on l requires a non-Gaussian model, which we leave for future work. Indeed, it is an open question how the relation between MBR and effective energy depends on l .

For the Gaussian model system, l however appears in the variance of back relaxation (VBR), which we determine here for any Gaussian system. We find that VBR, as a function of l , shows a single minimum, which suggests that this value of l yields the smallest statistical error bar of MBR. For cells, the theoretical prediction for VBR is observed qualitatively, with however some notable deviations, indicating that the cellular process is non-Gaussian. VBR therefore serves as a marker for non-Gaussianity.

Our investigations have revealed both striking similarities and important distinctions between the non-equilibrium Gaussian RHC model system and experimental observations in cells. The model successfully captures the qualitative behavior of MBR, and provides a framework for understanding the relationship between MBR and effective energy. However, there are also differences: The non-Gaussian character of the cellular process is visible in VBR. Furthermore, the dependence of effective energy on frequency is different, being ω^{-2} and ω^{-1} for RHC model and cells, respectively. This suggests that there are limitations on how accurate the complex cellular dynamics can be approximated via the Gaussian process modeled here. An accurate description should include non-linear interactions, which, again, are left for future investigations.

The striking linear relation between MBR and effective energy requires more investigation, both experimental as well as theoretical.

The linear relation between MBR and effective energy found in cell data for a larger range of τ values allows to investigate this with lower temporal and spatial resolution setups, such as standard bright- or dark-field microscopes. The investigation of VBR suggests, as a rule of thumb, to use $l \approx \sqrt{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$ in experimental applications.

Future theoretical work can explore potential connections between MBR and other non-equilibrium quantities, such as entropy production [3, 33, 63, 125]. It will also be interesting to evaluate MBR for other observables, such as density [4], to detect broken

detailed balance in cells. The current study therefore provides valuable insights on promising parameter values.

5.

Entropy bound for time reversal markers

This chapter is largely identical to the publication [3]. The mathematical calculations were primarily done by me under the supervision of MK in close collaboration with TB and TMM. The original draft was written by me under the supervision of MK and the support of TMM and TB. Some of the words might be theirs. We derive a bound in terms of the mean of the anti-symmetric part of an anti-symmetric observable, which we use in the last chapter to get a lower bound of said entropy production from experimental data using MBR.

5.1. Introduction

A common way of analyzing complex systems is observation of particle trajectories, e.g., via microscopy [23, 42, 126] in biological systems [127–131] or complex fluids [132, 133]. Detecting and quantifying the deviation from equilibrium, i.e., the violation of detailed balance, based on trajectories is however a challenging task, especially if relevant degrees of freedom are hidden and non-equilibrium processes are random [115, 134–139]. Several methods for such detection have been developed.

The fluctuation dissipation theorem (FDT) connects fluctuations and response functions [35], and it is violated out of equilibrium [72, 74, 75]. How far away from equilibrium a system is has, e.g., been quantified by using so called effective temperatures or effective energies [2, 44, 47, 73, 140, 141].

Another way of detecting broken detailed balance is via entropy production, which has been found to obey a variety of theorems including the fluctuation theorems [33, 57, 58, 142]. A number of important relations have been found that bound entropy production, such as the thermodynamic uncertainty relation (TUR) [61, 64, 67, 143–146]. TUR bounds mean and variance of currents by entropy production, or vice versa. It has been extended and refined, including path anti-symmetric observables (FTUR) or to more general path weights [62, 69, 147, 148] and has been applied to experiments and numerical data [125, 149–151]. Little is however known about how bounds behave under coarse graining.

In this chapter we derive an entropy bound in terms of the mean of path-antisymmetric observables, based on an integrated fluctuation theorem. In contrast to TUR and FTUR, it does not involve the variance of the observable. We determine the optimal observable,

i.e., the observable that maximizes the bound, to be the signum of entropy production, so that a relation between entropy production and its sign appears. As this relation saturates for a binary process at short times, we argue that no better relation between entropy production and its sign can exist with the same range of validity. The sign of entropy production, and hence the bound for entropy production, can be preserved under coarse graining with a simple path grouping rule. We apply these results for a discrete network on a ring. For this network, the signum of entropy production is coarse grained under preservation to the signum of traveled distance, demonstrating how a bound for microscopic entropy production is obtained from a macroscopic observable. Under such coarse graining, entropy production can at most reduce to the original bound.

5.2. Setup and fluctuation theorem

Consider a path observable $O[\omega]$, with path ω in phase space, with path probability $p[\omega]$, and the average formally given by the sum over paths [32] $\langle O \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\omega O[\omega] p[\omega]$. To construct a marker for path reversal, the sum is reordered [152],

$$2\langle O \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\omega \{O[\omega] p[\omega] + O[\theta\omega] p[\theta\omega]\}. \quad (5.1)$$

We introduced notation for path reversal, $\theta\omega$, including reversal of time as well as of kinematic reversal of momenta [153]. Validity of Eq. (5.1) requires the sum of paths to include $\theta\omega$ for any included ω . Adding a zero yields

$$2\langle O \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\omega \{ (O[\omega] + O[\theta\omega]) p[\theta\omega] + O[\omega] (p[\omega] - p[\theta\omega]) \}, \quad (5.2)$$

where the term $O[\omega] + O[\theta\omega]$ in the first line of Eq. (5.2) is the path symmetric part of O ,

$$O[\omega] + O[\theta\omega] \equiv 2O_+[\omega]. \quad (5.3)$$

With detailed balance obeyed, i.e., $p[\omega] = p[\theta\omega]$, antisymmetric observables average to zero, and

$$\langle O \rangle \stackrel{\text{d.b.}}{=} \langle O_+ \rangle. \quad (5.4)$$

Violations of Eq. (5.4) thus indicate the breakage of detailed balance [76, 154]. While the symmetric part O_+ does not appear in the final result, Eq. (5.12) below, for the derivation it is useful to start with O_+ finite.

To quantify the path reversal properties of cases that break detailed balance, we introduce the stochastic change in entropy defined as the log ratio of path probabilities ($k_B = 1$) [53, 54, 155]

$$s = \log \frac{p[\omega]}{p[\theta\omega]}. \quad (5.5)$$

For simplicity, we will in the following refer to s as the entropy production, despite some caveats regarding this term¹. The thermodynamic relevance of s is a topic of its own which has been discussed in various works [53, 54, 155]. Inserting s into Eq. (5.2) yields

$$2\langle O \rangle = 2\langle O_+ \rangle + \int \mathcal{D}\omega O[\omega](1 - e^{-s})p[\omega]. \quad (5.6)$$

Reordering the terms yields a fluctuation theorem including O

$$\langle O(1 + e^{-s}) \rangle = 2\langle O_+ \rangle. \quad (5.7)$$

Eq. (5.7) may be found equivalently from the so called strong detailed fluctuation theorem [152], and has been stated in similar form [154].

5.3. Entropy bound

Equation (5.7) can be used to find bounds for s , and we therefore restrict to positive observables, $O[\omega] \geq 0$. This allows Jensen's inequality [28, 156] to be applied for the average $\langle O \dots \rangle / \langle O \rangle$, to obtain from Eq. (5.7),

$$\frac{2\langle O_+ \rangle - \langle O \rangle}{\langle O \rangle} = \frac{\langle Oe^{-s} \rangle}{\langle O \rangle} \geq e^{-\frac{\langle Os \rangle}{\langle O \rangle}}. \quad (5.8)$$

As expected from Jensen's inequality, Eq. (5.8) saturates for small s , as seen by expanding it in this limit,

$$\frac{\langle Oe^{-s} \rangle}{\langle O \rangle} = 1 - \frac{\langle Os \rangle}{\langle O \rangle} + \mathcal{O}(s^2) = e^{-\frac{\langle Os \rangle}{\langle O \rangle}} + \mathcal{O}(s^2). \quad (5.9)$$

Taking the logarithm of Eq. (5.8) yields a lower bound for the correlation $\langle Os \rangle$,²

$$\log \left(\frac{\langle O \rangle}{2\langle O_+ \rangle - \langle O \rangle} \right) \leq \frac{\langle Os \rangle}{\langle O \rangle}. \quad (5.10)$$

Because the conjugate observable $O^*[\omega] = O[\theta\omega]$ is non-negative if O is non-negative, Eq. (5.10) is also valid for O^* . The bounds for $\langle Os \rangle$ and $\langle O^*s \rangle$ may thus be added to arrive at a bound for $\langle sO_+ \rangle$, the correlation of s and the symmetric part O_+

$$2\langle sO_+ \rangle \geq (\langle O \rangle - \langle O^* \rangle) \log \left(\frac{\langle O \rangle}{\langle O^* \rangle} \right). \quad (5.11)$$

¹The entropy defined in Eq. (5.5) corresponds to the total change in entropy in overdamped stationary systems. In underdamped or non-stationary systems the boundary terms differ [155].

²A similar relation was derived in Ref. [157], however, with the left hand side always negative.

Notably, when adding Eq. (5.10) for $\langle Os \rangle$ and $\langle O^*s \rangle$, the linear term in Eq. (5.9) drops out, so that Eq. (5.11) does in general not saturate for small s . As will be discussed below, it saturates for a binary process for short times, for any value of s .

A straight forward way to extract a bound for $\langle s \rangle$ from Eq. (5.11) is by considering $O_+ = 1$, i.e., path independent. In order for O to be positive, the antisymmetric part, $2O_-[\omega] = O[\omega] - O[\theta\omega]$, must be normalized to $|O_-[\omega]| \leq 1$. This yields

$$\langle s \rangle \geq \langle O_- \rangle \log \left(\frac{1 + \langle O_- \rangle}{1 - \langle O_- \rangle} \right) \geq 0. \quad (5.12)$$

Eq. (5.12) is a main result of this section, a bound for entropy production $\langle s \rangle$ in terms of the average of antisymmetric observable O_- . This relation is thus fundamentally different from uncertainty relations, which bound entropy production in terms of mean and variance [69].

The condition of $|O_-[\omega]| \leq 1$ may seem to be a strong restriction of validity of Eq. (5.12). However, a bound between $\langle s \rangle$ and $\langle O_- \rangle$ can only be useful if O_- is normalizable, i.e., if a maximum value of $\max_{\omega} |O_-| < \infty$ exists. Whenever this maximum exists, O_- can be normalized to fulfill $|O_-[\omega]| \leq 1$. Eq. (5.12) is thus applicable for any normalizable antisymmetric observable. We also note that the right hand side of Eq. (5.12) is non-negative, so that any nonzero $\langle O_- \rangle$ yields a positive bound for $\langle s \rangle$.

Eq. (5.12) can be read in two ways: (i) A given $\langle s \rangle$ yields a bound for how far the mean of (any) O_- can deviate from zero. Using, e.g., a time interval from $-t_0$ to t_0 , O_- can be the time-moment at which a certain event occurs, which is then bound by $\langle s \rangle$ via Eq. (5.12). This will be investigated in future work. (ii) A given non-vanishing value of $\langle O_- \rangle$ yields a lower bound for entropy production. We will analyze this below.

The form of Eq. (5.12) is illustrated in Fig. 5.1. For small $\langle O_- \rangle$, the bound grows quadratically in $\langle O_- \rangle$ while it diverges logarithmically for $\langle O_- \rangle \rightarrow 1$.

5.4. Optimal observable: Signum of entropy

Eq. (5.12), as mentioned, is valid for any normalizable antisymmetric observable, and, naturally, the observable that maximizes the right hand side of it, yields the best estimate for $\langle s \rangle$. Which observable is it? Answering this important question has been found non-trivial for entropy bounds [65, 158], while it has a clear answer for Eq. (5.12). To see this, rewrite ³

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O_- \rangle &= \sum_{\omega} O_-[\omega] p[\omega] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\omega} O_-[\omega] (p[\omega] - p[\theta\omega]) \\ &\leq \langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (5.13)$$

³Eq. (5.13) holds also for $-O_-$ and thus for $|\langle O_- \rangle|$.

Figure 5.1.: Illustration of Eq. (5.12) in terms of anti-symmetric observable $\langle O_- \rangle$, with accessible area marked in green. For $\langle O_- \rangle \rightarrow \pm 1$, the bound diverges logarithmically. Reprinted from Ref. [3].

In the second step, we used the anti-symmetry of O_- . The inequality in the last step of Eq. (5.13) follows by noting that the sum is maximized if $O_-[\omega] = 1$ for $p[\omega] > p[\theta\omega]$ and $O_-[\omega] = -1$ for $p[\omega] < p[\theta\omega]$. This is the definition of $O_- = \text{sign}(s)$ ⁴.

As the right hand side of Eq. (5.12) is a monotonically growing function of $|\langle O_- \rangle|$ (compare Fig. 5.1), $O_- = \text{sign}(s)$ yields the optimal bound for $\langle s \rangle$ from Eq. (5.12). To emphasize this, we write explicitly

$$\begin{aligned} \langle s \rangle &\geq \langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle \log \left(\frac{1 + \langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle}{1 - \langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle} \right) \\ &\geq \langle O_- \rangle \log \left(\frac{1 + \langle O_- \rangle}{1 - \langle O_- \rangle} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5.14)$$

The first inequality of Eq. (5.14) bounds $\langle s \rangle$ by $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle$. Writing $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\omega} \text{sign}(p[\omega] - p[\theta\omega])(p[\omega] - p[\theta\omega])$ shows that $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle \geq 0$, and that $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle = 0$ only if $\langle s \rangle = 0$, i.e., Eq. (5.14) yields a finite bound for any finite $\langle s \rangle$. The second inequality of Eq. (5.14) restates that $O_- = \text{sign}(s)$ yields the optimal bound, so that any other O_- lies below it.

⁴The terms with $p[\omega] = p[\theta\omega]$ cancel in the sum in Eq. (5.13) due to $O_-[\omega] = -O_-[\theta\omega]$, and $O_-[\omega]$ can be chosen arbitrarily in these cases.

5.5. Coarse graining

A bound of $\langle s \rangle$ in terms of $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle$ is fundamentally interesting, and it is also useful, as, e.g., $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle$ has beneficial properties under coarse graining. Therefore consider coarse grained paths Ω with probabilities $P(\Omega) = \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} p(\omega)$, and coarse grained entropy production $S = \log \frac{P[\Omega]}{P[\theta\Omega]}$. Naturally, $O_- = \text{sign}(S)$ fulfills Eq. (5.13), so that, for any grouping of paths

$$0 \leq \langle \text{sign}(S) \rangle \leq \langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle. \quad (5.15)$$

Coarse graining thus leads, in general, to a decrease of $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle$, reminiscent of the finding that $\langle s \rangle$ also decreases under coarse graining [66]. Notably, grouping paths according to the sign of s , i.e., with $\text{sign}(s[\omega]) = \text{sign}(S[\Omega_o])$ *conserves* $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle$,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\Omega_o} \text{sign}(P[\Omega_o] - P[\theta\Omega_o]) \times \\ &\quad \times \sum_{\omega \in \Omega_o} (p[\omega] - p[\theta\omega]) \\ &= \langle \text{sign}(S_o) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (5.16)$$

Under this "optimal" (index o) coarse graining, the bound provided by $\text{sign}(s)$ is invariant, so that the macroscopic $\langle \text{sign}(S_o) \rangle$ yields the same bound as the microscopic $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle$. Furthermore, as the bound must hold for s and S_o alike, coarse grained entropy production S_o never falls below the original, microscopic bound. This algorithm thus provides a controlled coarse graining of entropy production, which is especially useful if the bound from $\text{sign}(s)$ is close to s .

5.6. Example: Network on a ring

To display this in an example, consider a network on a ring, where every state is connected to two neighbors (see inset sketch of Fig. 5.2). In every discrete time step, a particle jumps to the left (right) with probability p (q). For $q \neq p$, the system violates detailed balance and shows a directed flow. After N steps, the probability of finding a specific path with n_L steps to the left, is given by the binomial distribution $p[\omega] = \frac{1}{L} p^{n_L} q^{N-n_L}$, with L the number of states in the network. With it, entropy production after N steps is given by,

$$\langle s \rangle = N(p - q) \log \left(\frac{p}{q} \right). \quad (5.17)$$

Optimal coarse graining can be performed here in straight forward manner: Because $s = d \log(p/q)$, the sign of entropy production equals the sign of $d = n_L - n_R$ (for $p > q$), with n_R the number of steps to the right, i.e., $\text{sign}(d[\omega]) = \text{sign}(s[\omega])$. This

Figure 5.2.: Network on a ring model: Entropy production $\langle s \rangle$ as a function of N , Eq. (5.17), for $p = 0.57$, versus the bound obtained from Eq. (5.12) for various observables as $\text{sign}(s)$, $\text{sign}(d)$ and $\tanh(\frac{d}{2})$ using numerical simulations. Gray dotted line is the asymptotic limit of large N . Graph also shows optimally coarse grained entropy $\langle S_o \rangle$. Reprinted from Ref. [3].

system thus allows coarse graining towards measurement of the net displacement d , under preservation of the bound. We may expect that d is easier to measure than s .

Having established that Eq. (5.12) is maximal for $O_- = \text{sign}(d[\omega])$, we can test the quality of the estimate for $\langle s \rangle$ provided by it. For $N = 1$, $\langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle = p - q$ and

$$\langle s \rangle \stackrel{N=1}{=} \langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle \log \left(\frac{1 + \langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle}{1 - \langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle} \right). \quad (5.18)$$

For $N = 1$, the bound of Eq. (5.12) thus meets entropy production exactly, for any p and q , i.e., arbitrarily far from equilibrium. This is the above mentioned case of binary process, where a particle either jumps right or left.

Figure 5.2 shows $\langle s \rangle$ and the bound of Eq. (5.12) as a function of N . For $N > 1$, the bound grows sublinear in N for an intermediate range, and thus falls below the value of s . For $N \gg 1$, it approaches a linear asymptote, which can be found via a large deviation principle. We find for $p > \frac{1}{2}$ and $N \rightarrow \infty$, [159]

$$\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle = \langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle \sim 1 - \frac{2}{1 - \frac{q}{p}} \frac{\left(\frac{1}{4pq} \right)^{-\frac{N}{2}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2} N}}, \quad (5.19)$$

i.e., $\langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle$ approaches unity exponentially fast with N . Because of this, the bound for

Figure 5.3.: Network on a ring model, with identical parameters as in Fig. 5.2, here focusing on the comparison to FTUR. FTUR is used with two different observables as indicated, $\text{sign}(s)$ or s . For large N , Eq (5.12) and FTUR for $\text{sign}(s)$ scale linearly in N , while FTUR for s scales with $\log(N)$. Reprinted from Ref. [3].

s of Eq. (5.12) grows linear in N , and plugging (5.19) into Eq. (5.12) yields $\frac{1}{2} \log\left(\frac{1}{4pq}\right) N$, shown as a gray line in the graph. The ratio between this large N asymptote and $\langle s \rangle$ of Eq. (5.17) varies between $\frac{1}{2}$ for $p \rightarrow 1$ and $\frac{1}{4}$ for $p \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}$.

The coarse graining groups paths according to their displacement, i.e., Ω for $d > 0$ and $\theta\Omega$ for $d < 0$. This way, the coarse grained entropy $\langle S_o \rangle$ can be determined, which is also shown in Fig. 5.2. The curve demonstrates that it, as expected, stays above the bound. As only two coarse grained paths with finite S_o exist, it is here found from

$$\begin{aligned} \langle S_o \rangle &= \log\left(\frac{P[\Omega_o]}{P[\theta\Omega_o]}\right) P[\Omega_o] \\ &+ \log\left(\frac{P[\theta\Omega_o]}{P[\Omega_o]}\right) P[\theta\Omega_o]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.20)$$

$$\stackrel{N_{\text{odd}}}{=} \langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle \log\left(\frac{1 + \langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle}{1 - \langle \text{sign}(d) \rangle}\right). \quad (5.21)$$

Notably, the bound Eq. (12) is saturated with respect to S_o for odd N as indicated. For N even, paths with zero entropy production exist, and the second equality Eq. (5.21) is not valid, and Eq. (12) lies below $\langle S_o \rangle$. For large N , these differences vanish, so that the bound of Eq. (5.12) and $\langle S_o \rangle$ share the same asymptote. In this system, entropy production may thus be coarse grained by a maximal loss of a factor between 2 and 4, depending on p , using the optimal algorithm.

According to Eq. (5.13), any other normalizable antisymmetric observable should yield a lower bound, which we exemplify by using $O_- = \tanh(d/2)$. Indeed, it lies lower, but approaches the optimal bound for large N , because then, a typical trajectory shows $d \gg 1$ so that $\tanh(d/2)$ becomes equivalent to $\text{sign}(d)$.

While the optimal coarse graining is possible in an exact manner in this model, we expect approximate preservation of $\text{sign}(s)$ to be possible in more complicated systems, which will be investigated in future work.

Can we compare to other relations such as TUR? The original TUR is not applicable to time discrete dynamics as used in this example. We thus compare to the so called FTUR [69] as shown in Fig. 5.3. Not knowing the optimal observable for FTUR, we try $\text{sign}(s)$ and s , analytically computing the required variances for these two. Interestingly, for each of the three curves shown in the figure, there exists a regime of N where it provides the highest estimate. It is also remarkable that FTUR used with $\text{sign}(s)$ can provide a better estimate compared to using s . This shows the advantage of Eq. (5.17), for which the optimal observable is known, leading to the coarse graining scheme. It also shows that the comparison between these relations is rich and nontrivial and needs to be studied in future work.

5.7. Summary

Entropy production is bound by the mean of normalizable antisymmetric observables. The optimal observable is identified to be the signum of entropy production, so that we determine a bound between entropy production and its sign, $\text{sign}(s)$. The latter may often be estimated from simple observables, like here, the displacement on a ring. The network example shows that, measuring $\text{sign}(s)$ (did the particle move left or right?) is expected to require a lower experimental resolution compared to measuring s (where did the particle move when?). One can also estimate $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle$ by use of Eq. (5.13), i.e., by testing various observables O_- and finding the maximum deviation from zero. For the investigated network, $\langle \text{sign}(s) \rangle$ approaches unity exponentially fast with number of steps, so that the bound grows with the expected linear dependence. Grouping paths according to $\text{sign}(s)$ yields a coarse graining algorithm that preserves $\text{sign}(s)$ and the bound. The presented analysis is not restricted to specific dynamics. Due to this, it is, additionally to the here discussed discrete system, also valid for fluids and biological systems [2]. Future work may as well investigate applications to Langevin systems, like active Brownian particles, or quantum mechanics [16, 160–162].

6.

Time reversal breaking and entropy production bound in cells

This chapter is entirely written by me and is not based on a publication. The experimental data was obtained by TMM and originally presented in [2], here with additional data for drugged HeLa cells. The data analysis was performed by me.

6.1. Time reversal symmetry breaking in cells

In chapter 4, we analyzed MBR for cell data and saw that we can mimic its characteristic qualitatively with an unconfined Gaussian model. However, we have not spoken about the time reversal breaking. A key condition to prove for MBR to approach $\frac{1}{2}$ in the long limit was

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} W_3(x_t, t; x_0, 0; x_{-\tau}, -\tau) = W_1(x_t) W_2(x_0, 0; x_{-\tau}, -\tau). \quad (6.1)$$

However, in cellular systems, at least on the observable time frame, Eq. (6.1) is typically not valid. The plateau at around 1 s in Fig. (4.1) is presumably comparable to the plateau one gets from a diffusive regime on intermediate times, as discussed in section 2.6.2. However, at the same time, we have already seen from VBR that the cell process is not Gaussian. So strictly speaking, the MBR-MSD relation, which predicts a plateau for a diffusive regime, is also not applicable.

However, to determine if the cell process breaks time reversal symmetry, this is not a major drawback. Suppose MBR evaluated from the forward trajectories compared to MBR evaluated from the backward differ for any combination of τ and l . Then, time reversal symmetry is broken [118].

Figure 6.1 shows the MBR for multiple different cell types, similar to Fig. 4.1 in chapter 4. However, this time we show the MBR, once evaluated from forward trajectories (solid line), and evaluated from the backward trajectories (dashed line). We find that for multiple cell types, forward and backward MBR clearly differ, indicating the breakage of time reversal symmetry. Notably, the drugged cells, which are a modified version of the HeLa wild type show a smaller signature than the wild type cells. For those, the actin network and microtubules have been destroyed and, hence, the activity of motor proteins is reduced. This is a strong hint that the observed breaking of time reversal symmetry is actually part of the cellular process and not an experimental error. It is also

Figure 6.1.: (a) MBR for multiple different cell types for $\tau = 0.047$ s and $l = 0.002$ μm . Solid line shows MBR evaluated for time forward trajectories and dotted line for time backward trajectories. For the wild type cells the solid and dotted line disagree, indicating breakage of time reversal symmetry. For the drugged HeLa cells, both lines are nearly identical. (b) Shows the anti-symmetric part of MBR as the difference between the lines shown in (a). The faces show the standard deviation of a bootstrap (4000 samples). Given the bootstrap distribution, MBR breaks time reversal symmetry for all cells except the drugged ones with over 2σ certainty.

obvious that solid and dashed lines do not add up to one within t to 1 s, which means the true MBR long time value has not been reached yet. That means Eq. (6.1) is not fulfilled in the observable time frame as we discussed earlier, and thus the MBR does not need to approach $\frac{1}{2}$ in equilibrium. It, however, is remarkable that the drugged cells actually get very close to $\frac{1}{2}$. In the spirit of the Gaussian model, this would mean that diffusivity on intermediate timescales has to be significantly smaller for drugged cells compared to the wild type case. This could hint that maybe an increased diffusivity in the wild type cell is the result of active cellular processes. It has also been reported by other experiments that the destruction of microtubules, a part of the cytoskeleton, reduces the movement of the colloidal particles inside the cytoplasm [163]. Figure 6.1(b) shows the mean of the anti-symmetric part of MBR, which is given by half of the difference between the time forward and reversed curves in (a). We can see that it increases with t .

Generally, one has to ask with which certainty MBR detects the time reversal breaking in the data. The two primary contributions here are the amount of statistics and the heterogeneity of the individual cells. To give a measure, we performed a bootstrap on the original data and computed the standard deviation of the bootstrapped distribution [164]. The result is shown as the colored area in Fig. 6.1(b). For all cells, apart from the drugged ones, we have over 2σ certainty from the bootstrapped distribution that MBR detects broken time reversal symmetry. With that, we can say with relatively high certainty that time reversal symmetry is actually broken for micrometer sized colloidal particles in cells.

6.2. Time reversal breaking of MBR and dependence on length and timescales

Before we continue with the analysis of the cell data, we want to spend a few lines on which properties of W_3 are ideal for MBR to detect broken detailed balance. We will also analyze how MBR depends on the length and timescales.

6.2.1. When does MBR detect broken time reversal breaking: Insights from the probability density

Assume that we have a translational invariant system i.e. all probabilities are invariant under shifting $x \rightarrow x + a$, and that the system is inversion symmetric i.e. all probabilities are invariant under $x \rightarrow -x$. Under these assumptions, we can make the first observation that any two point observable can not detect the breakage of time reversal symmetry, because

$$W_2(x_t, t, x_\tau, \tau) = W_2(x_t - x_\tau, t; 0, \tau) \quad (6.2)$$

$$= W_2(x_\tau - x_t, t; 0, \tau) \quad (6.3)$$

$$= W_2(x_\tau, t; x_t, \tau) \quad (6.4)$$

is always symmetric. MBR, as a three point observable, therefore, has an advantage over simpler two point observables under these conditions.

At next, we look at the joint distribution $p(b, t; d, \tau)$ of a displacement d in time τ and a following displacement of b in time t afterwards. We can express this distribution in terms of the three point probability

$$p(b, t; d, \tau) = \int dx W_3(x + d + b, t + \tau; x + d, \tau; x, 0) \quad (6.5)$$

Under time reversal we get

$$\theta p(b, t; d, \tau) = \int dx W_3(x, t + \tau; x + d, t; x + d + b, 0) \quad (6.6)$$

$$= \int d\tilde{x} W_3(\tilde{x} - b - d, t + \tau; \tilde{x} - b, t; \tilde{x}, 0) \quad (6.7)$$

$$= p(-d, \tau; -b, t). \quad (6.8)$$

where we shifted the integral via $\tilde{x} = x + b + d$. This means the time reserved distribution $\theta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ is the same as the original one, however, we execute the steps b, d in opposite order and opposite direction. We have not assumed inversion symmetry. Time reversal breakage can therefore be expressed as the following quantity

$$\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau) = p(b, t; d, \tau) - p(-d, \tau; -b, t) \quad (6.9)$$

which we call the time reversal braking part of the probability distribution (TRBP), and has the following property

$$\int dbdd\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau) = \int dbdd[p(b, t; d, \tau) - p(-d, \tau; -b, t)] = 0. \quad (6.10)$$

If time reversal symmetry is obeyed, then $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau) = 0$ for all (b, d) , otherwise time reversal symmetry is broken. Why is $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ important if we want to learn how observables that depend on two successive displacements b, d , like MBR, detect time reversal breaking?

In previous chapters, we have split the observables into a symmetric and an anti-symmetric part under time reversal. However, we can also shift the time reversal on the probability distribution

$$\langle O_-(b, d) \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \left[\int dbddO(b, d)p(b, d) - \int dbddO(b, d)\theta p(b, d) \right] \quad (6.11)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \int O(b, d)\Delta p(b, d). \quad (6.12)$$

So the mean of the anti-symmetric part of an observable, the part that is actually sensitive to time reversal breaking, is given by integrating the observable with $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$. As a side note, this shift from observables to the probability distribution is somewhat reminiscent of the transition from Heisenberg to Schrödinger picture in quantum mechanics. Remember Eq. (6.10), which shows that the integral over Δp has to vanish. Therefore, Δp has to take both positive and negative values. In a way, the observable $O(b, d)$ has to be "parallel" to $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ to show a signature of time reversal breaking. It is worth noting that O is the full observable, which contains a symmetric and an anti-symmetric part. In case of MBR, the anti-symmetric part can not be expressed in terms of b and d , since in x the anti-symmetric back relaxation is

$$\mathcal{B}_- = \frac{1}{2} \left[-\frac{x(t+\tau) - x(\tau)}{x(\tau) - x(0)} \vartheta_l(x(\tau) - x(0)) + \frac{x(0) - x(t)}{x(t) - x(t+\tau)} \vartheta_l(x(t) - x(t+\tau)) \right]. \quad (6.13)$$

Here, $x(t+\tau) - x(t) = b$ and $x(\tau) - x(0) = d$ can be identified, but $x(0) - x(t)$ and $x(t) - x(t+\tau)$ require at least another variable to be expressed in terms of displacements. This means, while the back relaxation $\mathcal{B} = -\frac{b}{d} \vartheta_l(d)$ can be expressed in terms of (b, d) , the symmetric and anti-symmetric parts \mathcal{B}_+ and \mathcal{B}_- can not, and therefore we can not compare \mathcal{B}_+ and \mathcal{B}_- directly to $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$. So it is necessary that indeed the full observable \mathcal{B} is "parallel" to Δp and not its respective symmetric or anti-symmetric parts.

We can use this insight to visualize how $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ should look, such that MBR is a good marker for time reversal breakage.

Figure 6.2 depicts the back relaxation \mathcal{B} , without the normalization factor $\langle \theta(|d| - l) \rangle$ which depends on the underlying distribution $p(b, t; d, \tau)$. In (a) we see \mathcal{B} for a very

Figure 6.2.: Illustration of the back relaxation $\mathcal{B}(b, d)$ without the normalization factor $\langle \theta(|d| - l) \rangle$. (a) A small length parameter $l = 0.001$. The back relaxation diverges close to the length parameter as $\frac{1}{d}$ and linearly for $b \rightarrow \infty$. Crossing from negative to positive d or b changes the sign of the back relaxation. (b) For a larger length parameter $l = 0.2$. The highest absolute values are taken for $|d| \rightarrow l$. Smaller $|d| < 0$ are set to zero.

small cutoff of $l = 0.001$. The divergence for $d \rightarrow 0$ is immediately obvious, meaning that it is beneficial for MBR if $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ has its strongest deviation from zero close to the length parameter $|d| \rightarrow l$. (b) shows a larger length parameter $l = 0.2$ to illustrate this. Qualitatively, the length parameter could therefore be used to scan for the maximal time reversal breakage in $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ in d direction. This could, for example, be made more systematic by also introducing an upper length parameter.

The second and probably most important feature is that the back relaxation looks very similar to a quadrupole structure. $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ should therefore have a sign change going from positive to negative d and a sign change going from positive to negative b , at least for d close to the length parameter l . Any contributions for larger d are suppressed by the back relaxation. On the other hand, contributions with large b are linearly enhanced. So this illustration predicts that MBR is most sensitive to a quadrupole structure of $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ at the order of the length parameter $|d| \approx l$.

6.2.2. Model: Random horse and cart with double well

Model

To illustrate these effects on an actual probability density, we investigate a non-Gaussian version of a random horse and cart model. The horse q and cart x are coupled by a double well potential [133]

$$U(x - q) = \Delta V \left(\left(\frac{x - q}{L} \right)^2 - 1 \right)^2 \quad (6.14)$$

Figure 6.3.: Sketch of the RHCDW model of Eq. (6.15). The particle x performs Brownian motion inside a double well with barrier height ΔV . The distance between the minimum and the maximum of the potential is given by L . The center q of the double well performs a random walk, independent of x , illustrated by the transparent versions of the potential.

of height ΔV and the minima are separated by $2L$. The Langevin equations are given by

$$\dot{x} = -\frac{1}{\gamma} U'(x - q) + \xi_x \quad (6.15a)$$

$$\dot{q} = \xi_q \quad (6.15b)$$

with white noise $\langle \xi_i(t) \xi_j(t') \rangle = 2D_i \delta(t - t') \delta_{ij}$. The system is non-reciprocal, therefore, driven out of equilibrium for finite activity D_q . A sketch of the system is drawn in Fig. 6.3. Compared to the RHC model in chapter 4 the memory inducing bath particle is missing. The RHC can not break time reversal symmetry because the projected dynamics on the particle coordinate is fully Gaussian and, hence, time reversal symmetric [165]. In the case of Eq. (6.15), which we term random horse and cart with double well (RHCDW), the double well interaction between q and x renders the system non-Gaussian, which makes it possible to detect time reversal breakage in the dynamics of x .

MBR

The typical MBR of this system is shown in Fig. 6.4(a). Similarly to the RHC, MBR saturates to a finite value after long times, which deviates from $\frac{1}{2}$ for finite activity D_q . However, in contrast to the RHC, if MBR is evaluated from the reversed trajectories, MBR differs. This shows that time reversal symmetry is broken, which is possible due to the non-Gaussian nature of the process induced by the non-linear interaction. The anti-symmetric part of the long time value of MBR is shown in Fig. 6.4(b). We see that for small and large τ MBR shows no time reversal breaking. For an intermediate range, the anti-symmetric part has a non-vanishing mean. The value of the anti-symmetric part also depends on the length parameter l . For small values, it is positive, while it

Figure 6.4.: (a) The MBR for the RHCDW model of Eq. (6.15) for finite t and $\tau = 0.34 \frac{L^2}{D}$ for various $\frac{D_q}{D}$. The solid line shows MBR for forward trajectories and the dotted line for backward trajectories. In equilibrium $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0$, forward and reversed MBR are the same, as expected, and the MBR approaches $\frac{1}{2}$. For finite $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.1$, forward and backward MBR are different, where the backward MBR lies above the forward MBR. For $\frac{D_q}{D} = 2.0 > 1$, MBR is negative and the forward MBR is greater than the backward MBR. (b) For $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.1$, the long time $t \rightarrow \infty$ mean of the anti-symmetric part of MBR for different τ and length parameters l . For very small and very large τ MBR shows no time reversal breaking. For small l the anti-symmetric part is negative i.e. forward MBR is smaller than backward MBR. For large l the anti-symmetric part changes sign.

changes sign for larger values. This indicates that MBR should be sensitive to specific time and length scales in the system.

To make it easier to compare to the probability density we choose in the following $\tau = t$ for MBR. This means the only two parameters left are τ and the length parameter l . Figure 6.5 shows the anti-symmetric MBR for the RHCDW for $t = \tau$ and different $\frac{D_q}{D}$. Notably, for $D_q = D$ in Fig. 6.5(b) MBR shows no time reversal breakage. For $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.1$ in (a) we see two peaks with opposite sign emerging for an intermediate range of τ values. For very large and very small values of τ , the peaks vanish. If one increases the length parameter from small to large values, the peaks change sign. For larger $\frac{D_q}{D} = 2.0$, the same structure remains, however, it's shifted to a smaller τ , and the high and low l peaks flip signs. The white areas show combinations of τ and l where, within the simulation time, no events $|d| > l$ were recorded. Overall, it is very similar to what we observed for long time MBR in Fig. 6.4. The only notable difference is that values for the anti-symmetric long time MBR are much higher compared to what we observe for the $t = \tau$ case. Hence, detecting the time reversal breaking seems to be easier with an asymmetric choice of t and τ .

One may argue that the most relevant length scales might be those where MBR changes the most. Figure 6.6 shows the derivative of the anti-symmetric part of MBR in l direction. In this case for $\frac{D_q}{D}$ only one peak remains at roughly $l \approx 0.5L$ and $\tau \approx 1.5 \frac{L^2}{D}$. For the higher $\frac{D_q}{D} = 2.0$ the peak is at roughly $l \approx 0.8L$ and for $\tau \approx 0.07 \frac{L^2}{D}$, so primarily

Figure 6.5.: The anti-symmetric part of MBR of the RHCDW model of Eq. (6.15) for $t = \tau$ versus the length parameter l and time τ for $\frac{\Delta V}{k_B T} = 2.0$ and different $\frac{D_q}{D}$. The grey vertical line shows the kramers rate [166] of the equilibrium system $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.0$ as a timescale reference. (a) $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.1$ the anti-symmetric part of MBR vanishes for very small and very large τ . There is an intermediate regime for $\tau \approx 10^{-1} \frac{L^2}{D} - 10 \frac{L^2}{D}$ where the MBR detects time reversal breakage. This time reversal breakage changes sign if the length parameter l crosses from small to large values, with a value in between where the anti-symmetric part vanishes. (b) For $D_q = D$, MBR shows no time reversal breakage. (c) $\frac{D_q}{D} = 2.0$ is similar to (a), however, the whole section is shifted to smaller τ , again with the change in sign going from smaller to larger length parameters, but in opposite direction.

Figure 6.6.: The derivative in l -direction of the figures shown in Fig. 6.5. (a) For $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.1$ MBR changes the most between $l = 0.1L - 1L$. (b) For $\frac{D_q}{D} 2.0$ this is similar, however shifted to smaller τ .

at lower τ , compared to the low activity case.

Probability density

The advantage of the RHCDW model system is that we can actually generate enough statistics to sample the probability distribution $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$. As stated earlier, for simplicity, we limit ourselves to $t = \tau$, which only requires us to measure a single probability distribution $p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$. The time reversal breaking part is then given by

$$\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau) = p(b, \tau; d, \tau) - p(-b, \tau; -d, \tau). \quad (6.16)$$

Further, the system has inversion symmetry, meaning the mapping $(b, d) \rightarrow (-b, -d)$ leaves all probabilities invariant. This means it has two vanishing axes $\Delta p(d, -d) = \Delta p(-d, d) = 0$ by default, and is point symmetric in $(b = 0, d = 0)$. Figure 6.7(a) shows the full density $p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$, which is peaked at $b, d = 0$, as one would expect. In Fig. 6.7(b), we can see the corresponding time reversal breaking part $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$. It has, in this particular parameter set, an octopole structure with alternating positive and negative contributions. The whole structure is point symmetric as expected by inversion symmetry. The gray dashed lines indicate where we expect $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$ to vanish by symmetry. It also looks like that $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$ vanishes for the lines $d = 0$ and $b = 0$, however, this is only a feature of this particular parameter choice.

Importantly, we have a quadrupole close to $d = 0.5$ and another at $d = 2$. With this structure, we expect MBR to detect time reversal breakage for these particular length parameters. Further, because the pole changes sign in between these values, the anti-symmetric part of MBR should change sign. That is exactly what we could observe in Fig. 6.5. Figure 6.8(a) shows $\mathcal{B}(b, d)$, multiplied by $\Delta p(b, d)$. We can clearly see the previously described effect, namely that MBR suppresses the outer peaks and amplifies the inner ones, which leads to a finite mean of the anti-symmetric part of MBR. A larger length parameter takes out the inner peaks, and only the outer ones remain.

Figure 6.7.: (a) The probability density $p(d, \tau, b, \tau)$ sampled numerically for the RHCDW of Eq. (6.15) for $\tau = t = 2.19 \frac{L^2}{D}$, $\frac{\Delta V}{k_B T} = 2.0$ and $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.1$. The probability density is peaked at $b = d = 0$. (b) The anti-symmetric probability density $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$ from (a). The probability density shows an octapole structure, where the peaks have alternating signs. For very small and large b, d there is no time reversal breakage in the probability distribution. The grey lines show where $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$ has to vanish due to inversion symmetry.

Figure 6.8.: Illustration of how MBR and observable Eq. (6.17) interact with $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$ in Fig. 6.7(b). (a) Shows the back relaxation multiplied with $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$ with normalization computed from the density shown in Fig. 6.7(a). MBR ($l = 0.1L$) projects out the poles at $d = 0.5$ and suppresses the peaks for higher d , leading to an overall non-vanishing mean anti-symmetric part of MBR. (b) The observable Eq. (6.17) for $n = 4$, $R = 2L$ and $\epsilon = 0.1L$ flips all poles such that they all contribute positively to the mean of the anti-symmetric part of the observable.

Alternative observable

The structure of $\Delta p(b, t; d, \tau)$ suggests to define a different type of observable, which reflects the symmetries of the probability distribution. Because of the observed pole like shape, one might construct observables of the following form

$$O(b, d) = \Psi(\varphi)\rho(r) \quad (6.17)$$

with the polar coordinates $\varphi = \arctan(b/d)$ and $r = \sqrt{d^2 + b^2}$. The major hypothesis of Eq. (6.17) is that the contributions of φ and r decouple, which seems to be a good approximation in the case of RHCDW. As basis functions for the angular dependency, we choose the circular harmonics, which are essential combinations of sine and cosine functions

$$\Psi_{n,\delta}(\varphi) = -\sin(n\varphi + \delta)/\sqrt{\pi} \quad (6.18)$$

with a frequency parameter $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ and a phase $\delta \in [0, 2\pi]$. We normalize such that

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \sin(n\varphi + \delta)^2 = 1. \quad (6.19)$$

For the radial component, we have no a priori guess for a good candidate. Therefore, we simply choose

$$\rho_{R,\epsilon}(r) = \chi_{[R-\epsilon, R+\epsilon]}(r)/\sqrt{R\epsilon} \quad (6.20)$$

with the step function

$$\chi_{[a,b]}(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x \in [a, b] \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6.21)$$

which means we filter radii between $R - \epsilon$ and $R + \epsilon$. In this setup R functions as a length scale parameter, whereas ϵ is a tool to control the statistics. The function is again normalized such that

$$\int_0^\infty dr \rho(r)^2 r = 1. \quad (6.22)$$

In total, the observable is given by

$$O(b, d) = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi R \epsilon}} \sin(n\phi + \delta) \chi_{[R-\epsilon, R+\epsilon]}(r) \quad (6.23)$$

and normalized such that

$$\int \int db dd O_{n,\delta,L,\epsilon}(b, d)^2 = 1 \quad (6.24)$$

and the different observables are orthonormal in n .

Figure 6.9.: The anti-symmetric part of observable Eq. (6.17) for $n = 4$ and $\epsilon = 0.05L$ for different R and τ for $\frac{D_q}{D_1} = 0.1$ and $\delta = 0$. (a) $\frac{\Delta V}{k_B T} = 2.0$ for small and very large τ the anti-symmetric part vanishes, for intermediate τ it is finite. The same is true for the radius R . With increasing τ , the R values for which the anti-symmetric part is finite also increase. The observable peaks at $R \approx 2L$, the distance between the wells, and $\tau \approx 2\frac{L^2}{D}$. (b) $\frac{\Delta V}{k_B T} = 4.0$ has a higher barrier. The overall shape seems to be similar to (a), however, we can now clearly see two peaks. The second one is similar to the peak in (a), the first one is for smaller $L \approx 0.5L$ and $\tau \approx 0.8\frac{L^2}{D}$.

We now look at the new observables for the RHCDW. Figure 6.8(b) shows for $n = 4$ and $R = 2$ how the observable flips the signs of Δp in such a way that (mostly) positive contributions remain. For this plot and in the following, we set $\delta = 0$. Crucially, we can now use R very precisely to scan for different length scales. Figure 6.9 shows how the observable mean changes with R and τ . (a) is for a moderate barrier height $\frac{\Delta V}{k_B T} = 2.0$ and low activity $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.1$. One can see that for small τ the anti-symmetric part vanishes, as for very large τ . There is an intermediate range where the breakage of time reversal symmetry is visible. With increasing τ , the required R also increases. In (a), one can only see a maximum at $R \approx 2.0L$ and $\tau \approx 1.5\frac{L^2}{D}$. This length scale would correspond to the distance between the two minima. In (b), we see a high barrier height of $\frac{\Delta V}{k_B T} = 4.0$, where we can now clearly see two peaks. The smaller one is similar to the one in (a), the higher one is at rather small values of $R \approx 0.5L$ and $\tau \approx 0.06\frac{L^2}{D}$. It is possible that this peak also exists in (a), but is rather blurred. The length scale here is not so obvious. It could correspond to the width of the potential. All these considerations were for $n = 4$. We can also test for different n and see if the octopole structure is universal. Figure 6.10 shows different n values, in (a) for different R and (b) for different τ . The most prominent contribution is from $n = 4$, as expected, however, $n = 8$ also has a non-vanishing mean. This $n = 8$ parameter would correspond to 16 poles, which is mainly relevant for large R compared to τ . This shows that the structure of $\Delta p(b, d)$ is a bit more complex than the simple octopole structure that is obvious in Fig. 6.7(b).

To summarize the study of the probability density and RHCDW, we have seen that MBR prefers a quadrupole structure in $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau)$ close to the value of the length parameter $|d| \approx l$ to show time reversal breaking. We could demonstrate that these

Figure 6.10.: The anti-symmetric part of observable Eq. (6.17) for $\epsilon = 0.05L$, $\frac{\Delta V}{k_B T} = 2.0$ and $\frac{D_q}{D} = 0.1$. (a) The parameter n versus the radius R for $\tau = 1.38 \frac{L^2}{D}$. One can see that the strongest signal can be seen for $n = 4$, however, there are also contributions from $n = 8$, which corresponds to 16 poles in $\Delta p(b, d)$. (b) shows the same for $R = 2.03L$ and different τ . Again, there are primarily contributions from $n = 4$ and $n = 8$. In (a) $n = 8$ peaks at higher R and in (b) for smaller τ , which indicates that the $n = 8$ contributions arise from more extreme displacements b, d than $n = 4$.

poles are present in the RHCDW model. The change in sign of the anti-symmetric part of MBR can be explained by first measuring the inner peaks for small l , and later for the outer peaks for large l . For this pole like structure, we have also looked at observables that incorporate the symmetries of $\Delta p(b, \tau; d\tau)$. We found that the RHCDW TRBP is dominated by an octapole, however, higher moment poles also exist. For this observables, we could also see that there is a clear relation between length and timescales for which time reversal symmetry is broken. We also noted with MBR, that asymmetric $t \neq \tau$ seems to give a stronger signal to detect time reversal breaking.

6.2.3. Cells: Length and timescales of long time MBR time reversal breakage

We now have a more detailed look at the time reversal breakage of MBR in cells. While Fig. 6.1 already shows that time reversal symmetry of colloidal particles in the cytoplasm is broken, we look at the τ and l dependence of the long time value in Fig. 6.11. (a) shows the long time value of MBR color coded for HeLa cells for different l and τ . We observe that for very small and large τ MBR detects no breakage in time reversal symmetry for the long time value at $t = 1$ s. For an intermediate regime of 2-400 ms on the other hand, we can see a non-vanishing mean of the anti-symmetric part of MBR. For small l the anti-symmetric part is positive, while for larger ones it gets negative. The length parameter in between, for which the anti-symmetric part is zero, seems to increase with τ . A typical approach in biology and biophysics is to knock out some cellular components to investigate how they influence the overall cellular properties. In (b), we show the results of cells that are treated with Cytochalasin-B (CytoB), which

Figure 6.11.: Shows the anti-symmetric part of long time MBR $t = 1$ s for various τ and l for different types of HeLa cells. (a) The wild type HeLa cell. For small and large τ there is no time reversal breaking. For an intermediate range from 2-400 ms we see a non-vanishing anti-symmetric part. For small l the anti-symmetric part is negative and gets positive for large l . The white area shows the region for which no event in 5% of trajectories was recorded. (b) HeLa cell drugged with CytoB. Similar to (a), with a smaller amplitude and time reversal breaking is less pronounced for larger τ . (c) HeLa cell drugged with Nocoda. The anti-symmetric part vanishes, so MBR shows no time reversal breaking. (d) HeLa with CytoB and Nocoda (drugged) also shows no time reversal breaking.

inhibits the formation of actin. This stops certain motors that sit in the actin network, like myosin, and so suppresses active fluctuations transmitted by the actin network. In this case, we observe a similar overall structure of the anti-symmetric part of long time MBR as in the wild type case (a). However, here the time reversal breaking is only visible between 2-200 ms. The deviation between forward and backward MBR seems to be a bit smaller than in the wild type case, but the length scales remain similar. In (c) the cells are instead drugged with Nocodazole (Nocoda), which destroys the microtubules inside the cells, so all effects transmitted by the microtubules are prohibited. In this case, MBR does not show obvious time reversal breakage for any parameter combinations of τ and l . (d) shows both drugs combined, which previously were always referred to as drugged (HeLa) cells. In this case, we also see no time reversal breakage of MBR. Overall,

Figure 6.12.: Derivative of the anti-symmetric long time MBR for $t = 1$ s as in Fig. 6.11 in l direction. (a) for HeLa wild type and (b) HeLa drugged with CytoB. One can see that the highest change of MBR is in the region of ca. 2-20 nm and 2-100 ms.

this investigation suggests that the time reversal breaking observed in the trajectory data is somehow related to processes on microtubules and less so in the actin network. However, a more in depth analysis would be needed to say which processes exactly, because there are multiple candidates, as molecular motors attached to microtubuli or the (de-)polymerization process of the microtubuli themselves. It is also possible, since destroying the microtubules is a rather invasive process, that there is some secondary effect which inhibits relevant time reversal breaking fluctuations. However, it would be very interesting to, for example, directly target motor proteins that operate on the microtubules to see if they are the main driving force of the time reversal breaking.

To get an idea of the relevant length scales, we can again look at the derivative of MBR in the l direction, which is shown in Fig. 6.12, in (a) for wild type HeLa cells and in (b) for the CytoB drugged ones. The length scale for which MBR changes the most seems to lie in the region of roughly 2-20 nm with τ between 2-100 ms. The upper bound in l may be higher because we lack statistics for larger length l . These numbers fit roughly with the typical length and timescales of molecular motors, which have a typical center of mass step motion of 8 nm with a few 10 ms cycle time, depending on load and ATP concentration [167]. However, this is only a very crude estimate and only serves as one possible candidate. By no means is this a clear indication that molecular motors are responsible for the observed effects.

Up to now, we have focused on the long time MBR. What is with the equal $t = \tau$ MBR that we have analyzed for the RHCDW? Figure 6.13 shows the anti-symmetric MBR in (a) for HeLa cells and (b) for A549 cells. Surprisingly, there is no huge time reversal breakage detected by MBR. This suggests that the asymmetry between t and τ is an important feature for MBR in cells. We have also seen this for RHCDW, but for cells, the effect seems to be even more pronounced.

To sum up, we have seen that MBR shows time reversal breakage of trajectories of colloidal particles in living cells. In HeLa cells this time reversal breakage vanishes if the microtubules are inhibited, which suggests that there is some underlying connection

Figure 6.13.: Anti-symmetric of MBR for $\tau = t$ for different τ and length parameters l . (a) HeLa cells and (b) A549 cells. Both show no time reversal breaking, in contrast to long time MBR in Fig. 6.11. This means the asymmetry between t and τ is important for MBR to detect time reversal breaking.

to the active processes. Also, the asymmetry between t and τ seems to be important to detect the time reversal breakage with MBR in cells.

6.3. Entropy production bound in cells

Now, as we have found observables that detect the break time reversal symmetry in the cell data, we can apply our results from chapter 5 to get a lower bound on entropy production. To use Eq. (5.12), we need an anti-symmetric observable whose absolute value is bounded by 1. Because we know that the optimal observable is given by the $\text{sign}(s)$, we also apply a sign function to the anti-symmetric part of MBR

$$O = \text{sign} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{x(t+\tau) - x(\tau)}{x(\tau) - x(0)} \vartheta_l(x(\tau) - x(0)) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{x(0) - x(t)}{x(t) - x(t+\tau)} \vartheta_l(x(t) - x(t+\tau)) \right). \quad (6.25)$$

Remember the normalization factor in $\vartheta_l(x) = \frac{\theta(|x|-l)}{\langle \theta(|x|-l) \rangle}$. However, we can expect that in a stationary system

$$\langle \theta(|x(\tau) - x(0)| - l) \rangle = \langle \theta(|x(t+\tau) - x(t)| - l) \rangle. \quad (6.26)$$

So we do not have to explicitly calculate this factor. Therefore, the observable simplifies to

$$O = \text{sign} \left(-\frac{(x(t+\tau) - x(t))\theta(|x(\tau) - x(0)| - l)}{x(\tau) - x(0)} + \frac{(x(0) - x(t))\theta(|x(t+\tau) - x(t)| - l)}{x(t) - x(t+\tau)} \right) \quad (6.27)$$

Figure 6.14.: The mean of the sign of the anti-symmetric part of MBR in Eq. (6.27) for different cell types for $\tau = 0.17$ s and $l = 0.002$ μm . Standard error shown by the areas which was obtained by the bootstrap method (2000 samples). For this we calculate the $\langle O \rangle_n$ for every individual trajectory and use as final mean $\langle O \rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum \langle O_n \rangle$. (a) For A549 cells and a reference measurement in Agarose, the latter is a purely passive system. One can see that the measurement for A549 deviates from 0 above the standard error, indicating the breaking of time reversal symmetry. The Agarose measurement stays close to zero. (b) The same curves for HeLa cells and drugged HeLa cells. The wild type clearly deviates from zero with high certainty, while the drugged cells fluctuate around it.

for the sign case.

Figure 6.14 shows the mean of the observable Eq. (6.27). In (a) we see the result for A549 cells and for a reference measurement in Agarose, with $\tau = 0.17$ ms and $l = 0.002$ μm . The measurement in Agarose should not show time reversal breakage, since it is a passive system. The areas show the standard error obtained from a bootstrap of the recorded data. For Agarose, $\langle O \rangle$ is close to zero, as we expect. For A549 the mean is positive, indicating that time reversal is broken. In (b) we have the same observable, however, for HeLa cells and drugged HeLa cells. For the normal HeLa cells, time reversal symmetry is broken with at least 2σ certainty, while for the drugged cells, this is at least not clearly the case, compared to the standard error.

Because Eq. (6.27) is a bounded anti-symmetric observable with $|O| = 1$, we can apply Eq. (5.12) to get a lower bound on entropy production $\langle s \rangle$. The last aspect we need to clarify is, how the entropy production depends on the times t and τ . To evaluate the observable O in Eq. (6.27), one needs at least a trajectory of length $t + \tau$. Therefore, the entropy production is a lower bound on the entropy production $\langle s(t + \tau) \rangle$. However, many possible combinations of t and τ lead to one specific $t + \tau$, which means we get several lower bounds from observables $O(\tau, t)$ for $\langle s(t + \tau) \rangle$. Figure 6.15 shows different bounds for the entropy production based on $\langle O(\tau, t) \rangle$ for HeLa cells. The x -axis shows the time $t + \tau$ and τ is color coded. All combinations of t, τ that result in the same $t + \tau$ are on a vertical line. The highest lower bound for $\langle s \rangle$ is given by the

Figure 6.15.: The entropy production bound Eq. (5.12) applied to the observable means of Fig. 6.14 for HeLa cells with $l = 0.002 \mu\text{m}$. The dots show different combinations of t and τ that add up to $t + \tau$ on the x -axis, with τ color coded. The gray dotted line shows the straight line, starting from zero, with the highest slope crossing the entropy bound. The slope then serves as a lower bound for the entropy production rate σ . In this graph $\sigma \approx 0.0014 \frac{1}{\text{s}}$. For the other cell types, this plot can be found in appendix D.

largest deviation from zero. From this, we can get an optimal bound by

$$\langle s(\tilde{t}) \rangle \geq \max_{t, \tau \text{ with } t + \tau = \tilde{t}} \langle O(\tau, t) \rangle \log \left(\frac{1 + \langle O(\tau, t) \rangle}{1 - \langle O(\tau, t) \rangle} \right). \quad (6.28)$$

Generally, one expects in a steady state that the entropy production scales linearly in time $\langle s(t) \rangle = \sigma t$, with an entropy production rate σ . We can get a lower bound for σ from Eq. (6.28) by maximizing

$$\sigma \geq \max_{t, \tau} \frac{1}{t + \tau} \langle O(\tau, t) \rangle \log \left(\frac{1 + \langle O(\tau, t) \rangle}{1 - \langle O(\tau, t) \rangle} \right). \quad (6.29)$$

In Fig. 6.14, this is illustrated by the gray dotted line. Getting the lower bound for the rate is equivalent to finding the straight line with the highest slope that connects the origin with the entropy bound dots. With the entropy production rate, we can reduce the analysis down to one number. Figure 6.16 shows on the y -axis the lower bound for entropy production rate σ for different cells. The error bars represent the 95% confidence interval of a bias corrected and accelerated bootstrap (BCa) [164]. For the bootstrap we calculate σ for a set of trajectories and then repeat for multiple randomly sampled sets. We can see that the entropy production rate is roughly of the order of $\sigma \approx 0.0015 \frac{1}{\text{s}}$. Generally, we would expect the overall entropy production inside

Figure 6.16.: The lower bound for entropy production rate σ for different cell types and Agarose. Error bars obtained via bias corrected and accelerated bootstrap (4000 samples) with confidence interval of 95% and $l = 0.002 \mu\text{m}$. The x -axis shows the effective energy amplitude, which was discussed in Section 4.3, and quantifies the FDT violation. One can see that a higher FDT violation correlates with a higher amount of time reversal breakage i.e. a higher bound on the entropy production rate.

the cell to be much higher. ATP consumption is in the order of 10^9 per second with approximately $12k_B T$ per hydrolysis [168, 169]. However, we only have access to the entropy production that is responsible for the dynamics of the one colloidal particle that we observe. This highly projected dynamics will have a much smaller entropy production by default. Secondly, we do not know how tight the bound is. Generally, we can expect to be off by multiple orders of magnitude. All in all, the absolute value of the entropy production rate does not tell us too much on its own. However, it is interesting to compare it between different cells. The σ -bound is a way to quantify the time reversal breaking in the stochastic trajectories. We can, for example, see that the wild type HeLa cells have a much higher σ -bound than the drugged HeLa cells. At the same time, the drugged cells seem to have a higher σ -bound than the Agarose reference measurement. This could be a hint that even in the drugged cells, still active processes are present. It could also be related to a decaying process due to the damage caused by the drugs.

The x -axis of Fig. 6.16 shows the effective energy amplitude, which we encountered in chapter 4. We can see here that a larger σ -bound correlates with a larger effective energy amplitude. This means that a more severe time reversal breaking could also be related to a more severe FDT violation. However, the error bars are indeed very large, which is probably also related to the large heterogeneity of the cells. So it is hard to say how strong these correlations are, and if one can make any quantitative

predictions. For example, the MDCK cells have a smaller σ -bound compared to HeLa, but a very similar effective energy amplitude. While within error bars, there might be some subtleties that have to be investigated further, for example, if there is a relation to mechanical properties.

To sum up, we have used the sign of the anti-symmetric part of MBR to derive an entropy production bound. Under the assumption of stationarity, we could also derive a bound on the entropy production rate σ . We have seen that the entropy production rate bound for wild type cells is higher compared to drugged HeLa cells, with reduced activity. We could also observe that the entropy production rate bound σ and the effective energy seem to be correlated i.e. a higher time reversal breaking tends to coincide with a higher FDT violation.

6.4. Summary

We have seen that MBR detects the broken time reversal symmetry of the motion of a colloidal particle inside the cytoplasm of a living cell. We replicated a time reversal breaking in a RHC type model where we exchanged the harmonic potential with a double well. The main reason for using a double well is that this system can, in principle, be realized in experiments, for example, using two or a very fast moving optical tweezer [133]. We omitted memory in our model, which would be required to represent a cell system more accurately. This will be the next step in extending the model. We further looked at the TRPB, which is the part of the joint displacement probability distribution that is sensitive to time reversal breaking. We figured that for MBR, it is beneficial if this distribution shows a quadrupole structure around the $|d| = l$ axis, so around the length parameter. A predominantly octopole structure was observed for the RHCDW model, which consists of two quadrupoles that are detectable by MBR. One could also define observables that are sensitive to arbitrary poles in TRBP. We showed that the octapole moment dominates for RHCDW, however, higher order pole contributions also exist. The concept of using observables that reassemble the structure of the time reversal breaking part of the probability distribution is very interesting. Because it is similar to getting the coefficients of a series expansion, one might be able to reconstruct the structure of the probability distribution with this approach, without the necessity to make a histogram. It is also intriguing whether the joint probability of displacements always has a pole structure or if other versions are also possible. This will require future studies. We have also seen that the asymmetry of t and τ seems to increase MBRs ability to detect time reversal breaking. At the moment, it is not clear why this is the case. A possible explanation is that the small τ with large t could be related to some extreme events which otherwise are suppressed, but this is only a guess. A more sophisticated analysis would be required to determine this.

Next, we looked at the anti-symmetric long time MBR in cells and analyzed the timescales of the system. We found that the time reversal breaking shows its biggest signature in the range of $l = 2 - 20$ nm and $\tau = 2 - 100$ ms, which could fit multiple cellular processes, including molecular motors. Because we lack statistics for extreme

values, the upper length scale of the length parameter could be underestimated. By comparing different types of drugged cells, we observed that if the microtubules are inhibited, the time reversal braking in MBR is severely reduced. This would suggest that the relevant processes are tied to them. More in depth and targeted experiments might reveal if the effect comes, for example, from molecular motors or other processes.

At last, we determined the entropy production bound via the mean of the sign of the anti-symmetric MBR. We found that this bound is larger for wild type HeLa cells compared to drugged versions, as one would expect from the results of MBR. Also, we observed that the entropy production bound seems to scale like FDT violations quantified by the effective energy amplitude. For the future, it would be beneficial to investigate this in more model systems.

7.

Summary, Discussion and Outlook

7.1. Summary

To summarize, we began with the initial question of whether we could distinguish the random motion of an equilibrium from a non-equilibrium Brownian particle. A necessary criterion for this is the violation of time reversal symmetry in non-equilibrium systems.

Mean Back Relaxation

We started by investigating whether MBR is a suitable observable to detect the violation of time reversal symmetry in chapter 2. MBR is the negative ratio of future displacements in time t to past displacements in time τ . We showed that under stationary conditions, the long time MBR will approach $\frac{1}{2}$ if the joint probability of the particle becomes independent for large times t , a well defined mean position exists and the system obeys the detailed balance condition. If the first two conditions are fulfilled and the long time value does not approach $\frac{1}{2}$, time reversal symmetry is broken. This can also be checked by comparing MBR evaluated from forward to time reversed trajectories. For simulations of an ABP in a harmonic potential, we demonstrated that MBR indeed shows the violation of time reversal symmetry.

For a purely Gaussian process, we derived a relation between MBR and MSD. Using this result, we got insights into the finite time t MBR, and the conditioning time τ . We saw that for an intermediate diffusive regime, MBR for a Gaussian process reaches a plateau that could be confused with a long time value, even though the real long time has not been reached. This was illustrated by the example of two harmonically coupled particles in a confining harmonic potential. To overcome this problem, we suggested a new version of MBR that builds on the fluctuating microscopic particle density function, the dMBR. In this version, we do not compare displacements of the particle but density fluctuations. In bulk, the microscopic particle density has a well defined vanishing mean for finite wavelength in Fourier space. We demonstrated that for two harmonically coupled particles with different temperatures, dMBR shows the violation of time reversal symmetry. This is remarkable because MBR of single particles cannot detect breaking of time reversal symmetry due to the Gaussian nature of the process.

At last, we analyzed the statistics of MBR by computing VBR for a Gaussian process in chapter 3. While we know that for a Gaussian process, MBR is independent of the length parameter l , VBR depends on it. Generally, VBR diverges for very small length parameters, due to division by zero in the back relaxation ratio, and for very large length parameters because the number of countable displacement events reduces. There is a value of the length l between the two extremes that minimizes VBR. As a rule of thumb, this length l is close to the square root MSD at time τ .

Application of MBR to cells and model

We applied MBR and VBR to cell data in chapter 4. We observed that MBR first rises and later decreases with t . Generally, MBR saturates to a value below $\frac{1}{2}$ for cell data. We could reproduce this behavior with the RHC model system and analyzed its τ dependence. We also compared the long time MBR with the experimentally measured effective energy and found that the effective energy amplitude and long time MBR have a linear relation. The slope of this relation is τ dependent. We also applied VBR and found that VBR from cell data does not match the Gaussian prediction. We conclude that the statistics from cell data, therefore, have strong non-Gaussian characteristics.

Entropy bound

We found an entropy bound that only relies on the mean of a bounded anti-symmetric observable in chapter 5. The bound is derived from a fluctuation theorem and does not rely on specific dynamics, such as overdamped. However, we still need local detailed balance in the sense that stochastic entropy production is given by the log ratio of path probabilities. We showed that the observable that is most tight is the signum of stochastic entropy production. This leads to a coarse graining scheme that leaves the bound intact by grouping paths according to their signum of stochastic entropy production. We illustrated and tested the entropy bound for a discrete jump process on a ring and compared it with the FTUR.

Time reversal breaking in cells and entropy bound

Lastly, we checked MBR for the time reversed cell data and applied the entropy bound in chapter 6. We found that MBR is different for forward and backward trajectories, indicating the breakage of time reversal symmetry. However, MBR and time reversed MBR do not add up to one, which means the true long time value has not been reached. By investigating the part of the displacement probability density that is responsible for time reversal breaking TRBP, we showed that MBR is sensitive to a quadrupole structure in TRBP. MBR detects time reversal breaking if the length l is close to any quadrupole at $|d|$ for which $\Delta p(b, \tau; d, \tau) \neq 0$. We studied a modification of the RHC that involved non-linear interactions, the RHCDW. In this model system, we observe time reversal breakage with MBR. We demonstrated that, in the model, the TRBP has an octapole structure. MBR therefore shows two peaks for different l , which correspond

to the two separate quadrupoles. We constructed other types of observables that make use of this multipole structure in the probability distribution. We can use them to scan for length and time scales in time reversal breaking part of the probability distribution.

For cells, we used long time MBR to scan for length and time scales. We found that the time reversal breaking is most prominent for a time scale of 2-70 ms and length scale of 2-20 nm. These roughly fit the order of magnitude for motor activity. The time reversal breaking was severely reduced by depolymerization of microtubules, which hints that the relevant active processes are tied to them.

Because we found a time anti-symmetric observable that detects time reversal breaking in living cells, we applied the entropy bound of chapter 5. We used the sign of the anti-symmetric part of MBR as an observable. We measured the bounds for multiple cell types. The lower bound for entropy production is definitely much lower than the expected entropy production within the cell. This can be explained by the highly coarse grained dynamics of the colloidal particle. The degree of time reversal breaking, expressed by entropy production, and FDT violation, given by the effective energy, seems to be correlated.

7.2. Discussion and outlook

Mean Back Relaxation

Returning to the initial question. Can we distinguish passive Brownian motion from active one using the MBR. We found both for model systems and actual cell data that MBR is a suitable marker for time reversal breaking. In this regard, there have been studies on in vitro systems, for example, actin myosin networks with nanotubes, where the time reversal breaking detected by correlation functions was also investigated for multiple length and time scales [170]. However, the effects we observed are more likely connected to the microtubules instead of the actin network. There have also been studies on this topic for larger scale systems, like hair bundle cells, where the time reversal breaking has also been shown from their dynamics. In these cases, the TUR has been applied and the FDT violations have been shown using active microreology [44, 125]. To my knowledge, the correlation between time reversal breaking entropy production bounds on one side and FDT violations on the other has not been extensively studied. However, it's rather plausible that it exists, for example, the Harada-Sasa relation states that for a simple Langevin system, the entropy production is directly given by the integral over the FDT violation [73, 140]. Thus, a higher amount of time reversal breakage, corresponding to a larger entropy production, would correspond to a larger (integral) FDT violation. Also, to my knowledge, we present here one of the first studies that directly detects time reversal breaking, in the sense that statistical properties differ for forward and reversed trajectories, of a micrometer sized colloidal particle inside the cytoplasm of living cells.

In this work, we have primarily focused on MBR of the position of one colloidal particle in one dimension. While it is surprising that MBR for positions shows some quite remarkable results, there are different directions to explore further. For scalar observables, we already introduced the density MBR. This quantity has the neat feature that we combine multiple particles and dimensions into one stochastic quantity. Also for bulk systems, we recover the MBR $\frac{1}{2}$ theorem. In our example, we have looked primarily at the Fourier transform of the density. The reason is that it is easier to determine in Fourier space for individual particle trajectories. In real space, one has to deal with delta functions or bins, which is not preferable if the system is not dense. However, it might be interesting to look at the density of actual camera data. The pixels of the camera or detector would already serve as bins. MBR could therefore also be applied to the plain camera data, or more abstractly to a real space field.

The absolute square of the Fourier transformed density is the structure factor [85]. This is one of the primary quantities obtained in scattering experiments. It would be very interesting if one could use the dynamic structure factor of an active system in MBR. Because the density MBR already shows time reversal breaking, one could hope for this to be the case. The only downside of the structure factor is that it loses the phase information of the Fourier transformed density, so it contains less information. It is therefore possible that relevant information to detect time reversal breaking with MBR can be lost. Initial studies by Laila Henkes in her Master Thesis, however, suggest that it is possible to use the structure factor, at least in some systems [171]. Technically, the structure factor does not necessarily have to be determined from scattering experiments. One could also use camera recordings and Fourier transform the resulting image, which is a technique already used by experimenters [172]. Considering the desired resolution and equipment, the latter approach might be beneficial in certain situations. This approach would also give rise to the missing phase of the density.

Another direction one can explore is to generalize MBR for vector valued quantities. We have taken some trials in this direction, however, we have not come to a final result. The easiest way, which keeps the MBR a scalar without introducing new parameters, is to rewrite MBR as

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \left\langle -\frac{\mathbf{bd}}{d^2} \vartheta_l(|\mathbf{d}|) \right\rangle \quad (7.1)$$

where \mathbf{b} is the vector displacement from time t to 0, and \mathbf{d} the displacement from $-\tau$ to 0. In this definition, we compare the future displacement from 0 to t projected on the direction of the displacement from $-\tau$ to 0. This definition has the nice feature that it collapses in the one-dimensional case to the original definition Eq. (2.5). Another possibility is to only look at the projection of the trajectory in one direction \hat{e} . MBR in this case can be direction dependent. In two dimensions, this means that $\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l, \phi)$ generally depends on an angle ϕ . This might be a useful approach to detect anisotropies in the system. Referring back to the usage in cells, it's not a priori clear that the cytoplasm is a homogeneous material. Generally, one would expect quite the opposite. If cells have a principal access, this might be visible in MBR. There have been initial studies by Sarah Lädke that show exactly this angular dependence of MBR in cells

using darkfield microscopy [173]. The last possibility we briefly discuss is to define a MBR matrix. In this case, we compare the b displacements, for example, in x -direction to the d displacements in y -direction. For general components x_i, x_j

$$\mathcal{M}_{ij}(\tau, t, l) = \left\langle -\frac{x_i(t) - x_i(0)}{x_j(0) - x_j(-\tau)} \partial_l (|x_j(0) - x_j(-\tau)|) \right\rangle. \quad (7.2)$$

With $i = j$ we get the ordinary MBR, with the MBR $\frac{1}{2}$ theorem. For $i \neq j$ the properties of this quantity are not well understood. If the x_i and x_j directions are uncorrelated, then the MBR matrix element vanishes. If they are correlated, they can have a non-vanishing value and detect time reversal breakage. Systems for which the off-diagonal terms are interesting are rotating or spinning particles, where a coupling between multiple spatial directions occurs. Further, it will depend on the chosen basis x_i and x_j . There have been preliminary studies for this quantity, as for the other ones. However, until now, there have not been any major results, which is more related to a lack of a focused study. Future investigation might find some interesting results of MBR for different spatial directions.

Entropy bound

Apart from MBR the second major result was concerning the derived entropy production bound. It has a relatively high validity, because it only requires that the entropy production can be written as the log ratio of path probabilities. In that sense, it is superior to the first iterations of TUR, which additionally require an overdamped time continuous dynamics. However, its range of validity is comparable to that of the FTUR relation. The main difference is that the observables it can be used for are a little different. The primary applications are signum observables of antisymmetric quantities, as the anti-symmetric part of MBR or a current. While one could also have continuous observables, limiting oneself to the signum type is definitely reasonable since we know that the signum of entropy production is the most ideal observable. The challenge is to find an antisymmetric observable that always has the same sign as the stochastic entropy production. The advantage of these types of observables is that they are relatively easy to construct, and one only needs to measure their mean. On the other hand, one can not assume that these observables track the full extent of the dynamics.

Missing in the earlier discussion is an interpretation of the bound. The TUR is usually related to precision, for example, how precisely a clock runs. The signum observables that can be constructed using the bound derived in this thesis have a yes-no structure. For example, was entropy production positive? Did the clock run forward? The only important part is that if the answer in the forward trajectory is yes, the answer in the backward trajectory is no. The relevant antisymmetric observables are then constructed as returning -1 and 1 (we ignore here that the answer can also be neither of the two given choices, which would correspond to zero). In simple terms, the entropy bound

Eq. (5.12) measures how much entropy production is at least required to make yes more likely than no. Or in the case of the clock, how much entropy production does one need at least to make the clock run forward more likely than backward? These types of questions are encoded in the signum observables. This is a little different from asking for the precision. However, the concepts have, of course, similarities. If a clock is significantly more likely to run forward in a time frame, then it's also reasonable that it is more precise.

For real world applications, the question of the tightness of the bound remains an important question if one tries to infer the entropy production. Generally, one has to say, one can not expect Eq. (5.12) to give an accurate estimate of entropy production, and usually will underestimate it by several orders of magnitude. However, the issue can also occur with other bounds, such as TUR. The bound can still be useful by comparing different systems, as we have done for the various cell types. The only important part is that the time reversal breaking, which is essentially quantified by the bound, scales here with the scale of the activity in the system. The comparison with the results from the FDT violations suggests that there might be a connection.

Going beyond MBR

At last, we may ask what other types of observables are also possible. In chapter 6, we constructed for the RHCDW model a new type of observable that tries to align with the structure of the time reversal breaking part of the displacement probability distribution TRBP. Because these observables are similar to determining coefficients of basis functions i.e. we try to decompose the time reversal breaking part into basis functions, they may be a very interesting way to learn about time reversal breaking length and timescales in the system. The major challenge here is to find a suitable set of basis functions. This will depend on which typical shapes TRBP displays, like the poles we saw for RHCDW. This direction may also be a very interesting pathway to explore in the future.

7.3. Final Remarks

The thesis has primarily focused on the development and application of MBR. A main avenue of future theoretical investigations will focus on the density MBR and similar quantities to enable new experimental workflows, like scattering experiments and multi-particle tracking. The investigation of length and time scales of biophysical systems will be a promising application of this work. One primary challenge to solve to date is the many parameters MBR depends on, like t, τ, l, q , and so on. It is not always clear how these parameters relate to each other. As a general curiosity, it would also be interesting to look at completely different systems, for example, from non-linear dynamics, quantum mechanics, or financial markets, and how MBR relates to typical quantities used in those respective fields. While we have a well developed understanding of Gaussian systems. What we lack is a deep understanding of how to

tackle non-Gaussian systems analytically and efficiently compute corrections to MBR from the Gaussian case. Such a derivation could reveal how MBR responds to various interparticle interactions and driving. Independent of which pathways are chosen, there are many interesting roads to explore. As the Klingons say - Dajqu' tuch. Qapla'!

A.

Mean Back Relaxation

A.1. Eq. (2.13) for general observable

We state the assumptions of Eqs. (2.8) and (2.9) for a general phase space observable A ,

$$\langle A \rangle = \int dA A W_1(A) \text{ with } \langle A \rangle \text{ finite} \quad (\text{A.1a})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} W_3(A_t, t; A_0, 0; A_{-\tau}, -\tau) \\ = W_1(A_t) W_2(A_0, 0; A_{-\tau}, -\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1b})$$

We also repeat the symmetry condition for W_2 [40]

$$W_2(A_t, t; A_0, 0) = W_2(\epsilon A_0, t; \epsilon A_t, 0), \quad (\text{A.2})$$

denoted as the usual condition for detailed balance for the joint distribution in Ref. [26]. We assume that A is either symmetric ($\epsilon = 1$) or antisymmetric ($\epsilon = -1$) under path reversal.

Assuming Eq. (A.2) and stationarity, one can use that $W_1(A) = \int dA_t W_2(A_t, t; A, 0) = \int dA_0 W_2(A, t; A_0, 0)$ to find

$$\begin{aligned} \langle A \rangle &= \int dA_t dA_0 A_0 W_2(A_t, t; A_0, 0) \\ &= \int dA_t dA_0 \epsilon A_t W_2(A_t, t; A_0, 0) \\ &= \epsilon \langle A \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

We proceed as in the main text, we start by the definition of the MBR and insert Eq. (A.1) for the long time limit

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} 2\mathcal{M}^A(\tau, t, l) &\stackrel{(\text{A.1})}{=} \int dA_0 dA_{-\tau} \left(-\frac{\langle A \rangle - A_0}{A_0 - A_{-\tau}} \right) \\ &\times \vartheta_l(|A_0 - A_{-\tau}|) W_2(A_0, 0; A_{-\tau}, -\tau) \\ &+ \int dA_0 dA_{-\tau} \left(-\frac{\langle A \rangle - \epsilon A_{-\tau}}{\epsilon A_{-\tau} - \epsilon A_0} \right) \\ &\times \vartheta_l(|\epsilon A_0 - \epsilon A_{-\tau}|) W_2(\epsilon A_{-\tau}, 0; \epsilon A_0, -\tau). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

We used the coordinate transform $A_0 \rightarrow \epsilon A_{-\tau}$ and $A_{-\tau} \rightarrow \epsilon A_0$ in the second summand. By adding a zero in the counter of the second summand and algebraic transformations one gets, using Eq. (A.3)

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}^A(\tau, t, l) &= \frac{1}{2} \int dA_0 dA_{-\tau} \frac{A_0 - A_{-\tau}}{A_0 - A_{-\tau}} \\ &\times \vartheta_l(|A_0 - A_{-\tau}|) W_2(\epsilon A_{-\tau}, 0; \epsilon A_0, -\tau) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \int dA_0 dA_{-\tau} \left(-\frac{\langle A \rangle - A_0}{A_0 - A_{-\tau}} \right) \vartheta_l(|A_0 - A_{-\tau}|) \\ &\times [W_2(A_0, 0; A_{-\tau}, -\tau) - W_2(\epsilon A_{-\tau}, 0; \epsilon A_0, -\tau)] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The first term is evaluated as $\frac{1}{2}$ because of the normalization $\langle \vartheta_l(|A_0 - A_{-\tau}|) \rangle = 1$. Using Eq. (A.2) we find that the second term vanishes and obtain

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}^A(\tau, t, l) \stackrel{(\text{A.1}) \& (\text{A.2})}{=} \frac{1}{2}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

A.2. Simulations

Simulations are performed with the Julia "Differential Equations" package with a Runge-Kutta-Milstein method (RKMil) without adaptive time stepping. Internal time step is $dt = 10^{-3}$ and the particle position is saved at $\Delta t = 10^{-2}$ in units of the simulation time scale. The simulations are performed in dimensionless space and time. For the active Brownian particle length is given in units of $\sqrt{\frac{\gamma D}{k}}$ and time in units of $\frac{\gamma}{k}$. Therefore the following dimensionless SDEs were simulated (compare Eq. (2.20))

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = -\mathbf{x} + \frac{v_0}{\sqrt{\frac{k}{\gamma D} D}} \hat{\mathbf{e}}(\varphi) + \mathbf{f} \quad (\text{A.7a})$$

$$\dot{\varphi} = f_\varphi \quad (\text{A.7b})$$

with $\langle f^{(i)}(t) f^{(j)}(t') \rangle = 2\delta(t-t')\delta_{ij}$ and $\langle f_\varphi(t) f_\varphi(t') \rangle = 2\frac{D_\varphi \gamma}{k} \delta(t-t')$. These equations thus involve two dimensionless parameters, $v_0 / \left(\sqrt{\frac{k}{\gamma D} D} \right)$ and $\frac{D_\varphi \gamma}{k}$.

For the coupled particles of Eq. (2.39), we scale length in terms of $\sqrt{\frac{k_B T}{k}}$ and time in terms of $\frac{\gamma_1}{k}$. The dimensionless equations are (compare Eq. (2.39))

$$\dot{x}_1 = -\frac{k'}{k} x_1 - (x_1 - x_2) + f_1(t) \quad (\text{A.8a})$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -\frac{k'}{k} \frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} x_2 - \frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} (x_2 - x_1) + f_2(t) \quad (\text{A.8b})$$

with $\langle f_1(t) f_1(t') \rangle = 2\delta(t-t')$ and $\langle f_2(t) f_2(t') \rangle = 2\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} \frac{T+\Delta T}{T} \delta(t-t')$ which depend on the dimensionless parameters $\frac{\gamma_2}{\gamma_1}$, $\frac{T+\Delta T}{T}$ and $\frac{k'}{k}$.

Figures 1-3 have a trajectory length of $t = 10^5$ in units of the simulation time scale with 80 trajectories, inset Figure 2 trajectory length of $t = 10^4$ with 1400 trajectories. Long time MBR in Figure 2 and 3 are evaluated at $t = 40$. Figure 5, main, has a trajectory length of $t = 10^4$ and 80 trajectories, and inset trajectory length of $t = 400$ and 800 trajectories. Figure 5 long time MBR evaluated at $t = 1000$.

A.3. Two coupled particles in harmonic potential

The Langevin equations of the two linearly coupled particles, discussed in section 2.6.2, are given by

$$\dot{x}_1 = -\frac{k'}{\gamma_1}x_1 - \frac{k}{\gamma_1}(x_1 - x_2) + f_1 \quad (\text{A.9a})$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -\frac{k'}{\gamma_2}x_2 - \frac{k}{\gamma_2}(x_2 - x_1) + f_2 \quad (\text{A.9b})$$

which is rewritten into the matrix equation

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = -\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{f} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

with

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{k'+k}{\gamma_1} & -\frac{k}{\gamma_1} \\ -\frac{k}{\gamma_2} & \frac{k'+k}{\gamma_2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

which has the general solution

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-\mathbf{M}(t-s)} \cdot \mathbf{f}(s) ds. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

To solve this equation we diagonalize \mathbf{M} with the eigenvalues

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{1/2} &= \frac{(k' + k)(\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)}{2\gamma_1\gamma_2} \\ &\pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{(k' + k)(\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)}{2\gamma_1\gamma_2}\right)^2 - \frac{k'^2 + 2kk'}{\gamma_1\gamma_2}} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

and corresponding eigenvectors $(1, \frac{k'}{k} + 1 - \frac{\gamma_1}{k}\lambda_i)^\top = (1, a(\lambda_i))^\top$. After basis transform one gets the following expression

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(t) &= \frac{1}{a(\lambda_2) - a(\lambda_1)} \\ &\int_{-\infty}^t \left[(a(\lambda_2)e^{-\lambda_1(t-s)} - a(\lambda_1)e^{-\lambda_2(t-s)}) f_1(s) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (-e^{\lambda_1(t-s)} + e^{\lambda_2(t-s)}) f_2(s) \right] ds. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

From here we can evaluate the correlation function

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x_1(t)x_1(0) \rangle = & \\ \frac{k_B T}{k} & \left[\left(\phi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \left(1 + \frac{\Delta T}{T} \right) \psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \right) e^{-\lambda_1 t} \right. \\ & \left. + \left(\phi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) + \left(1 + \frac{\Delta T}{T} \right) \psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) \right) e^{-\lambda_2 t} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

with dimensionless

$$\phi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = \frac{k^3}{\gamma_1^3} \frac{1}{(\lambda_2 - \lambda_1)^2} \left(\frac{a(\lambda_2)^2}{\lambda_1} - \frac{2a(\lambda_1)a(\lambda_2)}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2} \right) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = \frac{k^3}{\gamma_1^3 \gamma_2} \frac{1}{(\lambda_2 - \lambda_1)^2} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_1} - \frac{2}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2} \right) \quad (\text{A.17})$$

The mean squared displacement is obtained by the identity

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta x^2(t) &= \langle (x(t) - x(0))^2 \rangle \\ &= 2 \langle x^2 \rangle - 2 \langle x(t)x(0) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

and we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta x_1^2(t) &= \frac{2k_B T}{k} \left[\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)(1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)(1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t}) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

with $\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = \phi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + (1 + \frac{\Delta T}{T})\psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$. The relation is rewritten into the timescales $\tau_i = \frac{1}{\lambda_i}$. In the main text we investigate the case $k' \ll k$. In this case the first time scale $\tau_1 = \frac{1}{\lambda_1}$ approaches

$$\lim_{k'/k \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\lambda_1} = \frac{1}{k} \frac{\gamma_1 \gamma_2}{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

However in the same limit

$$\lim_{k'/k \rightarrow 0} \lambda_2 = 0 \quad (\text{A.21})$$

so the second time scale diverges as one would expect. It diverges with a power law

$$\lim_{k'/k \rightarrow 0} \frac{k'}{k} \tau_2 = \lim_{k'/k \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{k'}{k}}{\lambda_2} = \frac{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2}{2k} \quad (\text{A.22})$$

which means $\tau_2 \approx \frac{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2}{2k'}$. On time scales $\tau_1 \ll t \ll \tau_2$ we approach a diffusive regime

for which we can find a diffusion coefficient by expanding in terms of $\lambda_2 t$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta x_1^2(t) = \frac{2k_B T}{k} & \left[\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)(1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) \right. \\ & \left. + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)\lambda_2 t + \mathcal{O}(\lambda_2^2 t^2) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

where we identify $D_L = \frac{k_B T}{k} \lambda_2 \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)$ as the diffusion coefficient. In the limit $\frac{k'}{k} \rightarrow 0$ one gets

$$D \approx \frac{k_B T}{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2} + \frac{k_B \Delta T \gamma_2}{(\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)^2} \quad (\text{A.24})$$

B.

Variance of Back Relaxation

For purely Gaussian random variables, MBR only depends on the conditioning time τ and t , and is length parameter independent. The length parameter dependence enters when we consider VBR. First, we need to define the fluctuating back relaxation

$$\mathcal{B} = -\frac{x(t) - x(0)}{x(0) - x(-\tau)} \vartheta_l(x(0) - x(-\tau)) = -\frac{b}{d} \vartheta_l(d) \quad (\text{B.1})$$

with $\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle$. We assume that the joint process of b and d is also given by a Gaussian process. In this case the conditioned distribution is given by [174]

$$p(b|d) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \frac{(b+d\mathcal{B})^2}{\sigma^2}} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

with $\sigma^2 = \Delta x^2(t) - \Delta x^2(\tau) \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - \frac{\Delta x^2(t+\tau) - \Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}\right) = \Delta x^2(t) - \Delta x^2(\tau) \mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t)$, with the mean squared displacement (MSD) $\Delta x^2(t) = \langle (x(t) - x(0))^2 \rangle$. Because the variance σ^2 needs to be positive, $\alpha = \frac{1}{\mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t)} \frac{\Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)} > 1$. Note that in the Gaussian case MBR is independent of l . From here we proceed to calculate the distribution of the back relaxation

$$p(\mathcal{B}) = \int d d d b \delta\left(\mathcal{B} + \frac{b}{d} \vartheta_l(d)\right) p(b|d) p(d) \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$= \int d d p\left(\frac{\mathcal{B} d}{\vartheta_l(d)} \middle| d\right) p(d) \frac{d}{\vartheta_l(d)} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Using Eq. (B.2) and the Gaussian probability distribution

$$p(d) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\Delta x^2(\tau)}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

for the general displacements we can calculate VBR

$$\text{VBR}(\tau, t, l) = \langle \mathcal{B}^2 \rangle - \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle^2 \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$= \int dd \frac{\sigma^2 \vartheta_l^2(d)}{d^2} p(d) + \frac{\mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t)}{\text{erfc}\left(\frac{l}{\sqrt{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}\right)} - \mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t) \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$= \frac{\sigma^2}{\langle \theta(|d| - l) \rangle^2} \int dd \frac{\theta(|d| - l)}{d^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\Delta x_\tau^2}} e^{-\frac{d^2}{2\Delta x_\tau^2}} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$+ \mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t) \left(\frac{1}{\text{erfc}\left(\frac{l}{\sqrt{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}\right)} - 1 \right)$$

where we inserted $\vartheta_l(d) = \frac{\theta(|d|-l)}{\langle \theta(|d|-l) \rangle}$. The remaining terms can be solved using the Gaussian error functions to get

$$\text{VBR}(\tau, t, l) = \frac{\sigma^2}{\text{erfc}\left(\frac{l}{\sqrt{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}\right)^2} \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{e^{-\frac{l^2}{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}}{\sqrt{\Delta x^2(\tau)} l} - \frac{1}{\Delta x^2(\tau)} \text{erfc}\left(\frac{l}{\sqrt{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}\right) \right) \quad (\text{B.9})$$

$$+ \mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t) \left(\frac{1}{\text{erfc}\left(\frac{l}{\sqrt{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}\right)} - 1 \right) \quad (\text{B.10})$$

$$= \frac{\sigma^2}{\Delta x^2(\tau)} \frac{1}{\text{erfc}(\eta)^2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{e^{-\eta^2}}{\eta} - \text{erfc}(\eta) \right) + \mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t) \left(\frac{1}{\text{erfc}(\eta)} - 1 \right) \quad (\text{B.11})$$

$$= \left(\frac{\Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)} - \mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t) \right) \frac{1}{\text{erfc}(\eta)^2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{e^{-\eta^2}}{\eta} - \text{erfc}(\eta) \right) \quad (\text{B.12})$$

$$+ \mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t) \left(\frac{1}{\text{erfc}(\eta)} - 1 \right)$$

$$= \mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t) [(\alpha - 1) g(\eta) + h(\eta)] \quad (\text{B.13})$$

with a dimensionless $\eta = \frac{l}{\sqrt{2\Delta x^2(\tau)}}$, $\alpha = \frac{1}{\mathcal{M}^2(\tau, t)} \frac{\Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)}$ and the η dependent functions

$g(\eta) = \frac{1}{\text{erfc}(\eta)^2} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{e^{-\eta^2}}{\eta} - \text{erfc}(\eta) \right)$ and $h(\eta) = \frac{1}{\text{erfc}(\eta)} - 1$. Again note that $\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \langle \mathcal{B} \rangle$.

The expression $g(\eta)$ can be minimized numerically with $\eta_{\min}^{(g)} \approx 0.654334$. To get an approximation for the minimum of VBR up to first order in $y = \frac{1}{\alpha-1}$ we express the

derivative of VBR

$$\frac{d\text{VBR}}{d\eta} = \mathcal{M}^2 \left(\frac{1}{y} g'(\eta_{\min}) + h'(\eta_{\min}) \right) \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \quad (\text{B.14})$$

$$\Rightarrow 0 = g'(\eta_{\min}(y)) + yh'(\eta_{\min}(y)) \quad (\text{B.15})$$

Expand the last expression around $y = 0$ to linear order and use $\eta(y) - \eta(0) = y\eta'(0) + \mathcal{O}(y^2)$

$$0 = g'(\eta_{\min}(0)) + g''(\eta_{\min}(0))(\eta_{\min}(y) - \eta_{\min}(0)) + h'(\eta_{\min}(0))y + \mathcal{O}(y^2). \quad (\text{B.16})$$

At last $\eta_{\min}(0) = \eta_{\min}^{(g)}$ and therefore $g'(\eta_{\min}(0)) = 0$

$$\eta_{\min}(y) = \eta_{\min}^{(g)} - \frac{h'(\eta_{\min}^{(g)})}{g''(\eta_{\min}^{(g)})} y + \mathcal{O}(y^2) \quad (\text{B.17})$$

$$= \eta_{\min}^{(g)} - \frac{h'(\eta_{\min}^{(g)})}{g''(\eta_{\min}^{(g)})} \frac{1}{\alpha - 1} + \mathcal{O}((\alpha - 1)^{-2}) \quad (\text{B.18})$$

The expansion coefficients can be determined as $h'(\hat{\eta}_{\min}) = 5.84259$ and $g''(\hat{\eta}_{\min}) = 6.71207$.

C.

Random horse and cart model

C.1. Mean Back Relaxation

The mean back relaxation (MBR) is related to the mean squared displacement $\Delta x^2(t) = \langle (x(t) - x(0))^2 \rangle$ because the statistics of the overall system is Gaussian

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t, l) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\Delta x^2(t + \tau) - \Delta x^2(t)}{\Delta x^2(\tau)} \right) \quad (\text{C.1})$$

which is independent of the length parameter l . We, therefore, drop this index for brevity. To get the mean squared displacement we rewrite the equations into relative coordinates $r_1 = x_1 - x_2$ and $r_2 = x_1 - q$

$$\dot{r}_1 = -k_1 \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_1} + \frac{1}{\gamma_2} \right) r_1 - \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} r_2 + \xi_{r_1}(t) \quad (\text{C.2a})$$

$$\dot{r}_2 = -\frac{k_1}{\gamma_1} r_1 - \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} r_2 + \xi_{r_2}(t) \quad (\text{C.2b})$$

$$\dot{q} = \xi_q(t) \quad (\text{C.2c})$$

with $\xi_{r_1} = \xi_1(t) - \xi_2(t)$ and $\xi_{r_2}(t) = \xi_1(t) - \xi_q(t)$ The relative coordinates can be solved using the matrix equation

$$\mathbf{r}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t e^{\mathbf{M}(t-s)} \xi_{\mathbf{r}}(s) ds \quad (\text{C.3})$$

with

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} -k_1 \left(\frac{1}{\gamma_1} + \frac{1}{\gamma_2} \right) & -\frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \\ -\frac{k_1}{\gamma_1} & -\frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{C.4})$$

After diagonalizing \mathbf{M} and computing the correlation functions, the mean squared displacement of the particle x_1 is found by $\Delta x_1^2(t) = \langle (r_2(t) + q(t) - r_2(0) - q(0))^2 \rangle$

$$\begin{aligned} \beta k_2 \Delta x_1^2(t) = & 2 \frac{D_q}{D_1} \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} t + \left(f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \frac{D_q}{D_1} \right) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) \\ & + \left(f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) + g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) \frac{D_q}{D_1} \right) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t}) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

with time scales

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{1,2} = & \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{k_1}{k_2} + \frac{\gamma_1 k_1}{\gamma_2 k_2} \right. \\ & \left. \pm \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{k_1}{k_2} + \frac{\gamma_1 k_1}{\gamma_2 k_2} \right)^2 - 4 \frac{\gamma_1 k_1}{\gamma_2 k_2}} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.6})$$

and constants

$$f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = 2 \frac{\frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} - \lambda_2}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} \quad (\text{C.7})$$

$$g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = 2 \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \frac{(\lambda_2 - \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1})(\lambda_2 + \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1})}{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)\lambda_1} \quad (\text{C.8})$$

By introducing the coefficients $\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \frac{D_q}{D_1}$

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t}) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})}{2 \frac{D_q}{D_1} \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} \tau + \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})}. \quad (\text{C.9})$$

In the limit $\tau \rightarrow 0$ we obtain

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau \rightarrow 0, t) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\lambda_1 \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 t}) + \lambda_2 \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 t})}{2 \frac{D_q}{D_1} \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} + \lambda_1 \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \lambda_2 \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)} \quad (\text{C.10})$$

and in the long time limit $t \rightarrow \infty$ this expression simplifies to

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau \rightarrow 0, t \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{D_q}{D_1} \right) \quad (\text{C.11})$$

C.2. Maximum of MBR

The MBR has for certain parameters $\frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2}, \frac{k_1}{k_2}$ a maximum in t which one can obtain by

setting the derivative of Eq.(C.9) to zero. The result is given by

$$t_{\max} = \frac{1}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} \log \left(-\frac{\lambda_1 \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau})}{\lambda_2 \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})} \right). \quad (\text{C.12})$$

However, not for every time scales λ_1, λ_2 there is a finite time solution as is illustrated in Fig. 4.4 because the expression in the log can be negative or smaller than 1. For activities smaller than

$$\frac{D_q}{D_1} < \frac{(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)\lambda_2}{\frac{k_2}{\gamma_1} + \lambda_1} \quad (\text{C.13})$$

there is no maximum, which is remarkably independent of τ . Also for too high activities there is no maximum, which we find by setting $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{d}{dt} \mathcal{M}(\tau, t) \stackrel{!}{=} 0$

$$\frac{D_q}{D_1} > -\frac{\lambda_1 f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + \lambda_2 f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})}{\lambda_1 g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) (1 - e^{-\lambda_1 \tau}) + \lambda_2 g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) (1 - e^{-\lambda_2 \tau})}, \quad (\text{C.14})$$

however, this bound is τ dependent. In the limit $\tau \rightarrow 0$ we obtain Eq. (4.8).

C.3. Critical activity

The critical activity is given by the ration of active to passive diffusion $\frac{D_q}{D}$, for which the long time MBR gets negative and has a local minimum. This property depends on the timescales of the system λ_1 and λ_2 . The long time MBR for $\tau \gg \lambda_1, \lambda_2$ is given by

$$\mathcal{M}(\tau, t \rightarrow \infty) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{2 \frac{D_q}{D_1} \tau + \Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}. \quad (\text{C.15})$$

Because $\frac{D_q}{D_1} > 0$ the sign of the long time MBR is determined by the sign of $\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)$. Using $\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) = f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \frac{D_q}{D_1} g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$ we find for the critical activity $\Psi(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + \Psi(\lambda_2, \lambda_1) = 0$

$$\frac{D_q}{D} = -\frac{f(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + f(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)}{g(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) + g(\lambda_2, \lambda_1)} \quad (\text{C.16})$$

C.4. Effective energy

The diffusing potential with memory can be described by the following Langevin equations

$$\dot{x}_1 = -\frac{k_1}{\gamma_1}(x_1 - x_2) - \frac{k_2}{\gamma_1}(x_1 - q) + \xi_1(t) \quad (\text{C.17a})$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -\frac{k_1}{\gamma_2}(x_2 - x_1) + \xi_2(t) \quad (\text{C.17b})$$

$$\dot{q} = \xi_q \quad (\text{C.17c})$$

with x_1 the tracer particle, x_2 the bath particle that mimics the viscoelastic environment and q the trap position. The system is projected onto x_1 coordinate and by integrating out the bath particle a generalized Langevin equation can be found by

$$-k_2 x(t) + \int_{-\infty}^t \Gamma(t-s) \dot{x}(s) = k_2 q(t) + f(t) \quad (\text{C.18})$$

with a Gaussian random force $\langle f(t)f(t') \rangle = k_B T \Gamma(|t-t'|)$. The correlation function in Fourier space is therefore given by

$$\langle x(\omega)x(-\omega) \rangle = \frac{k_2^2 \langle q(\omega)q(-\omega) + \langle f(\omega)f(-\omega) \rangle \rangle}{\omega^2 \Gamma(\omega)\Gamma(-\omega) + k_2^2 + ik_2 \omega (\Gamma(\omega) - \Gamma(-\omega))} \quad (\text{C.19})$$

To get the effective energy we compare the correlation function with the active driving q to the correlation function without the active driving and obtain

$$\frac{E_{\text{eff}}(\omega)}{k_B T} = 1 + \frac{k_2^2 \langle q(\omega)q(-\omega) \rangle}{\langle f(\omega)f(-\omega) \rangle} \quad (\text{C.20})$$

$$= 1 + \frac{k_2^2 \langle q(\omega)q(-\omega) \rangle}{k_B T \tilde{\Gamma}(\omega)} \quad (\text{C.21})$$

$$= 1 + \frac{D_q k_2^2}{D \gamma_1} \frac{1}{\omega^2} \frac{1}{\tilde{\Gamma}(\omega)} \quad (\text{C.22})$$

with $\tilde{\Gamma}(\omega)$ the Fourier transform of $\Gamma(|t|)$ and the Fourier transform of the free diffusion $\langle q(\omega)q(-\omega) \rangle = \frac{D_q}{\omega^2}$ with $D = \frac{k_B T}{\gamma_1}$. For the model system the memory kernel is given by

$$\Gamma(t) = \left[2\gamma_1 \delta(t) + k_1 e^{-\frac{k_1}{\gamma_2} t} \right] \theta(t) \quad (\text{C.23})$$

with the Fourier transform $\tilde{\Gamma}(\omega) = \gamma_1 + \frac{k_1^2}{\gamma_2} \frac{1}{\frac{k_1^2}{\gamma_2} + \omega^2}$ we get the final expression for the effective energy in the main text that scales with $\frac{D_q}{D}$.

D.

Entropy bound in cells - Supplementary plots

The experimental details can be found in Ref. [2]. Multiple trajectories for different cells and media have been recorded A549 ($N = 179$), C2C12 ($N = 177$), CT26 ($N = 173$), Drugged ($N = 75$), HeLa ($N = 231$), HoxB8 ($N = 170$), MDCK ($N = 183$), Agarose ($N = 27$), HeLa CytoB ($N = 60$) and HeLa Nocoda ($N = 63$) with a sampling rate of 1.57×10^{-5} s. For A549, the trajectory lengths lie between 3 s - 10 s with an average of 8.7 s. For HoxB8, the trajectory lengths lie between 5 s - 10 s with an average of 5.6 s. For all other cells and media, the trajectory lengths are exactly 10 s.

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Declaration on the use of ChatGPT and comparable tools

In this thesis, I have used the GWDG Chat AI service (Gemma 3) for brainstorming, proofreading, and optimization of self-written text passages. Further, I used Grammarly for proofreading and optimization of self-written text passages. I have also used the GWDG CoCo AI Service (Qwen 2.5 coder) for the development and optimization of software code. I hereby declare that I have stated all uses completely.